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Interpretation of the prologue

For the final seminar in our book-club we are going back to the prologue. I think this is the best way to approach the work – the prologue is quite hard to grasp and understand without having read the book; *why is earth the quintessence of the human condition?* It's one of those introductions that also works as an epilogue, and having read the book we can now return to it to fully understand what Arendt is trying to say in her masterpiece. As the prologue is only 6 pages, I will approach it by lifting individual quotes and give my interpretation of what Arendt is saying, and to what section of the book she is referring.

In 1957, an earth-born object made by man was launched into the universe, where for some weeks it circled the earth according to the same laws of gravitation that swing and keep in motion the celestial bodies—the sun, the moon, and the stars. To be sure, the man-made satellite was no moon or star, no heavenly body which could follow its circling path for a time span that to us mortals, bound by earthly time, lasts from eternity to eternity. Yet, for a time it managed to stay in the skies; it dwelt and moved in the proximity of the heavenly bodies as though it had been admitted tentatively to their sublime company

This is the beginning that often confuse new readers. Why would Arendt begin her study of our active life by addressing Sputnik? Having read the entirety of the book we should now understand why. For, as she claims in the final section, our ability to *action* is repressed by modernity and has been replaced by the scientific/fabrication process that move humanity towards some greater future – it is here, in the very beginning of the book, that Arendt gives her own interpretation of what that future is: a cosmological humanity. Thus, *Sputnik is the definition of modernity's replacement of action with process*, and a dire threat to the human condition as it's been given to us.

But, curiously enough, this joy was not triumphal; it was not pride or awe at the tremendousness of human power and mastery which filled the hearts of men, who now, when they looked up from the earth toward the skies, could behold there a thing of their own making.

I think this is Arendt being poetic, as usual. She claims in the final part that we can't understand anything without turning it into the mold of fabrication, so that the unknown becomes known to us by our own hands. In this quote that unknown is *the very heaven* that now is *sky*. As the Soviet atheist propaganda poster portraying Gagarin claimed: "I See No God up here". Sputnik is not only the symbol of modernity's form of action, but also modernity's secularization and reduction of everything into a process, including spirituality and faith.

The immediate reaction, expressed on the spur of the moment, was relief about the first "step toward escape from men's imprisonment to the earth." And this strange statement, far from being the accidental slip of some American reporter, unwittingly echoed the extraordinary line which, more than twenty years ago, had been carved on the funeral obelisk for one of Russia's great scientists: "Mankind will not remain bound to the earth forever."

A foretaste of Arendt's claim about processual thinking and becoming, and the danger inherent in it. I believe that Arendt, writing the book in 1958, implies that "one of Russia's great scientists" can be understood as "one of Communism's great scientists," and there's a totalitarian aspect to processual thinking, as she claims in *Origins of Totalitarianism*.

[A]lthough Christians have spoken of the earth as a vale of tears and philosophers have looked upon their body as a prison of mind or soul, nobody in the history of mankind has ever conceived of the earth as a prison for men's bodies or shown such eagerness to go literally from here to the moon. Should the emancipation and secularization of the modern age, which began with a turning-away, not necessarily from God, but from a god who was the Father of men in heaven, end with an even more fateful repudiation of an Earth who was the Mother of all living creatures under the sky?

I connect this to Arendt's concept of *Amor Mundi*, and action as a form of validation of the world that is around us. Because, in one of the great statements in the entire books...:

The earth is the very quintessence of the human condition, and earthly nature, for all we know, may be unique in the universe in providing human beings with a habitat in which they can move and breathe without effort and without artifice

We are bound to earth as our natural public sphere. Earth is the entity that enables us to be thrown into the world as beings-in-ourselves and be truly free and plural. When we abandon earth (or destroy it) we necessitate an active manipulation of our bodies and the world we can *be* in, and thereby reduce all our surroundings into *work*, and achieve the promise of modernity to make the world known to us by reducing it into something known and 'at-hand'.

The human artifice of the world separates human existence from all mere animal environment, but life itself is outside this artificial world, and through life man remains related to all other living organisms.

As earth is our own truly *existentially given* public sphere, it's where we can appear and be political, and not be the slaves or animals in the private sphere of the household. When we turn earth into a piece of fabrication we remove the distinction between public/private, known/unknown, and thereby achieve the massification of modernity's 'The Social'.

It is the same desire to escape from imprisonment to the earth that is manifest in the attempt to create life in the test tube, in the desire to mix "frozen germ plasm from people of demonstrated ability under the microscope to produce superior human beings" and "to alter [their] size, shape and function"; and the wish to escape the human condition, I suspect, also underlies the hope to extend man's life-span far beyond the hundred-year limit.

Explication of the claim introduced above, that modernity and modernity's scientific epistemology is being turned on humanity itself and reduce the randomness and 'thrownness' of our being, which is a direct threat to our plurality and action. Summary by Arendt:

This future man, whom the scientists tell us they will produce in no more than a hundred years, seems to be possessed by a rebellion against human existence as it has been given, a free gift from nowhere (secularly speaking), which he wishes to exchange, as it were, for something he has made himself. There is no reason to doubt our abilities to accomplish such an exchange, just as there is no reason to doubt our present ability to destroy all organic life on earth.

I do not think it's a coincidence that Arendt compares this destruction of the randomness of thrownness with a nuclear holocaust. Both would entail the destruction of humanity and life in different ways – one biological the second existential. Which is why she turns to politics:

The question is only whether we wish to use our new scientific and technical knowledge in this direction, and this question cannot be decided by scientific means; it is a political question of the first order and therefore can hardly be left to the decision of professional scientists or professional politicians.

As she claimed in the final section, scientists and professional politicians are both engaged in forms of fabrication and not action, and can therefore not be trusted with the existential (and biological) future of humanity.

The trouble concerns the fact that the "truths" of the modern scientific world view, though they can be demonstrated in mathematical formulas and proved technologically, will no longer lend themselves to normal expression in speech and thought. The moment these "truths" are spoken of conceptually and coherently, the resulting statements will be "not perhaps as meaningless as a 'triangular circle,' but much more so than a 'winged lion'".

I see the above as a small foretaste on her claim that politics must be phenomenological and embodied, and can't be understood through any "objective" perspectives as claimed by the logical positivists or mathematicians. As she is quick to explicate in the book, we can't escape the human condition, we may try to change and operate on it, but we can never find an actual universal 'Archimedean Point,' we may only try to act as such. She implies this argument:

But it could be that we, who are earth-bound creatures and have begun to act as though we were dwellers of the universe, will forever be unable to understand, that is, to think and speak about the things which nevertheless we are able to do. In this case, it would be as though our brain, which constitutes the physical, material condition of our thoughts, were unable to follow what we do, so that from now on we would indeed need artificial machines to do our thinking and speaking.

If we try to reduce politics into some "objective" criteria then we will be engaging in *cognition* and not *thinking*, and we can well expect ourselves to be replaced by the giant calculating machines who are better to process cognition than we could ever be.

If it should turn out to be true that knowledge (in the modern sense of know-how) and thought have parted company for good, then we would indeed become the helpless slaves, not so much of our machines as of our know-how, thoughtless creatures at the mercy of every gadget which is technically possible, no matter how murderous it is.

Here she combines the arguments for our ontological decline (brought on by science & rational politics) and our reduction of thinking into cognition. If that situation is ever to occur then we will continue the scientific process while lacking the ability to even approach it from a fully subjective, *and therefore political*, way. We become the de-politicized slaves in a process we will never be able to fully understand. This is obviously political questions of the highest level, but Arendt doesn't focus on its obvious connection politics, instead she detours to language:

However, even apart from these last and yet uncertain consequences, the situation created by the sciences is of great political significance. Wherever the relevance of speech is at stake, matters become political by definition, for speech is what makes man a political being. If we would follow the advice, so frequently urged upon us, to adjust our cultural attitudes to the present status of scientific achievement, we would in all earnest adopt a way of life in which speech is no longer meaningful. For the sciences today have been forced to adopt a "language" of mathematical symbols which, though it was originally meant only as an abbreviation for spoken statements, now contains statements that in no way can be translated back into speech.

As she explains in the section on Action, speech is crucial for our ability to disclose ourselves to create the public sphere and its intersubjective bonds. When we turn speech into symbols, graphs, and equations we will bring the Archimedean Point into our relations and become depoliticized, and this is why Arendt doesn't want us to trust the scientists and their fabrication process, for *speech* is thinking, and thinking is to engage one's judgement:

The reason why it may be wise to distrust the political judgment of scientists qua scientists is not primarily their lack of "character"—that they did not refuse to develop atomic weapons—or their naivete—that they did not understand that once these weapons were developed they would be the last to be consulted about their use—but precisely the fact that they move in a world where speech has lost its power. And whatever men do or know or experience can make sense only to the extent that it can be spoken about. There may be truths beyond speech, and they may be of great relevance to man in the singular, that is, to man in so far as he is not a political being, whatever else he may be. Men in the plural, that is, men in so far as they live and move and act in this world, can experience meaningfulness only because they can talk with and make sense to each other and to themselves.

To me, this is a great summary of Arendt's claim in the section on Action, where our intersubjective engagement is what creates the world we share between us, and if we remove any of its aspects (the public sphere, thrownness, or language) then we're going to lose parts of our Human Condition and ability to be fully free. But it is not the only danger faced by our human condition, it may be the most dramatic and insidious one, but we should also concern ourselves with the activities we engage with. Arendt summarize her analysis of Labor Work and Action:

It is a society of laborers which is about to be liberated from the fetters of labor, and this society does no longer know of those other higher and more meaningful activities for the sake of which this freedom would deserve to be won. Within this society, which is egalitarian because this is labor's way of making men live together, there is no class left, no aristocracy of either a political or spiritual nature from which a restoration of the other capacities of man could start anew. Even presidents, kings, and prime ministers think of their offices in terms of a job necessary for the life of society, and among the intellectuals, only solitary individuals are left who consider what they are doing in terms of work and not in terms of making a living. What we are confronted with is the prospect of a society of laborers without labor, that is, without the only activity left to them. Surely, nothing could be worse.

As she claims late in the book, politics require something transcendental. The pursue of this transcendental has been the justification for all labor from ancient Greece to early modernity, but now we may be able to achieve the liberation from labor without any higher ideal to pursue.

We will be thrown back on the most basic of all human desires: life and pleasure. They can't serve as the basis for any political entity: we're at the risk of becoming Nietzsche's Last Men.

To these preoccupations and perplexities, this book does not offer an answer. Such answers are given every day, and they are matters of practical politics, subject to the agreement of many; they can never lie in theoretical considerations or the opinion of one person, as though we dealt here with problems for which only one solution is possible.

Arendt, practicing what she preaches, does not claim to give an answer to what we should do. She will show the way we can step away from this edge through political action, but if she would try to tell us what we ought to do with our politics then she will become that great fabricator she claims to be tyrannical in the section on Work. She wants to show the path back to subjectivity and politics, and not anything more.

We are free to find our own solution to the issue.

This, obviously, is a matter of thought, and thoughtlessness—the heedless recklessness or hopeless confusion or complacent repetition of "truths" which have become trivial and empty—seems to me among the outstanding characteristics of our time. What I propose, therefore, is very simple: it is nothing more than to think what we are doing.

In her great interview with Gunter Gaus, Arendt claimed that her only goal in her writings was to try and understand, and to share her understanding with her readers – and what she does in *The Human Condition* is to *think* our active life. This means that she will “blow away” the trivial and complacent truths of her age and *think* what we are *doing*, and by doing this create a new free approach to our life and time, and having done this, she will share this understanding with us, her readers, so that we too many free ourselves from the complacent “truths” of our age and begin something new. *The Human Condition* is almost like a theological text, it's an instruction on how to achieve a miracle in a new beginning: *natality*.

As Margaret Canovan begins her foreword to the second edition of *The Human Condition*: “Hannah Arendt is preeminently the theorist of beginnings”. Appropriately, in the beginning of her text on new beginnings she gives a tour de force of thick writing, summarizing extraordinarily complex thoughts in 6 pages.

Part 1: The Human Condition

Seminar 1: Chapter 1-3

Major themes

As it's the beginning of the book, Arendt wants to prepare the reader for what's to come.

- What the Human Condition is and what characterizes it
- What the Vita Activa and the Vita Contemplativa is, and what distinguishes them
- Why the Vita Activa disappeared from the western political tradition
- What the aim of the book is

Chapter 1 - The Vita Activa and The Human Condition

In this chapter Arendt presents the concept of the Vita Activa. What it consists of (labor, work, action) and how it relates to the human condition given to humanity on earth. This is the first sentence in book, and it's important to note how she phrases it in relation to "earth". The reason for this only becomes clear towards the end of the book.

She makes a clear distinction that she's interested in the Human Condition, and how her analysis is not a claim about human *nature* since (taking a phenomenological approach) everything that appears to us immediately becomes part of our human condition. Here she makes a pun, as the world simultaneously *conditions* (forms) *us* while also being the *human* (existence) *condition*: i.e., the book is about our surroundings as well as our contemporary condition. It's through this argument she claims that leaving earth would change our *conditions* and the *human condition*.

Having clarified this, she makes a brief summary of the three activities she famously investigates in the book, in order of appearance and argumentation sequence:

1. Labor are reoccurring activities necessary for life (gathering food, creating cloths, hygiene etc.). Barely results in anything lasting or tangible.
2. Work is 'worldliness' – the activity of creating a human artifice and environment through buildings, laws, art, infrastructure etc. These things last, and have "durability" as she will call it.
3. Action corresponds to unpredictability, *Plurality*, and our insertion into the world. This is quite vague at this point, but the relation and distinction of this activity to the previous two is one of Arendt's major insights in this book.

She claims she does not make a formal hierarchy between the activities, only seeking to understand them and their development in western political theory and history. Yet, towards the end of the book, she will argue that only Action can fully realize a person's unique existence, and a central claim in this book is that these activities were once clearly distinct between different social classes (genders, ages, professions, communities etcetera) but has now begun to become indistinguishable from one another, something she problematic.

This later critique is hinted at on page 10, where she claims that only a God could turn "who" into "what" – and it's just this transformation she claims that our reduction of *Action* into *Work* results in.

So, thus far in the very first chapter Arendt has teased many later arguments and claims. Another such teaser is her seemingly innocuous statement on Natality and new beginnings, which will become of paramount importance for her goal in the book. It's mentioned here, but later she will use these specific terms to suggest a revolutionary new foundation for political legitimacy and authority. It's often said that *The Human Condition* is a book that must be re-read to fully understand, and this very first chapter shows why.

Chapter 2 - The Term Vita Activa

In this chapter Arendt gives an overview of Vita Activa as a political tradition and its major changes – from the Greek discovery of it to its inversion at the end of western antiquity. The Greeks and Romans (to some degree) saw *politics as a way of life*, but with Christian theology and revelation, the status of this world became a form of anti-chamber to the afterworld, which turned *life into a form of politics* instead. A pious Christian life would give you meaning and reward in existence, instead of the Greeks who considered great deeds and politics as providing meaning in the individual becoming a person remembered through tales, stories, and myths.

However, Arendt doesn't accuse the Christian church and community for this inversion, but goes back to the Greeks themselves, for it was Plato and Aristotle (who argued for the Vita Contemplativa in quiet wonder of existence) who transformed reality from this world into the Platonic abstracted "forms." With this they made worldliness (political engagement) inferior to philosophical religious contemplation. "What had been demanded only by [philosophers] was now considered to be a right of all [souls]" (p.15).

This framework "has not been changed essentially by the modern break with the tradition and the eventual reversal of its hierarchical order in Marx and Nietzsche" (p.17). Modernity has however its own peculiarly dangerous framework that Arendt puts in sight with the following parts.

In summary, the previous chapter had Arendt teasing a lot of the later arguments and perspectives in the book, in this chapter she reveals her intent: to recover and rehabilitate a political tradition that was lost with the Greek city-states, and to adjust it to modern conditions.

Chapter 3 – Eternity Versus Immortality

So, what are the most important distinction between the Vita Activa and Vita Contemplativa then? Arendt makes a distinction by clarifying their different temporal alignments.

Vita Activa can be understood as the pursuit of *immortality*. In contrast to the "Asiatic" Gods who are timeless and eternal, men are *the mortals* who have a set time on earth. The nature is cyclical while human life is linear with a clear beginning (birth) and end (death) – this distinction between a cyclical nature/cosmos that's ever-repeating, and the linearity of human life, gives a contrast that situated men *against* nature, and that only the Greatest Men (heroes, craftsmen and legends) could become God-like and gain the same everlasting immortality as nature.

Humans can achieve this greatness through activities, and, if their deeds and words are great enough, they deserve to be part of the greatness of nature. Arendt even goes so far as to claim that Greeks saw hedonistic peoples, living for the simple and short pleasures, almost as animals while true humans are born by their great deeds that place them among the Pantheon of myths and gods.

In contrast to this striving for immortality and remembrance is the *Vita Contemplativa*, which can be understood as the philosophical or religious meditation on eternity in “*the standing now*”. What Arendt refers to with that term is the phenomenological experience of thought as a presence that never becomes the past. When in the active life you’re by necessity oriented towards some future, be it planning for dinner, predicting an argument, scheduling appointments or making plans, but when one is contemplative there is only a presence that is stretching out into the future and everchanging present – *eternity*. In other works, Arendt will use this as an argument for the experience of the divine, but in *The Human Condition* she investigates *the active life*, so this “standing now” is understood as apolitical in that you’re not among your peers but in contemplative solitude. This necessity for solitude to contemplate makes philosophy incompatible with politics as a phenomenon, as solitude is only possible in the private sphere, while politics *should* only be carried out in the public sphere. This distinction has been screwed up in modernity and will be explored in the next part of the book.

Before we move into it I want clarify Arendt’s thinking on the *Vita Contemplativa* – for in this chapter she seems to be quite negative towards it, which is regrettable as it becomes absolutely crucial in her discussions of Banal Evil. Not only is silent contemplation important for knowing what you’re doing, it’s also important to recognize where you’re going. It’s through contemplation and critical thinking that we can blow away all preconceptions and ideologies to gain a new and free approach towards life and our “insertion” into the public sphere – so we need both the active life *and* the contemplative life. We just need to have them distinct, and I can’t think of a better example of it than *the book we’re reading right now*, for in it Arendt spent time in contemplation and critical thinking to open up a new approach towards our active life.

So how did we begin to mix them up then? Arendt believes it happened through the fall of Rome, which proved that the great deeds and the immortality they’re supposed to achieve may not be everlasting as political communities and societies are as mortal as the men whose memory they’re supposed preserve. Instead, the citizens of post-empire Europe turned towards the church to preserve the immortal soul that could gain ‘greatness’ in an eternal heaven/hell. Here the contemplative life became more likely to provide meaning than the active life and is the reason the Christian church became the foundation of medieval politics.

Today, Arendt claims, we have become secular and no longer believe that the church (*vita contemplativa*) represents universal truths and meaning in life, but we’ve yet to rehabilitate the active life (*vita active*) as an alternative to it – this book wants to change all of that.

Discussion questions:

1. Is there other political traditions we can look at to find immortality over eternity other than ancient Greece? Does it have to be “western” politics?
2. Are the Greeks even a good example? Their slavery and misogyny should horrify us.
3. Why do we have to look backwards to find ‘good’ politics? Why not try to create something wholly new?
4. Has Arendt’s worst fears about the future of the human condition come true with the Anthropocene and global surveillance? She writes on page 10: “such an event, no longer totally impossible, would imply that man would have to live under man-made conditions, radically different from those the earth offers him”.
5. Wasn’t her fear of humanity’s ability change and form the natural world already achieved in the nuclear bomb? Today we’ve gone much further than that.

Part 2: The Public and The Private Realm

Seminar 2 – Chapter 4–5

Major themes

- What the private and the public spheres are, and how they relate to one another and the three central activities of the active life
- How these two spheres became confused and merged together into “the social”
- The difference between a Political community and a Social community

Chapter 4 – Man: A Social or Political Animal?

With Arendt having made a brief introduction of the Vita Activa and the Vita Contemplativa, she now makes another distinction: that between the public and private realms, and how the three activities analyzed in this book (*Labor, Work, Action*) interact with these two spheres in society.

The most important aspect is that the terminology she uses in the book is bound to the public sphere, and that we have different terms for these activities when they are carried out in the private realm. In that realm they become the activities of animals instead of men. See the following schema where I summarize her analysis and distinction.

	Private / Household	Public / Polis
Role in politics:	Pre-political	Political Sphere
Means & Ends:	Realm of Necessity (means)	Realm of Freedom (end)
Relationships defined by:	Inequality & Rule “Pater familias”	Equality & Freedom “Homini inter homini”
Primary virtue	--- No virtues outside the Polis	Courage Politics is always risky
Activity <i>for</i> life:	Animal labourans	Labour
Activity of Worldliness:	Demiurge	Homo Faber
Activity of plurality	--- Contradiction in terms	Action
Determined by:	Violence & Incomprehensible “Bar-bar-bar”	Action & Speech

Note, for example, that a person engaging in the activities necessary for biological existence in the private realm (*Household*) becomes a form of subhuman animal. These are the slaves kept away from being political and discussed, seen as mere tools or labor power. When they enter the political sphere (*Polis*), and become seen as human beings, they are called laborers working in factories or in the farmland. She’s not very subtle here.

She makes this man/animal distinction by referencing the Greeks. For them human co-existence could not be based on the very fact that we live together, for animals do the same, instead they argued that it's the political community (of speech and action) that makes us unique and distinct from animals. The Romans didn't preserve this distinction, and made their community defined by the very fact that people were living together – this is the distinction between man as Social (Rome/Animals) or Political (Greek).

The tragic consequences of this Roman conception is that it invited violence and domination into the community, which the Greeks had kept outside among the barbarians. Arendt's argument is deceptively difficult and hard to understand at this point, but in her section on *Action* she will show how violence (as pain) can never be political and the central importance of speech and rhetoric is in creating a shared political community.

It's also very worthwhile to note the last paragraph of the chapter. Arendt notices how the Roman *Social* conception of community makes the King/Emperor/General Secretary a head of the household (*Pater*) and thereby turns the entire Public into *his own* very Private realm. Just like the head of the household has absolute dominion over his private realm, so do the tyrant over the public (social) realm. What makes this particular paragraph so noteworthy however is that Arendt rejects this reading because a Political community (in contrast to a social community) have such distributed power (which Arendt will discuss at a later point in the book) that it can never be ruled from one central point.

So, in this small paragraph Arendt reveals many later arguments and even makes objections against arguments she will soon present herself!

Chapter 5 – The Polis and the Household

Having made these fundamental distinctions in western politics, Arendt now returns into her contemporary age, in which the distinction between a social and a political community has completely disappeared. The appearance of the nation-state, and the socioeconomic political administration that has been created alongside it, has made the private realm a big concern for the political machinery. Arendt is sometimes understood as reactionary and against progressive policies, and this and following arguments is usually cited as justification for that reading, for Arendt is *opposed to social politics*. Much of her political thinking is based on this very distinction, that politics and social issues are two fundamentally distinct entities that must be kept far apart from one another, so when we have social democracy Arendt believes that we are reducing the existentially important role of politics by turning it into social administration.

As she writes, “political economy” is an etymological contradiction since you can't have a public (“political”) economy (“household”). Yet, this is what we've created and obsess over in modernity.

Here I want to refer to the schema above. When we begin to mix the private and the public we're either going to transform pointless activities (“*means*”) into ends, or reduce our ends into means. Either way, Arendt believes, we're going to reduce our freedoms in exchange for social goals – a bad tradeoff for her, for the most important goal of any community is the freedom of its members. She recognizes of course that we need to first satisfy our biological necessities before we can engage in politics, but we must never lose track of the end goal of any community, which is not the biological necessities (a means) but politics.

Note also how she gives emphasis that *Glory* was only possible in the public realm, this will become an important part later in this book, both in her political analysis but also claims on the meaning of life. She believes that we can re-discovery meaning in life by looking back to the Greeks understanding of it – namely distinction in the public realm instead of a life in the private realm that's taken over all aspects of society in modernity. Before we achieve that we must first find a way to split the private from the public again, and as we will discuss in the next seminar, it is *urgent that we do this as soon as possible*.

Discussion questions:

1. The Little Rock 9 issue: should personal and private preferences and bigoted opinions (discrimination; misogyny) be kept outside the realm of public opinion?
2. Is Arendt's politics even attractive? Isn't Arendt supporting a form of labor-slavery to achieve the necessities for politics? Can we overcome it with Universal Basic Income? Should we?
3. If the public is what's known and recognized, then could the private be pure potential as the household is undetermined and undefined? Is that the case with the mass surveillance of our time?
4. Arendt understands freedom as being a form of equality that you then rise above (Great Deeds). Is it any good in contrast to other definitions such as freedom as private property, as choice, as non-interference and rights?
5. Is the welfare state undesirable? The Social Democracy seems to be just the sort of mix-up Arendt is concerned about with governmental agencies explicitly concerned about the status and character of families, and the opportunities given to each person in education, health, self-realization etcetera. Is the welfare state a focus on social outcomes over a focus on healthy political structures?
6. As Giorgio Agamben recognized, isn't the danger of *The Social* that anyone can be reduced into the pre-political stage and placed outside of the community as rightless? As we don't make distinctions, what sort of entity is a pre-political person? Stateless? Rightless?
7. Is this a critique of American or European politics?

Seminar 3: Chapters 6-7

Major themes

- 'The social' as a dynamic of modernity's destruction of the private/public distinction
- Action's reduction into Behavior
- The importance of a shared world and its durability
- The tendency of 'the social' to grow and prolongate itself

Chapter 6 – The Rise of The Social

In the previous chapters Arendt distinguished the private from the public and introduced the concept of 'the social' as a confused mix of the household and the Polis. She argued that the household, in its biological imperative (labor), had overtaken politics' highest aspirations in personal distinction (action). In these chapters Arendt goes into a critique of the phenomenon, why 'the social' is a such a menace to politics, humanity, and our future.

Her concept of 'the social' is one of the most debated aspects of this book, and there are many good reasons to argue that this is **the** central chapter for Arendt's dystopian analysis of modernity. There's been many interpretations of how one should understand the concept, some think it's a critique of social politics and the welfare states, some that it's an ontological critique, and some believe that it can't be studied in itself without reference to her previous work *Origins of Totalitarianism*. I'm in this latter camp, and I will present the argument in the next chapter. Regardless to say, the importance of this chapter is hard to understate, and I recommend you to reread it at least twice – and possibly a third time after you've finished reading the sections on labor and action.

She begins chapter 6 by noting how the existence of 'the social' began with the society-critique of Rousseau, who believed that civilization corrupted the human heart. Man had to discover himself and his heart, and bring it forth into the world to make the intimate a political entity. This intimacy was previously held inside the family and closest social bonds (Household), but with the rise of the modern nation-state the individual now had to act as if the entire political community (The Polis) was one large 'social family' (The Social) to which one had as many obligations to as one's does to one's own family.

Just like the private family was supposed to be ruled by one household head, so too was the social family organized:

The equality of the members of these groups, far from being an equality among peers, resembles nothing so much as the equality of household members before the despotic power of the household head, except that in society, where the natural strength of one common interest and one unanimous opinion is tremendously enforced by sheer number, actual rule exerted by one man, representing the common interest and the right opinion, could eventually be dispensed with. The phenomenon of conformism is characteristic of the last stage of this modern development.

This political household head doesn't need to be a monarch or tyrant, it doesn't have to be a singular person, but it must be the central source of power from which the rest of society has obedience towards. This 'nobody' Arendt states:

As we know from the most social form of government, that is, from bureaucracy (the last stage of government in the nation-state just as one-man rule in benevolent despotism and absolutism was its first), the rule by nobody is not necessarily no-rule; it may indeed, under certain circumstances, even turn out to be one of its cruelest and most tyrannical versions.

Arendt then connects this to the site for political action and engagement. For, as we will read later in the book, politics and action is only possible in the public sphere among equals, and when we have reduced this site by turning it into a version of a "family" we have denigrated shared action into personal responsibility to act according to social norms and expectations – to be good family members.

In turn this has made us become copies of one another in the sense that we all follow the same sets of norms and expectations, and have become a form of massified copies of the specific social roles we're given – which is an absolutely central aspect of Arendt's analysis of totalitarianism.

With this structuring of society as a family, action has become personal behavior according to the norms and expectations that's established themselves throughout society. This was radically different from how the Greeks imagined the politics and society:

This modern equality, based on the conformism inherent in society and possible only because behavior has replaced action as the foremost mode of human relationship, is in every respect different from equality in antiquity, and notably in the Greek city-states. To belong to the few "equals" (*homoioi*) meant to be permitted to live among one's peers; but the public realm itself, the *polis*, was permeated by a fiercely agonal spirit, where everybody had constantly to distinguish himself from all others, to show through unique deeds or achievements that he was the best of all (*aien aristuein*). The public realm, in other words, was reserved for individuality; it was the only place where men could show who they really and inexchangeably were. It was for the sake of this chance, and out of love for a body politic that made it possible to them all, that each was more or less willing to share in the burden of jurisdiction, defense, and administration of public affairs.

This conformism, the massification of humanity and individuals, created and is reinforced by contemporary science. Arendt specifically refers to economics and statistics, but later she will argue that all natural sciences use an implicit perspective that denies individuality, but that's for the very end of the book. Arendt brings it up at this point to highlight the consequences of 'the social's' reduction of the individual into a family member and action into behavior:

The laws of statistics are valid only where large numbers or long periods are involved, and acts or events can statistically appear only as deviations or fluctuations. [...] The application of the law of large numbers and long periods to politics or history signifies nothing less than the wilful obliteration of their very subject matter, and it is a hopeless enterprise to search for meaning in politics or significance in history when everything that is not everyday behavior or automatic trends has been ruled out as immaterial. However, since the laws of statistics are perfectly valid where we deal with large numbers, it is obvious that every increase in population means an increased validity and a marked decrease of "deviation." Politically, this means that the larger the population in any given body politic, the more likely it will be the social rather than the political that constitutes the public realm. [...] Large numbers of people, crowded together, develop an almost

irresistible inclination toward despotism, be this the despotism of a person or of majority rule; and although statistics, that is, the mathematical treatment of reality, was unknown prior to the modern age, the social phenomena which make such treatment possible—great numbers, accounting for conformism, behaviorism, and automatism in human affairs—were precisely those traits which, in Greek self-understanding, distinguished the Persian civilization from their own. The unfortunate truth about behaviorism and the validity of its “laws” is that the more people there are, the more likely they are to behave and the less likely to tolerate non-behavior. [...] In reality, deeds will have less and less chance to stem the tide of behavior, and events will more and more lose their significance, that is, their capacity to illuminate historical time. Statistical uniformity is by no means a harmless scientific ideal; it is the no longer secret political ideal of a society which, entirely submerged in the routine of everyday living, is at peace with the scientific outlook inherent in its very existence.

It's a long quote but certainly worthwhile to read carefully. What Arendt believes happens when the private and public realm meet is that a new form of knowledge ways of understanding community is created, one where each individual loses his individuality and becomes a statistical entity that can be predicted – and this prediction becomes a self-reinforcing norm through which people are being analysed. In this way the massification of society becomes self-reinforcing – as massification turns into abstracted economic and psychological concepts, framing the human person and turn our individual freedom into predictable pre-determined molds of behaviour – which Arendt refers to as the “communistic fiction” where all social and economic interests are harmonized and depolitized, which she claims, with gleeful sarcasm towards the neoclassical thinkers of the Austrian School, the classical economists to have invented.

Having said that, she turns to Marx, whose material dialectic follow a similar premise of predetermined human behaviours and fate. Arendt claims that his denial of human unpredictability was not due to his philosophy but rather the socialized nature of the society he reacted against. While not discussed in this chapter, Arendt argues that the only site where we can overcome the norms of the public sphere is by retreating into the private realm of personal contemplation and critical thinking, which disappeared with ‘the social’.

This is the first time Arendt engages with Marx’s thinking in the book, something she will do for much of the remaining parts of it, and while The Human Condition have often been read as critique of Marx I believe that Arendt had huge respect for him and wanted to engage his thinking in an age (red scare 50’s USA) where doing so explicitly (especially as a German stateless jew with a ex-Spartacist) would invite all sorts of trouble.

Another interesting aspect of the chapter is how she repeatedly returns to the argument that in modern society nobody rules except the self-reinforcing process of a “communistic fiction”:

whose outstanding political characteristic is that it is indeed ruled by an “invisible hand,” namely, by nobody. What we traditionally call state and government gives place here to pure administration—a state of affairs which Marx rightly predicted as the “withering away of the state,” though he was wrong in assuming that only a revolution could bring it about, and even more wrong when he believed that this complete victory of society would mean the eventual emergence of the “realm of freedom.”

This is important to point out, for a central aspect of the totalitarian phenomenon is just this self-sustaining process where humanity is supposed to follow some ideological force towards a self-emerging utopia of harmonized interests. While the totalitarian societies did this by an explicit intervention in society through ideological thinking, in *The Human Condition* Arendt seems to argue that the same dynamic can be created through the hands-off approach of an economical “communistic fiction”.

For just like the totalitarian societies and movements had to keep on moving and would fall apart the moment they stagnated, so too does ‘the social’ continue to consume and conquer all aspects of the political community to align it with “behavior”:

Since the rise of society, since the admission of household and housekeeping activities to the public realm, an irresistible tendency to grow, to devour the older realms of the political and private as well as the more recently established sphere of intimacy, has been one of the outstanding characteristics of the new realm. This constant growth, whose no less constant acceleration we can observe over at least three centuries, derives its strength from the fact that through society it is the life process itself which in one form or another has been channeled into the public realm

I like to think of *The Human Condition* as Arendt’s Huxleyan book in contrast to the ‘Orwellianism’ of *Origins of Totalitarianism*, and I think this chapter (when read in the light of her discussion on labour) proves why. Take this quote as an example:

It is because this one-ness of man-kind is not fantasy and not even merely a scientific hypothesis, as in the “communistic fiction” of classical economics, that mass society, where man as a social animal rules supreme and where apparently the survival of the species could be guaranteed on a world-wide scale, can at the same time threaten humanity with extinction.

So just like the citizens of Huxley’s *Brave New World* are mere beast obsessed with pleasure with no regards for freedom or higher ambitions or ideals, so too has the modern society’s mix of the private and public realm reduced humanity into “laborers and jobholders [...] centered around the one activity necessary to sustain life”.

The dystopian nature of this argument may be hard to understand at this point, but as Arendt points out in the remaining chapters, she believes that labour can’t provide any meaning and is inherently pointless, and must never be turned into a political *end* but must be strictly kept as a means to politics.

I hope that the central importance of this chapter has become clear. It’s where Arendt frames labour’s conquest of society, and what detrimental effects this has on all aspects of human existence. In summary:

Not even the social realm—though it made excellence anonymous, emphasized the progress of mankind rather than the achievements of men, and changed the content of the public realm beyond recognition—has been able altogether to annihilate the connection between public performance and excellence. While we have become excellent in the laboring we perform in public, our capacity for action and speech has lost much of its former quality since the rise of the social realm banished these into the sphere of the intimate and the private.

Chapter 7 – The Public Realm: The Common

So why is the public realm so important then? In this chapter Arendt will discuss the different ways that a shared sphere affects our lives and reality. She begins with the most important function of the public realm: the creation of a shared reality:

The presence of others who see what we see and hear what we hear assures us of the reality of the world and ourselves, and while the intimacy of a fully developed private life, such as had never been known before the rise of the modern age and the concomitant decline of the public realm, will always greatly intensify and enrich the whole scale of subjective emotions and private feelings, this intensification will always come to pass at the expense of the assurance of the reality of the world and men.

It is this “sameness in utter diversity” that makes the public realm so important, for it is in it that we can have intersubjective engagements and validate our realities to ensure that we have the same conception of society and political issues (p.57).

The second importance of the public realm is that it is the force that unites us without having us “falling over each other”. Arendt uses the metaphor of the table, in the sense that we all sit on individual chairs and it’s only the table that makes us all into a united entity that can engage one another. But, and this is very important for Arendt, this ‘uniting’ is also *separating* in the sense that each participant has their own chair and place at the table, and isn’t a disorganized clump of bodies tied together through some game of Twister. It’s of crucial importance:

This can happen under conditions of radical isolation, where nobody can any longer agree with anybody else, as is usually the case in tyrannies. But it may also happen under conditions of mass society or mass hysteria, where we see all people suddenly behave as though they were members of one family, each multiplying and prolonging the perspective of his neighbor. In both instances, men have become entirely private, that is, they have been deprived of seeing and hearing others, of being seen and being heard by them. They are all imprisoned in the subjectivity of their own singular experience, which does not cease to be singular if the same experience is multiplied innumerable times. The end of the common world has come when it is seen only under one aspect and is permitted to present itself in only one perspective.

Having argued that the “table” disappeared with the fall of the Greek city states and the Roman empire, Arendt makes a segment into an historical analysis of different attempts to replace the “table”. The first method of replacement was to create a shared religious world in Augustine’s Christian conception of politics:

This surprising illustration of the Christian political principle is in fact very well chosen, because the bond of charity between people, while it is incapable of founding a public realm of its own, is quite adequate to the main Christian principle of worldlessness and is admirably fit to carry a group of essentially worldless people through the world, a group of saints or a group of criminals, provided only it is understood that the world itself is doomed and that every activity in it is undertaken with the proviso *quamdiu mundus durat* (“as long as the world lasts”). The unpolitical, non-public character of the Christian community was early defined in the demand that it should form a *corpus*, a “body,” whose members were to be related to each other like brothers of the same family. The structure of communal life was modeled on the relationships between the members of a family because these were known to be non-political and even antipolitical.

This worldlessness led however to the rejection of the human artifice that's of crucial importance to the shared public realm, so objects such as a table lose their importance as entities with 'durability' that lasts throughout history and binds us and the coming generations together, creating the possibility of the earthly immortality that Arendt sees as the goal and meaning of political engagement.

Without this transcendence into a potential earthly immortality, no politics, strictly speaking, no common world and no public realm, is possible. For unlike the common good as Christianity understood it—the salvation of one's soul as a concern common to all—the common world is what we enter when we are born and what we leave behind when we die. It transcends our lifespan into past and future alike; it was there before we came and will outlast our brief sojourn in it. It is what we have in common not only with those who live with us, but also with those who were here before and with those who will come after us. But such a common world can survive the coming and going of the generations only to the extent that it appears in public. It is the publicity of the public realm which can absorb and make shine through the centuries whatever men may want to save from the natural ruin of time. Through many ages before us—but now not any more—men entered the public realm because they wanted something of their own or something they had in common with others to be more permanent than their earthly lives.

We, as humans, are bound and limited by our inevitable death. And the Greeks triumph against it was the possibility that we would leave something behind that would keep our name and existence alive throughout stories and memories. But as we've turned away from politics and action, and denigrated the importance of the durability of the physical world around us (what Arendt will call *work* in this book) we have also reduced the possibility of being remembered and achieving the excellence that Arendt sees as the highest goal of human life.

These achievements are for Arendt not just bounded to the specific time and age in which it is consumed by has a timeless quality as a meditation on the human existential precarity that we've all existed in, from hunter-gatherers, to the Sumerians, to Renaissance Florence to today. The importance of having a "table" that last throughout the ages is that the "sameness in utter diversity" will also connect us to the ones before us and the ones that will follow us:

Being seen and being heard by others derive their significance from the fact that everybody sees and hears from a different position. This is the meaning of public life, compared to which even the richest and most satisfying family life can offer only the prolongation or multiplication of one's own position with its attending aspects and perspectives. The subjectivity of privacy can be prolonged and multiplied in a family, it can even become so strong that its weight is felt in the public realm; but this family "world" can never replace the reality rising out of the sum total of aspects presented by one object to a multitude of spectators. Only where things can be seen by many in a variety of aspects without changing their identity, so that those who are gathered around them know they see sameness in utter diversity, can worldly reality truly and reliably appear.

The stakes here is not just about us connecting to one another in society but also that we create a shared understanding of the human condition that unites us all, not just in time but also in geographical width.

It's by understanding that we all share the same condition that we can understand that people who are strangers to us are actually the same even in their own diversity, and through this we can create the empathy and cosmopolitanism that can counter the racism that Arendt believes is the "end of humanity" as she claims in *Origins of Totalitarianism*.

This argument is much more complicated than what can be summarized here, but the importance of preserving historical objects and entities is what give a social group their "depth" and standing that gives them a form of weight and importance, and thereby also a form of relevance in politics. One aspect of her critique of statelessness in the 1930's was that it was a wholly new social group that had never existed before, and therefore didn't have the same historical works of art that can create a public realm and common understanding with the rest of society – the unique, problematic, and novel singularity of them probably contributed to them being put in camps with no clue on how to integrate or assimilate them.

Discussion questions:

1. Is it true that we're understanding others by their "behavior" rather than their actions?
2. Is it necessarily bad that we're becoming grey but pleasant consumers in the modern 'social'? Why do we have to distinguish ourselves?
3. Is it really the case that the public has entered into our private homes? Are we still expecting to 'behave' there? How is this influenced by mass surveillance?
4. Do we have a 'common world' with strangers in today's hyperconnected world? Or have we grown more distinct from each other and become more strangers to one another than we were before?
5. Is the connection between statistics, economics, behaviorism, and a massified society true?

Seminar 4: chapters 8-10

Having introduced her major concept in 'The Social,' Arendt spends these chapters laying the groundwork for much of the arguments in the coming sections on labor, work, and action.

Further, I think these chapters are quite complicated as Arendt deals with a very delicate topic at the time of writing. Having ensured her McCarthyistic "patriotism" by giving a clear critique of left-wing politics, with this possibly being the reason she used the term 'the social' instead of something like mass society, she now turns towards capitalism to give it the same critical treatment – which could promptly put her under suspicion. In fact, one of her students were inspired by her lectures and told her parents about Arendt, who then informed FBI, who opened a file on her. In said file the FBI quickly concluded that she was no threat to anyone but was a simple but particularly bright, domineering, and eloquent professor of politics.

Nevertheless, Arendt took deep inspiration from Marx, and I think much of these sub-chapters can be read as having Marxist inspiration, just disguised and carefully circumscribed.

Major themes

- The many shifts and changes in the relationship between the public and private spheres
- Arendt's critique of wealth, capital, and capitalism
- The importance of both the private and the public realm, both in distinction and in interaction with the other
- Arendt's predictions on the future of the Private/Public distinction
- The location of activities, with largest emphasis on goodness and philosophy

Chapter 8 – The Private Realm – Property

Having discussed the importance of the public realm she begins this chapter by focusing why the private realm can't suffice on its own:

To live an entirely private life means above all to be deprived of things essential to a truly human life: to be deprived of the reality that comes from being seen and heard by others, to be deprived of an "objective" relationship with them that comes from being related to and separated from them through the intermediary of a common world of things, to be deprived of the possibility of achieving something more permanent than life itself. The privation of privacy lies in the absence of others; as far as they are concerned, private man does not appear, and therefore it is as though he did not exist. Whatever he does remains without significance and consequence to others, and what matters to him is without interest to other people.

Under modern circumstances, this deprivation of "objective" relationships to others and of a reality guaranteed through them has become the mass phenomenon of loneliness, where it has assumed its most extreme and most antihuman form. The reason for this extremity is that mass society not only destroys the public realm but the private as well, deprives men not only of their place in the world but of their private home, where they once felt sheltered against the world and where, at any rate, even those excluded from the world could find a substitute in the warmth of the hearth and the limited reality of family life.

The insufficiency of the private realm is then problematized by Arendt who notes how the Christian command to render unto Caesar made the public subsumed to the private, while also transforming the private realm into a means for salvation. This movement from public/private coexistence into public subordination to the private, and the reduction of the private realm into a means for salvation, survives today and can be seen in the Marxist prediction of the withering away of the state and the public realm.

Arendt then claims that this final stage, the reduction of the private sphere into a means, can (in 1958) be seen as the discussion on the political expedience of private property or not.

Nor is it an accident that the whole discussion has eventually turned into an argument about the desirability or undesirability of privately owned property. For the word "private" in connection with property, even in terms of ancient political thought, immediately loses its privative character and much of its opposition to the public realm in general; property apparently possesses certain qualifications which, though lying in the private realm, were always thought to be of utmost importance to the political body.

She is however too sophisticated to engage in specific polemics but rephrases the question into the frame of the private/public distinction:

The profound connection between private and public, manifest on its most elementary level in the question of private property, is likely to be misunderstood today because of the modern equation of property and wealth on one side and propertylessness and poverty on the other. This misunderstanding is all the more annoying as both, property as well as wealth, are historically of greater relevance to the public realm than any other private matter or concern and have played, at least formally, more or less the same role as the chief condition for admission to the public realm and full-fledged citizenship

Here she makes a remarkable vault and brings in an *almost* Marxian analysis of private ownership. She claims that the modern age began with the creation of a propertyless strata of society (*proletariat?*). As property (as a private realm) was a requirement for being considered a full member of a political community this propertyless strata of society became the intermediary classes that were necessarily public (having no other place to be) and thereby always present in politics, while not possessing any private realm (property) for themselves and therefore none of the "chairs" at the table that united everyone – this strata became the precarious and dehumanized class possessing none of the same rights as propertied citizens did:

It is therefore not really accurate to say that private property, prior to the modern age, was thought to be a self-evident condition for admission to the public realm; it is much more than that. Privacy was like the other, the dark and hidden side of the public realm, and while to be political meant to attain the highest possibility of human existence, to have no private place of one's own (like a slave) meant to be no longer human.

So just like the lack of a durable common world made a social group history-less, and therefore outside intersubjective sympathies, this propertyless and privacy-less social group suffered the same dehumanization. As she argued previously, our biological needs must be satisfied before we can enter the public realm and be political, so humans without the ability to satisfy said primary needs can't be expected to enter politics and be recognized in the public sphere:

To own property meant here to be master over one's own necessities of life and therefore potentially to be a free person, free to transcend his own life and enter the world all have in common.

This entire equation (property -> citizenship -> human dignity) is ignored by her contemporary market liberals, who argued that private property should be beyond political relevance and the only means to prevent tyranny. Arendt rejects this as foolish, for their political analysis is to position the private realm (property) as being distinct from the public realm, while Arendt argues that they must be seen in coexistence and exchange with one another, as she writes in a footnote:

I must confess that I fail to see on what grounds in present-day society liberal economists (who today call themselves conservatives) can justify their optimism that the private appropriation of wealth will suffice to guard individual liberties [...] these liberties are safe only as long as they are guaranteed by the state, and even now they are constantly threatened [...] by [the social].

Private property may be seen as some human right, but the reality is that it is a right only for as long as the owners are considered to be politically relevant and important. Should the state transform from its liberal version, private property, made distinct from political exchange and dynamics, will quickly be appropriated for the public: *property is political*.

Chapter 9 – The Social and The Private

She continues this argument and claims that a very important shift happened when *wealth* became *capital*. Wealth can be saved, used up, or consumed, while capital must always generate more capital. In other terms: capital doesn't have durability in that it can preserve through itself, but can only be preserved through the process of capital accumulation.

So, as we live in a capital-based society, by which she not-so-subtly means Capitalism, our durability is not inherent in the goods we produce but only in the character of a self-sustaining process of continual capital accumulation.

This capital-wealth distinction is a very important for Arendt, for wealth is *common* while capital is *private*. As we've denigrated the public for the private, and made the private into a means, we've made modern politics and governance into a royal mess:

The obvious contradiction in this modern concept of government, where the only thing people have in common is their private interests, need no longer bother us as it still bothered Marx, since we know that the contradiction between private and public, typical of the initial stages of the modern age, has been a temporary phenomenon which introduced the utter extinction of the very difference between the private and public realms, the submersion of both in the sphere of the social. By the same token, we are in a far better position to realize the consequences for human existence when both the public and private spheres of life are gone, the public because it has become a function of the private and the private because it has become the only common concern left.

The only thing we have in common today is the shared pursuit of individual goals rather than any shared conception of the good. And this shared pursuit of individual goals is for Arendt nothing else than the market. It's here that Arendt carefully embedded a radical critique of capitalism in her discussion of the private/public distinction.

Arendt, believing that the sheer abundance of capital available for private people will result in political instability, saw the public as taking revenge against the private by turning the private/public relationship around so that the public would dominate the private:

For wealth, after it became a public concern, has grown to such proportions that it is almost unmanageable by private ownership. It is as though the public realm had taken its revenge against those who tried to use it for their private interests. The greatest threat here, however, is not the abolition of private ownership of wealth but the abolition of private property in the sense of a tangible, worldly place of one's own.

What seems to have happened instead was that the private came to dominate the public even more intensely as seen with the case of Citizens United in the USA, where private entities are now considered to be political entities in themselves and able to use their private capital influence the distribution of public wealth – the opposite of Arendt's prediction. The same ironic inversion of her prediction is also visible in the following paragraph:

The second outstanding non-privative characteristic of privacy is that the four walls of one's private property offer the only reliable hiding place from the common public world, not only from everything that goes on in it but also from its very publicity, from being seen and being heard. A life spent entirely in public, in the presence of others, becomes, as we would say, shallow. While it retains its visibility, it loses the quality of rising into sight from some darker ground which must remain hidden if it is not to lose its depth in a very real, non-subjective sense. The only efficient way to guarantee the darkness of what needs to be hidden against the light of publicity is private property, a privately owned place to hide in.

What seems to have happened in our world today is that our governments have become privatized so that they have not become more shallow and visible, but rather more mysterious and seemingly corrupt with less transparency and insight. As we all probably experience today, this is not a very desirable situation, but is it better than Arendt's fear that we would destroy the private sphere in politics? Or is it that we've somehow managed to get the worst of both worlds with a privatized governance and a politized private through mass surveillance? Isn't this the thesis of "Surveillance capitalism"?

Her one prediction that seems to have come true is the politization of the body and biological necessities:

The fact that the modern age emancipated the working classes and the women at nearly the same historical moment must certainly be counted among the characteristics of an age which no longer believes that bodily functions and material concern should be hidden. It is all the more symptomatic of the nature of these phenomena that the few remnants of strict privacy even in our own civilization relate to 'necessities' in the original sense of being necessitated by having a body (p.73)

As we know today, the "bedchamber matters" have become quite political and a subject of intensive capital accumulation through products and media – the private realm has been abolished under capital, as the defining character of modernity's public realm. Capitalism doesn't stop at any private/public boundaries but commercializes more and more: no private realm, no limit for the politics inherent in capitalism to commercialize and publicize.

Chapter 10 – The location of Human Activities

Having spent most of the section on clarifying the *political* superiority of the public realm vis-a-vis the private realm, Arendt finishes the section by taking a look at the positive traits of the private realm. There are good reasons to preserve it from the public, reasons other than preventing the social from consuming all of society. Arendt argues that all activities have their appropriate location, and in this final chapter of the section she focuses on *goodness*.

Her argument is quite simple: if a good act is done in the public sphere it automatically becomes a political action, and an attempt to appear as a person with specific charitable traits:

For it is manifest that the moment a good work becomes known and public, it loses its specific character of goodness, of being done for nothing but goodness' sake. When goodness appears openly, it is no longer goodness, though it may still be useful as organized charity or an act of solidarity. Therefore: "Take heed that ye do not your alms before men, to be seen of them." Goodness can exist only when it is not perceived, not even by its author; whoever sees himself performing a good work is no longer good, but at best a useful member of society or a dutiful member of a church. Therefore: "Let not thy left hand know what thy right hand doeth." (p.74)

For Arendt this results in one of the most paradoxical events in history, for how could Jesus both be a practitioner of the private and true good while also being a wholly public figure? In the same vein, how come philosophers, who are the private people par excellence in their thinking solitude, be political like Plato? For Arendt, the distinction between goodness and politics can be identified in the activity of thinking, as a "dialogue between 'me and myself'". In a later work (*Life of the Mind*) she calls it the "two-in-one":

But the similarity between the activities springing from love of goodness and love of wisdom ends here. Both, it is true, stand in a certain opposition to the public realm, but the case of goodness is much more extreme in this respect and therefore of greater relevance in our context. Only goodness must go into absolute hiding and flee all appearance if it is not to be destroyed. The philosopher, even if he decides with Plato to leave the "cave" of human affairs, does not have to hide from himself; on the contrary, under the sky of ideas he not only finds the true essences of everything that is, but also himself, in the dialogue between "me and myself" (*eme emantō*) in which Plato apparently saw the essence of thought.

A secondary distinction between thinking and goodness is the results they achieve. As Socrates and Plato both knew, writing down a philosophical conversation is a radical act that changes its nature from perplexity and reflection into a part of the human artifice, the "table" we all share. And, while she doesn't go into it in this chapter, Arendt is *highly* skeptical about the role of philosophy in politics, for as philosophy is an activity defined by lone thinking, how can it possibly become political without becoming normative and either (1) forcing itself on one's political interlocutors to adopt one's own philosophical perspectives on truth and reality or (2) create conceptions on what the ideal society should be, and thereby becoming politically normative (ideological) and coercive? And, much like the issues of political philosophy, acts of goodness and love can never be made into the public human artifice without becoming corrupted by politics and turn into a means to gain reputation, clients, change opinion (etcetera) instead of a private end of goodness for goodness sake. This is why she cites Machiavelli to argue that goodness doesn't belong in politics for the reason that it will either be corrupted by politics or corrupt politics:

Goodness, therefore, as a consistent way of life, is not only impossible within the confines of the public realm, it is even destructive of it. Nobody perhaps has been more sharply aware of this ruinous quality of doing good than Machiavelli, who, in a famous passage, dared to teach men “how not to be good.” Needless to add, he did not say and did not mean that men must be taught how to be bad; the criminal act, though for other reasons, must also flee being seen and heard by others. Machiavelli’s criterion for political action was glory, the same as in classical antiquity, and badness can no more shine in glory than goodness. Therefore all methods by which “one may indeed gain power, but not glory” are bad. Badness that comes out of hiding is impudent and directly destroys the common world; goodness that comes out of hiding and assumes a public role is no longer good, but corrupt in its own terms and will carry its own corruption wherever it goes. Thus, for Machiavelli, the reason for the Church’s becoming a corrupting influence in Italian politics was her participation in secular affairs as such and not the individual corruptness of bishops and prelates. To him, the alternative posed by the problem of religious rule over the secular realm was inescapably this: either the public realm corrupted the religious body and thereby became itself corrupt, or the religious body remained uncorrupt and destroyed the public realm altogether.

Discussion questions:

1. How Marxist is her critique that private property’s commodification of the public sphere leaves us with no private sphere?
2. How credible is her attempt to go beyond ideologies and critique our political structures? Is it just her being an obnoxious continental philosopher creating her own ideology, or is she trying to abolish ideological thinking wholesale?
3. Is it true that our main pursuit in life is the accumulation of property in a commodified private realm?
4. Is it true that if everything is property that everything simultaneously is public? Are all marketplaces public realms?
5. Can’t goodness be public? Or does that assume a politically dangerous naivety? Is it a dynamic similar to the prisoners dilemma?

Part 3: Labor

Seminar 5: chapters 11-14

The chapters we've read so far are only the introduction into Arendt's discussion of Labor, Work and Action. Having distinguished the Private from the Public sphere, and introduced her concept of 'The Social,' she now begins to analyze how we've confused our activities, and why it's detrimental humanity.

Major themes

- What Labor is
- What distinguishes Labor from Work and Action
- Why our contemporary mixing of them is so detrimental.
- The distinction between consumption goods (labor) and use goods (work)
- What labor can't do in politics.

Chapter 11 – “The labor of our body, and the work of our hands”

Before beginning her discussion of labor Arendt gives an ironic and really quite funny comment on Marx, and how literature on Marx is a form of common *labor* for intellectuals.

The true humor of this statement becomes visible on a second read-through, for as she argues in this chapter, intellectuals who have no tangible production have lost their economic value and must reify their thinking into tangible objects to have a place in society. They've become intellectual laborers, and she will argue in this section that such labor is quite pointless. Her comment on intellectuals laboring with Marx is self-referential, for Arendt is herself also engaged in the same activity as she engages Marx¹ in the section – implying that his thinking is quite exhausted by now, and only engaged for the public interest... and to make a living.

But if that was her actual motive the book would be far from as influential as it is! For while *labor* and *work* once had clear distinctions in history, Arendt accuses Marx of fusing and confusing them for one another, and Arendt will spend this and the next section on separating them once again. There are good reasons for this in both activities, but here Arendt focuses on labor being the activity historically associated with *slaves* because it was *non-political*. Labor has not become despised for being the activity of slaves, it was despised and made to a slave's drudgery because it had to be excluded from your life for you to be free, *political*, and human.

She continues with this premise (labor=slavery) by noting that laborers were generally seen as being outside the political realm, and that the term *animal laborans* should be given special attention as the slaves was considered non-human; beasts of burden². This was tragically misunderstood by Marx and Adam Smith since they defined humans by their ability to produce, which is a property of *both* labor *and* work, and thereby began to rehabilitate *animal laborans* into a central role in society and politics. Here, Arendt believes, is where we began to mix labor with work.

¹ The Human Condition grew out of a project where Arendt intended to criticize Marx.

² Arendt argues in *Origins of Totalitarianism* that humans outside the political community has no rights at all, a situation Giorgio Agamben calls “Bare Life” or, borrowing Greek terms, *Bios* in contrast to *Zoe*.

Marx and Smith were willing to distinguish between skilled and unskilled *labor* and intellectual and non-intellectual *work*, but instead of seeing labor and work as distinct activities they equated them and then made internal distinctions, so that we have a society where work can be considered labor (i.e. factories) and labor considered as “unproductive” while in reality being highly productive but only circular, non-lasting, and not contributing to the human artifice (i.e. the gendered *labor* of the household activities often attributed to housewives such as laundry, child-rearing, cleaning etc.). One may use Arendt’s analysis of the slavery of labor to scrutinize the power-dynamics of maternity wards, as done by Emily Martin in “The Woman in the Body”.

This is Arendt’s central insight: with us mixing labor and work we’ve constructed a society that simultaneously privilege the creating of lasting objects over the “unproductive” activities, while also reducing all those lasting objects into labor-goods to be consumed.

The consequences of this are (among many other that we will encounter through the book):

- *Workers* have, in Arendt’s interpretation of Marx, become alienated *laborers* (i.e.: *slaves*).
- Society has become a consumer society that consumes all objects.
- Intellectuals have lost their place in society since the unproductivity and temporarily of mere thoughts can’t be made into use-objects. Therefore, thinkers have done like Plato, and not Socrates, and *write* things down, i.e., produce a piece of *work* to be *consumed* by society. Thinkers can’t be workers or laborers; it destroys the freedom of thoughts³.

Chapter 12 – The Thing-Character of the World

Following the massive chapter 11 Arendt makes a brief chapter where she notes how the public realm can only be constructed upon a human artifice that last. Since labor is circular and short-lasting it is highly unfit to achieve this, and since all durable work-objects have become consumption-objects we are in quite the pickle as we’re treating our public realm as consumable. Attentive readers will realize the ecological aspect of this argument, she will engage this towards the end of the book. Both the ecological argument but also the existentialist.

Here we also see one example of why *The Human Condition* is a book that require a re-read. She gives a brief introduction to her analysis of Action and argues that we must have objects to reify Action-activities and make them lasting. For example, if we did not have Homer we would not know about the Trojan War⁴ and the story of Odysseus.

Once again Arendt uses ‘the world’ as a term to refer to the public sphere.

³ Arendt makes this a central aspect of her moral thinking since she believes thoughts seeking to produce something is not thinking in itself but a form of ‘reckoning with consequences’ and for us to not fall for banal evil we must be able to think freely without a specific goal in mind.

⁴ In an essay called “The Crisis of Culture” Arendt argues that our consumer society have begun to consume our inherited culture so that Goethe can be transformed from his historical context into our contemporary society for easy consumption by society. In doing this we are stripping ourselves of the richness of our historical *work-objects* and we lose contact with our past. I find the argument not very convincing, the production of a movie doesn’t mean the original documents disappear.

Chapter 13 – Labor and Life

Having established the need for a durable framework to establish a public sphere, Arendt argues that we also transform it. A framework is made to last and is self-perpetuating (as we will see in the Work-section) and creates the conditions for human uniqueness. Arendt writes:

Without a world into which men are born and from which they die, there would be nothing but changeless eternal recurrence, the deathless everlastingness of the human as of all other animal species (p. 97)

So, while labor can be understood as a circle that always repeats the same, and work as the movement from A to B, Action is the interruption of these activities. In another word, it's free will⁵.

She ends chapter 13 by, what I think, is an incredibly prescient insight that labor also includes the preservation of our human artifice against nature's intrusion into it. I understand this as us keeping our objects in a state of functionality, and that repairing and restoring items has become one of those "unproductive" activities that's better replaced by a theoretically productive activity (*GDP*), such as the creation of a new use-object. In other words, I think Arendt argues that our confusion of labor and work is the source for us preferring to buy new equipment rather than committing to the *labor* of fixing or repairing slight damages to them.

So, in these chapters Arendt has not only shown a feminist critique of the political economy in our idea of unproductive activities, but also an ecological critique in us consuming use-objects and then buying them anew instead of restoring the original object.

Discussion questions

1. If Arendt thinks that we need lasting objects to make action and public appearances lasting, how do we understand contemporary culture focused on fiction, where biographical movies is one of the less popular genres? Are we missing the existential meaning of art? *Is 300 the political movie par-excellence?*
2. If labor is the activity for slaves and *animal laborans*, should we understand the production of consumption-goods as a form of slavery too? It is, as Arendt argues, a form of production of consumption-goods
3. Have intellectuals and philosophers really lost their place in modern and capitalist society?
4. Is Arendt correct by claiming that labor can't create a public sphere? It strikes me as saying that slaves could not be political as their life was defined by laboring, which seems quite problematic.
5. Is the reparation and restoring of broken objects seen as an inherently meaningless activity? Can't it also be seen as a form of work since it restores historical objects, or does it only 'count' for objects produced before 20th century mass-production?

⁵ Arendt makes a comment on the determinism/free will discussion by using phenomenology. She notes that the past is determined, the present always *is*, and the future is unknowable. Since we can't be in the past as we're always in the now, we are making a mistake by looking to the past, as inaccessible, to try and determine the future. It's a mistake in phenomenological *intentionality*.

Seminar 6: chapters 14-15

Having established how the confusion of work and labor is dangerous, leading to the consumption of our public sphere and degradation of use-objects into consumer objects, Arendt now tries to understand why labor was paradoxically remade into a political activity, while also providing some positive characteristics of labor and the phenomenological negatives of it.

Major themes

- Why labor became a political problem for Locke, Smith and Marx
- Why none of them managed to resolve the problem, but only created the issues discussed in the previous session.
- The nature of wealth accumulation as a process (*very* important for the final section)
- Labor as pain, and pain as a politically irrelevant

Chapter 14 – Labor and Fertility

Having discussed the confusion of work and labor Arendt now turns to history to find the reason for it. She had already identified how Smith and Marx made the work-labor mix into a proper philosophical system, but Arendt thinks it's true beginning was the early modern realization of labors incredible productivity.

Having lost the reliability of the given world⁶ thinkers began to reformulate European philosophy around introspection instead of the scholastics' Aristotelian (natural) philosophy. This introduced new perspectives and thinking, at which the early modern accumulation of wealth and rapid growth became a fascination, as this growth and potential could provide a clear break with previous societies. Trying to understand it Locke, Smith and Marx all arrived at the same fundamental force as the foundation for all progress: labor. For Locke labor created all property, for Smith labor created wealth, and for Marx an entire all-embracing philosophical system.

What they all had in common was a metaphor with labor and life⁷. Just as life can create more life so can labor create more laborers, in this they misunderstand labor's inherent unproductivity (it produces nothing of durability) and equates it with the traits of work (which has durability). This failure of distinction is the origin of the western world mixing work and labor.

This is also one of Arendt's main characteristics of modern society. In *Origins of Totalitarianism* she argues that Hobbes realization that power begets more power was a core force that drove Europe into imperialism and eventually WW1. But it's not just power that becomes self-intensifying, the concept of progress shares the same dynamic of being self-reinforcing and self-strengthening, which becomes very important in the final section of the book.

⁶ A claim made and analyzed by Arendt in the final section; in brief she argues that early modern Europe was in a full cosmological breakdown following the discovery of the Americas, craters on the moon, and the challenge to Catholicism in Luther, and that the seeming unreliability of all previous knowledge made Descartes formulate his universal doubt and forced philosophy into introspection. See p.248.

⁷ One of the best books in medical anthropology I've read uses the insight of labor as a metaphor for life an example of how male doctors have reduced female pregnancies and deliveries into the discourse of a factory – and objectifies the body. Emily Martin's "The Woman in the Body" (1987)

Arendt ends chapter 14 by noting how labor used to have positive existential properties, being a core aspect of the happiness in being alive, before it was reduced into a means for progress:

The right to the pursuit of this happiness is indeed as undeniable as the right to life; it is even identical with it [...] There is no lasting happiness outside the prescribed cycle of painful exhaustion and pleasurable regeneration, and whatever throws this cycle out of balance – poverty and misery where exhaustion is followed by wretchedness instead of regeneration, or great riches and entirely effortless life where boredom takes the place of exhaustion and where the mills of necessity, of consumption and digestion, grinds an impotent human body mercilessly and barrenly to death – ruins the elemental happiness that comes from being alive (p.108)

Chapter 15 – The Privacy and Property of Wealth

Reiterating her argument that a society of property-holders (capitalism) have an explicit antagonism against both the common realm and the state, she now introduced the insight drawn from chapter 14 in the process-character of modern society. She had already made this implicit connection in chapter 9⁸.

The consequence of this unending process of wealth accumulation is that it cannot stop, and it will inevitably result in the consumption of the private sphere into production-orientation. Here Arendt is likely referring to our entire lives becoming oriented towards salaried laboring and daily work, but reading it I realized that she could equally be referring to the *consumption of our private sphere with mass-data and surveillance capitalism*.

She argues that our bodies are safe from this wholesale incorporation into the wealth-accumulation process since our bodies are always going to be private – however I believe this is wrong as we today have our biomarkers and biodata harvested en-masse by corporations like 23-and-me and Amazon. I believe our bodies have become very public.

But she also argues that a focus on the body is incompatible with public appearance since the body is an *'what'* and not an *'who'* and that our personalities are more than mere objects. Trying to understand a *who* from *what* is what Wordsworth called “murder to dissect”. But this is equally a critique on Hedonism, since a focus on bodily pleasures is our personal focus on what rather than who we are⁹.

The opposite is equally true. Pain, like pleasure, is also non-political¹⁰. While pleasure does not develop our subjectivity, pain completely absorb it in the panicked introversion, so that the reality of our surroundings becomes incomprehensible in the face of the overwhelming attention given to our bodies in pain. In both examples reality becomes detached from our subjectivity and we're turned inwards instead of outwards towards the public sphere.

⁸ “However, this permanence [of capitalism] is of a different nature; it is the permanence of a process rather than the permanence of a stable structure” (p.69).

⁹ Refer for example to Nozick's experience machine argument against Hedonism.

¹⁰ In *On Violence* Arendt makes a clear argument that violence, like pain, can only emulate the political in coercion - you can force people to act politically under pain. But this is only a veneer of politics that can never sustain itself.

Discussion questions

1. Arendt argues that our bodies will always be private. I believe this is wrong today due to new technology allowing a reach into our most private spheres, but the argument also seems wrong in 1958, with the female body and reproduction of humanity being a very public concern.
2. Arendt argues that pain is non-political because it separates us from reality. It seems naïve since politics can give rise to systematic infliction of pain, in which the pain becomes a political reality and a tool. Maybe she is normative rather than descriptive? She was a holocaust survivor, so she had intimate knowledge on the politics of pain.
3. According to Arendt, the philosophies of the early-modern age shifted labor into life. Is it a coincidence that the event of giving birth is referred to as “going into labor”?

Seminar 7: chapters 16-17

Having described labor as a circular activity required for life and the very existence of politics, and actually being a unproductive activity in opposition to the early-modern belief, Arendt now begins to look ahead. Previously she argued that we had them mixed up and must make distinctions, now she begins to give a more detailed contrast between labor and work.

Major themes

- How labor has taken the shape of a machine, and why it is dangerous
- Why labor is like slavery, and part of our existential condition
- How the labor-society became a consumer's society
- Why the consumer's society destroys the durability of the world to find meaning in life.

Chapter 16 – The Instruments of Work and the Division of Labor

Seeing the title of the chapter, it becomes clear that Arendt is taking aim at the interactions between labor and work, specifically the use-objects of work (instruments/tools) and the consumption-objects (food/clothes) of labor.

Arendt begins, once again, by reiterating how labor can only produce labor-objects, which do not last and is done under the yoke of our biological/physical necessity. This means that labor can't produce freedom in itself but only the pre-political conditions for it, here we once again see her argument why labor was the household activity and can't be public or political.

From this she then argued that Marx's goal in a society of laborers means that we turn ourselves into a collection of the species mankind (*animal laborans*), and not humans. She argues that Marx's emphasis on human productivity ignores the crucial aspect of man being political and strive for public individual appearance. Since labor corresponds to our biological necessities for survival, it is compulsive in life, and can't be ignored or done away with – it's forced on us.

Through this equation Arendt argues that life is a form of slavery, which is an important insight she uses to critique the activity. For as labor is an inherent part of our given existence and therefore central to our human condition. This takes us into the relation between work and labor.

By reformulating labor as life, and work as technology¹¹, she notes how life can't last forever, while technology exists independently of our own finite lifespan. However, she argues, it's not this simple, for labor/life creates the conditions *for* our technology, while technology can then *change the premises* for our lives and labor.

So far technology has only made life/labor easier and less painful and compulsive, but it has not (until recently?) been able to change life itself. In other words, technology has changed the premises for our lives but not the human condition of labor/life itself yet, and Arendt encourages us to be careful in doing this since it would be an enormous break in all traditions of human existence and politics¹².

¹¹Labor, since it's not political, can't create reality. This argument will become clearer in later sections.

¹² It strikes me as she was prescient about the ethical concerns about biotechnology already in 1958.

Yet, she notices, we have already begun to change our human condition by another form of technology in The Social's division of labor¹³. With it we've already altered the condition in which we labor. Previously labor was a form of wholistic activity that contained several different forms of actions, but when we divide these into repetitive single acts we've alienated ourselves from the natural rhythm of our existential life-process. She notes how this has the twofold result of both alienating ourselves from our human condition, as 'natural' labor is an essential part of it, but also how it, taken from its broadest perspective, massifies us into single Hobbesian leviathan: an artificial person conducting the life process through each person's individual section of The Social machine.

This machine-like laboring also results in the leviathan-machine imitating the dynamic of labor in that it becomes endless and will continue to accumulate wealth, as argued in the previous chapters. Once this is combined with the decline of use-objects into consumption-objects, consumption will continue eternally. As the productivity of labor increases, so will the wealth accumulation, and so will consumption. *Everything is accelerating, while nothing is built to last.*

Chapter 17 – A Consumer's Society

With the closing chapter on labor Arendt tries to give a general overview of her argument, while also characterizing the society we've created through the emancipation of labor. Notice also how she uses the singular possessive in the title, and writes it from the perspective that the consumers, who have a natural orientation towards the bodily and is therefore individualistic, dominate the society she's been describing in this section.

With the argument in chapter 16, that our society has become a laboring machine, we've created a consumer society since labor only result in biologically necessary consumption, so that

[w]e have almost succeeded in leveling all human activities to the common denominator of securing the necessities of life and providing for their abundance. Whatever we do, we are supposed to do for the sake of 'making a living' (p.126)

Since we're all becoming consuming laborers, who must produce things to be seen as "productive," then the pursuit of human thinking and the non-materiality of ideas is becoming increasingly untenable a career, as we can see in the "publish or perish"-culture of our academies. This is what she jokes with in the first chapter of this section, chapter 5.

This hyper-focus on labor means that everything that doesn't belong in the laboring activity becomes mere leisurely 'play', so that all workmanship or artistry is not seen as serious activities unless it becomes an object of consumption or making a living. Everything else is a mere hobby, and with hobbies' delegation into pastime activities our meaningful activities are rapidly disappearing for the mere biological imperative of surviving.

It all results in a mankind "free to 'consume' the whole world and to reproduce daily all things it wishes to consume" (p.132) while not producing any meaning from it. Meaning in the consumer's society is consumption, as it's the goal of the entire system.

¹³ While Arendt doesn't recognize it as a machine, Lewis Mumford has argued that large social techniques in production should be viewed as machines and technology.

The laboring process, as described in chapter 16, will continue autonomously and amplify:

[t]he rhythm of machines would magnify and intensify the natural rhythm of life enormously, but it would not change, only make more deadly, life's chief character with respect to the world, which is to wear down durability (p.132).

Since we don't find any meaning in our labor nor our hobbies, it is consumption that fills that role, ending in "the grave danger that eventually no object of the world will be safe from consumption and annihilation through consumption" (p.133).

The environmental consequences of this society are well visible for us today. And I want to end this summary of Arendt's understanding of labor in politics with this quote on page 134:

One of the obvious danger signs that we may be on our way to bring into existence the ideal of the *animal laborans* is the extent to which our whole economy has become a waste economy, in which things must be almost as quickly devoured and discarded as they have appeared in the world, if the process itself is not to come to a sudden catastrophic end.

Discussion questions:

1. Is she correct?
2. Do we still live in a consumer's society?
3. In chapter 16 Arendt imply that our division of labor makes society appear like a laboring machine, do you agree?
4. Have meaning disappeared into consumption today?
5. Is it possible to have a consumer's society while also ecological soundness?

Part 4: Work

Seminar 8: chapters 18-20

This write-up became much longer than I expected. Reading the chapters I realized that this is where Arendt introduces the central argument in the book, namely that we have created a form of process-society that will automatically follow a machine-like procedure unable to stop nor avoid the inevitable disaster of unending processes. The complexity of Arendt's argument also made me write this summary in detail to give as much explanation of her thoughts as possible.

These chapters' central argument mirrors a claim in the *Origins of Totalitarianism*, where Arendt argues that imperialism took the shape of the same automated process, the same type of dynamic that she describes here regarding technology. Origin's argument can be summarized:

No matter what individual qualities or defects a man may have, once he has entered the maelstrom of an unending process of expansion, he will, as it were, cease to be what he was and obey the laws of the process, identify himself with anonymous forces that he is supposed to serve in order to keep the whole process in motion; he will think of himself as mere function, and eventually consider such functionality, such an incarnation of the dynamic trend, his highest possible achievement.

[...]

But when the last war has come and every man has been provided for, no ultimate peace is established on earth: the power-accumulating machine, without which continual expansion would not have been achieved, needs more material to devour in its never-ending process. If the last victorious Commonwealth cannot proceed to "annex the planets," it can only proceed to destroy itself in order to begin anew the never-ending process of power generation.

Major themes

- How work is principally different from labor, but has become *like* labor
- Why work has become like a rhythm, and the rhythm like automatic processes, and the automatic processes our engine for social progress.
- Why work has reached a point of no return in regard to durability

Chapter 18 – The Durability of the World

Beginning this new section Arendt makes the fundamental distinction between work and labor in the *vita activa*: Labor creates the biological necessities for human existence and politics, work fabricates "the sheer unending variety of things whose sum total constitutes the human artifice."

Already in this opening sentence Arendt introduces two human types that will return in this section: *animal laborans* (laboring beasts) and *Homo Faber* (producing/working humans). While the laborer can't establish anything more than a larger number of itself, see previous section, *Homo Faber* is what creates the structure of stability and solidity (durability) within which the unpredictability of humanity takes place.

Arendt is however quick to make note that this artifice and stability is only relative and not absolute. Nothing lasts, and just like mankind itself has a life-process, so do all items and use objects. Men shall return to the dirt, just as a chair will eventually return to wood. In this way work is like labor: circular. But, while labor can't create any lasting artifice for humanity, work's long durability makes it suitable for this end. Arendt stresses this, usage is different from consumption in that usage only wear down durability, while consumption is destruction. *Consuming* (destroying) the world is different from *using* the world (wearing down its circular durability).

A unique feature of durability is its independence from the creator. A consumption object has no durability, food only last a few days before spoiling, while durable objects endure time. This has profound effects on us since it both creates an objective and positioned world we can understand and through it create chronologies and the experience that time stretches backwards in time: that history is real.

If not for the independent durability of the world around us the relativist claim that everything is contingent on our subjectivity would be true:

In other words, against the subjectivity of men stands the objectivity of the man-made world rather than the sublime indifference of an untouched nature, whose overwhelming elementary force, on the contrary, will compel them to swing relentlessly in the circle of their own biological movement [...] Only we who have erected the objectivity of a world of our own from what nature gives us, who have built it into the environment of nature so that we are protected from her, can look upon nature as something "objective". Without a world between men and nature, there is eternal movement but no objectivity. (p.137).

Expecting the counterargument that the *usage* of the environment is similar to *consuming* it, Arendt agrees that there is a similarity between them but notes how a village field is not necessarily made for *consumption* but *usage* to create the foodstuffs necessary for a society. If the durability of a field is to sustain it requires incessant labor. Here one may make the comparison to the use-objects that we prefer to treat as consumption objects (waste) rather than use labor to restore to their original functionality, as Arendt highlighted in the previous section.

Chapter 19 – Reification

The example of the field requiring constant labor makes the case for use-objects' need of reification: the reproduction of objects that, as with everything, can't last forever. This is a trait of all material who itself exists in their own life-processes that we interrupt in order to create our own artifice. To build a house we need to interrupt the life process of the tree to gain its wood, to produce drinks we must interrupt the life process of water. It's interesting how Arendt uses the term *life process* in discussing our use of nature – she does this to give emphasis of the violence inherent in work and its reification. As she writes: "Homo faber, the creator of the human artifice, has always been a destroyer of nature." (p.139.)

This is the central paradox of humanity: we're both the violent masters of nature, and its slaves. Theology may have given the western man¹⁴ the self-image of an unbound divinity unleashed on a garden to go forth and procreate, but we're inevitably bound to nature and life.

This is also another fundamental difference between labor and work since the latter requires strength and violence, and is therefore man applying itself *on* nature instead of *within* nature:

[Work's violence] can provide self-assurance and satisfaction, and can even become a source of self-confidence throughout life, all of which are quite different from the bliss which can be attend a life spent in labor and toil or from the fleeting, though intense pleasure of laboring itself which comes about if the effort is coordinated and rhythmically ordered, and which essentially is the same as the pleasure felt in other rhythmic body movements. (p.140).

This applying *on* nature also means we are not following the flow of the urgencies of life, but use a model that we've received or appropriated from somewhere – where did we get the idea of what a chair should look like, or for that matter a flower, or a statue symbolizing justice? Arendt thinks we rarely are fully creative but usually appropriates our approach towards the environment from external sources. Making this claim she uses the phenomenological critique against Cartesian dualism in which we believe that our minds are free to apply themselves on an objective nature – Arendt believes our ideas are informed by our *being in the world*:

What claims our attention is the veritable gulf that separates all bodily sensations, pleasure or pain, desires and satisfactions – which are so “private” that they cannot even be adequately voiced, much less represented in the outside world, and therefore are altogether incapable of being reified—from mental images which lend themselves so easily and naturally to reification that we neither conceive of making a bed without first having some image, some “idea” of a bed before our inner eye, nor can imagine a bed without having recourse to some visual experience of a real thing. (p.141)

These received models could crudely be described as culture, and Arendt thinks it's of great importance that the durable objects produced *from* this model then becomes the artifice *for* that model, thus creating an 'infinite continuation of fabrication' in multiplication of the same model-formed object. This is also the reason why work can't solve the contradiction it's found itself in, as we shall see in the next chapter. According to Arendt this phenomenon is the foundation for Plato's eternal ideas, which are essentially the same as Arendt's abstract models.

Basing all work on models also means that work takes the form of mean-ends logics. Models are always oriented towards making the end product as close to the model ideal (turning wood into the abstract concept of a chair) and achieve its durability independent of human intervention. Without the same compulsion of necessity that drives labor, work can be pursued for multiple reasons “outside itself,” such as market conditions, art, memory, construction of a city etcetera.

Since work has this definitive beginning in violence, and predictable end in a model, it distinguishes itself from both labor and action as being the most reliable and independent. Labor is always bound to the laborer (unless exploited) and action, as we shall see, is unpredictable.

¹⁴ Arendt claims this is universal to humanity, which I believe is strictly false as there are many other communities and cultures that posits a far more wholistic conception on the relationship between man and nature.

Chapter 20 – Instrumentality and *Animal Laborans*

Animal Laborans, as seen in the previous section, is a consumer. *Homo Faber*, in distinction, is a tool maker. The tools they make is designed for objective use, as in solving some issue or easing some pain. We've mixed these up.

Arendt believes that labor's triumph in modernity is what caused the switch in the relationship between man and machine, so that machine now rules man and not man ruling machine. As laboring is cyclical, it destroys work's unique means-end character, and with that it loses its instrumental character. Our production of a specific tool becomes a labor-like rhythm, and not a self-contained project. This insight will become crucial for later parts of *The Human Condition*.

This labor-like productive rhythm becomes a form of automation-process that reduces the person in the productive process into a part of the production machine:

What dominates the labor process and all work processes which are performed in the mode of laboring is neither man's purposeful effort nor the product he may desire, but the motion of the process itself and the rhythm it imposes upon the laborers. Labor implements are drawn into this rhythm until body and tool swing in the same repetitive movement, that is, until, in the use of machines, which of all implements are best suited to the performance of the *animal laborans*, it is no longer the body's movement that determines the implement's movement but the machine's movement which enforces the movements of the body. The point is that nothing can be mechanized more easily and less artificially than the rhythm of the labor process, which in its turn corresponds to the equally automatic repetitive rhythm of the life process and its metabolism with nature (p. 146).

This machine-rhythm of modern laboring society also affects our subjectivity. Using her phenomenological premise, this machine-rhythm automation becomes a part of our lifeworld, so our very lives and experiences too take the form of an automatic rhythm¹⁵. In the context of technological advances, this automatic rhythm can be understood as the inevitable progression towards progress, and in this progression we've taken several radical steps without seemingly realizing it. She mentions how electricity is *homo faber* controlling the natural forces we previously tried to escape:

Today we have begun to "create," as it were, that is, to unchain natural processes of our own which would never have happened without us, and instead of carefully surrounding the human artifice with defenses against nature's elementary forces, keeping them as far as possible outside the man-made world, we have channeled these forces, along with their elementary power, into the world itself. (p.148f)

This is a radical transformation since the power made available to us threatens the existence of all organic life on earth, and as the machine-rhythm of our lives continues we'll continue to discover more and more tools to increase our power, and the threat they also contain. In other words, work has reached a point of no return. The more *Homo Faber* continues to create tools and enhance our technologies, the less likely durability is. Arendt summarize the issue:

¹⁵ While she does not discuss it in *The Human Condition* this universal logic of all existence can be compared the natural laws on which the totalitarian movements was founded. The connection between the Italian futurists and the fascists is not new, and for the futurists the automation and factory rhythm was the key to a new humanity, just like race science and dialectic materialism was for the Nazis and Bolsheviks respectively.

The question therefore is not so much whether we are the masters or the slaves of our machines, but whether machines still serve the world and its things, or if, on the contrary, they and the automatic motion of their processes have begun to rule and even destroy world and things. (p.151)

Since we're being affected by the automation-rhythm, and our lifeworlds becomes like machines, we're stuck in a truly dangerous situation in which we will continue to produce more and more dangers to the world, while being unable to stop it, just like our consumer's society is unable to stop the process of the waste-economy. To summarize these very important chapters Arendt ends with a conclusion:

For a society of laborers, the world of machines has become a substitute for the real world, even though this pseudo world cannot fulfil the most important task of the human artifice, which is to offer mortals a dwelling place more permanent and more stable than themselves. In the continuous process of operation, this world of machines is even losing that independent worldly character which the tools and implements and the early machinery of the modern age so eminently possessed. The natural processes on which it feeds increasingly relate it to the biological process itself, so that the apparatuses we once handled freely begin to look as though they were "shells belonging to the human body as the shell belongs to the body of a turtle." Seen from the vantage point of this development, technology in fact no longer appears "as the product of a conscious human effort to enlarge material power, but rather like a biological development of mankind in which the innate structures of the human organism are transplanted in an ever increasing measure into the environment of man."

Discussion questions:

1. Is she correct?
2. Do our lives have the form of a process?
3. Does our continued discovery of technologies and tools reduce the likelihood of the world's durability?
4. Have our machines-society become our lived world?
5. Do we rule machines, or do machines rule us?

Seminar 9: chapters 21-23

Having, in the previous chapters, argued that modern society has the shape of an automated process of 'progress,' Arendt now turns to the consequences this has for our public sphere – what she usually refers to as 'the world.'

These chapters will feature two central arguments in Arendt's general thinking, the difference between reflexive and instrumental thinking (which she calls *thought* respectively *cognition* in chapter 24) and the importance of public art in our subjectivity, democracy, and freedom.

Major themes

- How meaning has disappeared with Homo Faber's utilitarianism
- How the exchange market became a placeholder for the agora, and the detriments this have on both politics and Homo Faber itself
- Why art has the possibility of liberation, and a source for our thinking
- How thinking differs from cognition, and how cognition relates to the machine society

Chapter 21 – Instrumentality and *Homo Faber*

Since the world now is in an automatic machine-rhythm, our experience of the world takes a similar form. The worldview of modern working humanity, singularly focused on the model of production, is always in the means-end perspective:

The end justifies the violence done to nature to win the material, as the wood justifies killing the tree and the table justifies destroying the wood. Because of the end product, tools are designed and implements invented, and the same end product organizes the work process itself, decides about the needed specialists, the measure of co-operation, the number of assistants, etc. During the work process, everything is judged in terms of suitability and usefulness for the desired end, and for nothing else. (p.154)

This means-end-orientation, *Instrumentalization* as Arendt refers to it, eventually becomes self-reflecting so that any object (end-product) produced in this instrumentalizing frame eventually becomes viewed as a means for something else, whose end-product will then also become a mean for a third product. This creates an unending chain of products always viewed as "in order to" – reinforcing the process-like character of modernity's economy.

Thus Arendt argues that *Homo Faber* is the utilitarian par excellence, for just like the utility-property of an object is the usefulness of *something*, *Homo Faber* has become unable to define what the actual end-use of all the products are. As Arendt writes, citing Lessing: "And what is the use of use?". In this society of use without ends meaning has disappeared, except for the meaning of the process itself. Stopping the process would be to break the very use-means mentality of *Homo Faber*, it's premise for being able to act.

The loss of identifiable ends in the world (meaning), and the loss of *objectivity* of the world (as in the durable objects existing independent of us; everything has become resources and therefore subjectivized) has made us try to find a replacement for meaning by introspection¹⁶.

¹⁶ This is an *absolutely* crucial claim that underpins Arendt's argument that our subjectification of reality has displaced us from the world. It's the argument that supports the concept of the Archimedean Point and is simultaneously its connection to the concept of World Alienation.

This self-focus (*Descartes*) has resulted in modernity's anthropocentrism, and has taken its ultimate form in Kant's Principle of Humanity – that we must always treat humans as ends and never means – which would've been quite unnecessary before *Homo Faber* made all aspects of the world (including other humans) into potential means.

Not even Kant could solve the perplexity or enlighten the blindness of homo faber with respect to the problem of meaning without turning to the paradoxical "end in itself," and this perplexity lies in the fact that while only fabrication with its instrumentality is capable of building a world, this same world becomes as worthless as the employed material, a mere means for further ends, if the standards which governed its coming into being are permitted to rule it after its establishment. (p.156)

And while Kant tried to save humanity from *Homo Faber's* utility-process, he was unable to change the instrumentalization (ends reduction into means) of the world:

The instrumentalization of the whole world and the earth, this limitless devaluation of everything given, this process of growing meaninglessness where every end is transformed into a means and which can be stopped only by making man himself the lord and master of all things, does not directly arise out of the fabrication process; for from the viewpoint of fabrication the finished product is as much an end in itself, an independent durable entity with an existence of its own, as man is an end in himself in Kant's political philosophy. (p.157)

Here can we arguably see *the* clearest parallels between Arendt and her old mentor Heidegger, who had been thinking and lecturing on the same topics before publishing his Question Concerning Technology. Just to display how similar they are in their concern over the reduction of nature into ontological instrumentalization (H.A)"/"enframing" (M.H), see these two quotes:

Hannah Arendt; Instrumentality and Homo Faber	Martin Heidegger; Question Concerning Technology
<p>the wind will no longer be understood in its own right as a natural force but will be considered exclusively in accordance with human needs for warmth or refreshment—which, of course, means that the wind as something objectively given has been eliminated from human experience.</p>	<p>The earth now reveals itself as a coal mining district, the soil as a mineral deposit. The field that the peasant formerly cultivated and set in order appears differently than it did when to set in order still meant to take care of and to maintain. [...] Agriculture is now the mechanized food industry. Air is now set upon to yield nitrogen, the earth to yield ore, ore to yield uranium, for example, uranium is set upon to yield atomic energy, which can be released either for destruction or for peaceful use</p>

Chapter 22 – The Exchange Market

[T]he modern age was as intent on excluding political man, that is, man who acts and speaks, from its public realm as antiquity was on excluding homo faber. (Page.159)

The quote above can summarize the entirety of the section on Work. When our society has been reduced into a consumption society, and driven by rhythmic and automatic processes, then actual politics – as we shall see in the next chapter – have become nothing but “‘idle talk’ and ‘vain-glory’” (ibid.).

The agora of today, our public sphere, has been reduced into a capitalist exchange market. Arendt is clear that this was not necessarily a bad thing in itself, and will spend a large section of the chapter in arguing how the possibilities of liberating work was lost under capitalism.

At first sight it seems like work can simulate the dynamics of action (*appearance in the public sphere*). If we view politics as the possibility to display ourselves to our peers, then the work of our hands is not necessarily a bad simulation of speech and action since they both reveal ourselves as an *who* instead of an *what*¹⁷. We all produce things with our own characteristics.

Even more, *Homo Faber* (as pre-industrial artisan) had the same private/public distinction as the Greek agora. A private sphere where the production of an object was created, and a public sphere where they went to reveal it and gain recognition. However, like modernity mixed the private and the public, so did the artisans lose the private/public dynamic. They became required to accept assistants in the workshop, and thereby gained the division of labor that ends up in the destruction of the holism of the production-activity for machine-like dynamics.

There can be hardly anything more alien or even more destructive to workmanship than teamwork, which actually is only a variety of the division of labor and presupposes the "breakdown of operations into their simple constituent motions." The team, the multiheaded subject of all production carried out according to the principle of division of labor, possesses the same togetherness as the parts which form the whole, and each attempt of isolation on the part of the members of the team would be fatal to the production itself. But it is not only this togetherness which the master and workman lacks while actively engaged in production; the specifically political forms of being together with others, acting in concert and speaking with each other, are completely outside the range of his productivity. (Page.161-162)

Even the public sphere, *the last occurrence of it*, was connected to the work of the artisan *Homo Faber*. As the agora was the area in which heroic deeds was recorded, so was the exchange market the place where great deed of creation was recognized and valued – for example the renaissance masters. However, the people meeting in the exchange market are not persons-qua-persons but “owners of commodities and exchange values”.

This is where we the exchange market lost its political possibilities. Citing Marx, Arendt argues that the reduction of our production into exchange goods, from goods revealing *who* we are into producers of *what*, also meant that we as humans became goods too – Marx’s self-alienation.

¹⁷ I actually believe this connection between product and person is the same simulation of interpersonal engagement that’s used by corporations to create relatable personas like Colonel Sanders, the ‘Samsung Girl’ or Geico Gecko and etcetera.

So as nature became instrumentalized with the disappearance of ends, we became instrumentalized upon the exchange market's domination of the public sphere.

Without the exchange market as an 'political' sphere we would never have developed capitalism, partly because the actions taken by the participants in the exchange market (as will become clearer in the next section) but also because reality is shaped by the conditions of the public sphere¹⁸. As the *interpersonal exchange* of the agora became the *commodity exchange* of the marketplace another¹⁹ terminological confusion was created, this time between *values* and *value*.

For it is only in the exchange market, where everything can be exchanged for something else, that all things, whether they are products of labor or work, consumer goods or use objects, necessary for the life of the body or the convenience of living or the life of the mind, become "values." This value consists solely in the esteem of the public realm where the things appear as commodities, and it is neither labor, nor work, nor capital, nor profit, nor material, which bestows such value upon an object, but only and exclusively the public realm where it appears to be esteemed, demanded, or neglected. Value is the quality a thing can never possess in privacy but acquires automatically the moment it appears in public. (p.163-164)

Having previously argued how the singularity of the private sphere – and its lack of plurality – only provide a singular perspective, and that the public sphere is crucial for the establishment of higher values and 'culture,' the reduction of the agora into exchange market has reduced these shared values into the negotiated valuations. If the context for our gatherings is to negotiate commodity exchange, over the discussion of values, these shared upon 'truths' becomes relative to the market. This has the ironic effect that Homo Faber's public sphere lead to the inevitable reduction of the solid objectivity required for their activity:

Universal relativity, that a thing exists only in relation to other things, and loss of intrinsic worth, that nothing any longer possesses an "objective" value independent of the ever-changing estimations of supply and demand, are inherent in the very concept of value itself. The reason why this development, which seems inevitable in a commercial society, became a deep source of uneasiness and eventually constituted the chief problem of the new science of economics was not even relativity as such, but rather the fact that homo faber, whose whole activity is determined by the constant use of yardsticks, measurements, rules, and standards, could not bear the loss of "absolute" standards or yardsticks. (Page.166)

The consequence of the market society is this relativity. Once everything has become a commodity – inevitable under the consumption society following automatic processes – then the permanence of the world is lost. As is more than obvious in our times, everything has become fluid and reality itself (aided by technology) have become a commodity sold by corporations like Cambridge Analytica.

¹⁸ "Being seen and being heard by others derive their significance from the fact that everybody sees and hears from a different position. [...] Only where things can be seen by many in a variety of aspects without changing their identity, so that those who are gathered around them know they see sameness in utter diversity, can worldly reality truly and reliably appear" (page.57)

¹⁹ Just like the confusion between labor/work, private/public, and as she argues in later essays between authoritarian/dictatorship/totalitarian, liberty/freedom, and violence/power/force.

Without the public sphere, defined by the meeting of a plurality of humans, then the marketplace will be its replacement where everything is a utility, valuation and not value, – a means for something else – and there is no meaning other than our hard biological beingness, and its single remaining joy: consumption.

Chapter 23 – The Permanence of the World and the Work of Art

Luckily, at least in 1958, everything was not lost. There was one aspect of work that still had its meaning and had yet to be reduced into an exchange good: art.

Among the things that give the human artifice the stability without which it could never be a reliable home for men are a number of objects which are strictly without any utility whatsoever and which, moreover, because they are unique, are not exchangeable and therefore defy equalization through a common denominator such as money; if they enter the exchange market, they can only be arbitrarily priced (page.167)

Since art is not useful for anything productive it is free from *Homo Faber's* instrumentalization. This means that works of art are the only and best anchor we have to preserve the permanence of the world and reality. So, while most other items have become consumption-objects or instrumentalized, art has remained outside the rhythmic and automatic machine society – art, in this way, has a liberatory promise, and is why Arendt is often seen as a very important thinking in art-theory for her strong defense of the importance of public art.

Art's uselessness also means that it has unmatched durability since it barely receives any wear and tear. As durability is equal to independent existence from its creator it also can create the shared world we inhabit from our parent's generation.

Further, by not having any initially obvious use-case, art becomes thought-objects par-excellence – faced with art we're teased to think²⁰ and contemplate what we're viewing to understand it. This dynamic also separates it from the model-to-model dynamic (see previous chapters) of regular objects in the world.

Art-objects	Use-objects
Thoughts -> Art object -> Thoughts -> New art object	Design Model-> End Object-> Idea-model-> Design Model

Use objects follow a framed model of what a table is, and how it should be constructed for that use. Art objects don't have the same framed dynamic and is open to re-interpretation and inspiration, traits that quickly can defeat the usefulness in any use-objects.

Having introduced the *thinking* into the discussion, Arendt now beings to round out the section by first distinguishing and clarifying two different ways of thinking: Cognition and Thoughts;

²⁰ *Far* too long to be included here, but I've argued in a paper that this form of teasing-out-thoughts ("intentionality" in phenomenological jargon; in the case of my paper the messiness of urban life) is crucial for us to be able to retake control over the processes that we're engaging in within our daily lives, and thus provide an opportunity for us to reimagine ourselves and our values. In this way art becomes liberation *and* sustainability.

Thought and cognition are not the same. Thought, the source of art works, is manifest without transformation or transfiguration in all great philosophy, whereas the chief manifestation of the cognitive processes, by which we acquire and store up knowledge, is the sciences. Cognition always pursues a definite aim, which can be set by practical considerations as well as by "idle curiosity"; but once this aim is reached, the cognitive process has come to an end. Thought, on the contrary, has neither an end nor an aim outside itself, and it does not even produce results; not only the utilitarian philosophy of homo faber but also the men of action and the lovers of results in the sciences have never tired of pointing out how entirely "useless" thought is—as useless, indeed, as the works of art it inspires. (Page.170).

Arendt's philosophy on thinking is *truly enormous* and stretches across dozens of different articles and several books and cannot under be fully introduced here. Suffice to say that the true power of thoughts was discovered by Socrates when he realized how nothing holds up under the dissecting blade of thinking, and that thoughts are only destructive²¹ and unable to create anything "objectively true". Cognition, on the other hand, is a form of reckoning with consequences:

Cognition, on the other hand, belongs to all, and not only to intellectual or artistic work processes; like fabrication itself, it is a process with a beginning and end, whose usefulness can be tested, and which, if it produces no results, has failed, like a carpenter's workmanship has failed when he fabricates a two-legged table. The cognitive processes in the sciences are basically not different from the function of cognition in fabrication; scientific results produced through cognition are added to the human artifice like all other things. (Page.171)

The crucial difference between them is that thinking is bound to the subjective existence of humanity, and impossible to recreate in a machine²², while cognition and its logical structure was already being recreated in machines in Arendt's time and has far eclipsed all human capabilities in our time.

Since our age also views thinking as useless (see jokes about philosophy majors) and cognition, as STEM, as valuable, we've created a society better suited for machines than actual humans engaged in our unique subjective abilities to *think*, marvel at existence, and create a shared world in the public sphere:

All that the giant computers prove is that the modern age was wrong to believe with Hobbes that rationality, in the sense of "reckoning with consequences," is the highest and most human of man's capacities, and that the life and labor philosophers, Marx or Bergson or Nietzsche, were right to see in this type of intelligence, which they mistook for reason, a mere function of the life process itself, or, as Hume put it, a mere "slave of the passions." Obviously, this brain power and the compelling logical processes it generates are not capable of erecting a world, are as worldless as the compulsory processes of life, labor, and consumption. (Page. 172)

²¹ And therefore also liberating in modernity's automatic processes and reduction of all values into valuation without creating new structures that limits our ways of *being in the world*.

²² See "What Machines Still Can't Do" by Robert J. Thomas

This is the reason Arendt is commonly referred to as crucial reading regarding AI and 'the coming age of machines,' but this is just the origins of the machine society. There is equally much to say about humans-as-machines in *Origins of Totalitarianism*.

To finally wrap up the section on work (and this enormous write-up), Arendt makes a summary and prepares us for the section on action:

The man-made world of things, the human artifice erected by homo faber, becomes a home for mortal men, whose stability will endure and outlast the ever-changing movement of their lives and actions, only inasmuch as it transcends both the sheer functionalism [*instrumentalization!*] of things produced for consumption [*consumption-society!*] and the sheer utility of objects produced for use [*instrumentalization again!*]. Life in its non-biological sense, the span of time each man has between birth and death, manifests itself in action and speech, both of which share with life its essential futility. The "doing of great deeds and the speaking of great words" will leave no trace, no product that might endure after the moment of action and the spoken word has passed. [...] without them the only product of their activity, the story they enact and tell, would not survive at all. In order to be what the world is always meant to be, a home for men during their life on earth, the human artifice must be a place fit for action and speech, for activities not only entirely useless for the necessities of life but of an entirely different nature from the manifold activities of fabrication by which the world itself and all things in it are produced (Page 173).

And hints on how it's going to be about liberation and freedom:

We need not choose here between Plato and Protagoras, or decide whether man or a god should be the measure of all things; what is certain is that the measure can be neither the driving necessity of biological life and labor nor the utilitarian instrumentalism of fabrication and usage. (*ibid.*)

Discussion questions:

1. Do we only have two types of products today, consumption objects and objects "for the sake of [...]?"
2. Has the marketplace become the public sphere of today? What about the internet? How do we understand it as a place to display ourselves and our deeds?
3. Have our values become valuation?
4. Does public art have such power to change the world through both creating a shared reality while also encouraging thinking?
5. Has not art itself become a "for the sake of [...]" in art-auctions? Wasn't art always about cultural capital? (Baudrillard)
6. Is the distinction between thinking/cognition reasonable? Do we have a cognition-society rather than a thinking society?

Part 5: Action

Seminar 10: chapters 24-27

Walking to the café in which I am writing this I passed by a line of people queuing to the small office where they may place an early vote for the Swedish general election, held tomorrow on the 11th. This is the peak of Swedish political engagement – and it's tragically insufficient from Arendt's perspective. If my highest form of political engagement is standing silently in a line, enter a room to put a cross in a form, and placing it in a small box... then I'm not political, I'm merely participating a statistical exercise.

As we shall see in the coming chapters on Arendt's famous analysis of Action, this rationalistic and Hobbesian form of politics is not just incapable of managing the issues of modern society's technology (see previous chapters), it's equally unsustainable, alienating, and profoundly boring. What Arendt will present in the following chapters is an alternative where politics becomes self-actualization, and joy.

Major themes

- How Being and existential freedom is the foundation for all politics
- Why self-disclosure is crucial to politics.
- Why speech and action are crucial to self-disclosure.
- How and why does Arendt disagree with determinism.
- The role of the public sphere in politics
- Why stories are important in politics, and why they're also dangerous
- Why politics must be more than just the creation of structures and laws
- How the Greeks got it right at the first try – and why and how Plato messed it up

Chapter 24 – The Disclosure of the Agent in Speech and Action

Arendt begins by arguing that human plurality, the foundational premise of the entire book, is based on the reality that all humans are simultaneously equal (in the political sphere) *and* distinct. If we're not distinct then we would become a massified blob – remember Arendt's critique of 'The Social' that treated everyone as the same? If we're not equal then there's no such thing as democracy or humanity.

This distinction is a very strange thing. If all things share some existential Being (dasein) then how come we can make distinctions? This has troubled philosophers for millennia, and Arendt suggest her own answer to it: Speech and Action. These two abilities, present in every human person, is what makes us into an *who* instead of a *what*. Every human possesses these qualities on the ability of taking initiatives. Anyone unable to take any form of initiative can hardly be called human. Here Arendt relies upon Augustine: "that there be a beginning, man was created before whom there was nobody" (page 177). This is the essence of Action, as distinct from Labor or Work:

With word and deed we insert ourselves into the human world, and this insertion is like a second birth, in which we confirm and take upon ourselves the naked fact of our original physical appearance. This insertion is not forced upon us by necessity, like labor, and it is not prompted by utility, like work. (P.176f)

It's the very definition Arendt uses for Action: "To act, in its most general sense, means to take an initiative, to begin [...] to set something into motion" (page 177). We're thrown into this world without our consent, we follow our life-process to its inevitable end. Anything in-between requires our initiative – our Action.

She already expects the objection from determinists, that the events between our birth and death has been pre-decided by structures, which she disagrees with:

The new always happens against the overwhelming odds of statistical laws and their probability, which for all practical, everyday purposes amounts to certainty; the new therefore always appears in the guise of a miracle. The fact that man is capable of action means that the unexpected can be expected from him, that he is able to perform what is infinitely improbable. And this again is possible only because each man is unique, so that with each birth something uniquely new comes into the world. With respect to this somebody who is unique it can be truly said that nobody was there before. (P.178).

The most stunning occasion of something new appearing is whenever a new human existence comes into being. If initiative is infinitely improbable, and initiative is expected from each human being, then every birth is the promise of a completely new world. This is something Arendt will discuss at length later. 'Nativity' is the ever-present potential for salvation of Humanity, but she lays the groundwork for it here in the very first pages of the section.

She now turns to the connection between Being, initiative, and action & speech. Using her phenomenological premise Arendt argues that action is a form of appearance, of showing yourself to others²³. However, mere action can never answer the question of *who* one is, only a *what* something is²⁴:

Without the accompaniment of speech, at any rate, action would not only lose its revelatory character, but, and by the same token, it would lose its subject, as it were; not acting men but performing robots would achieve what, humanly speaking, would remain incomprehensible. [...] The action he begins is humanly disclosed by the word (P.178f)

Here we can also see a precursor to Arendt critique of the modern rationalistic bureaucratic state: it's a machine that takes action without much speech, for it is unable to speak for itself:

Thus, it is also true that man's capacity to act, and especially to act in concert, is extremely useful for purposes of self-defense or of pursuit of interests; but if nothing more were at stake here than to use action as a means to an end, it is obvious that the same end could be much more easily attained in mute violence, so that action seems a not very efficient substitute for violence, just as speech, from the viewpoint of sheer utility, seems an awkward substitute for sign language. (Ibid.)²⁵

²³ In *Life of The Mind* Arendt goes into depth of this argument. She claims that there is a world (noumena) that has Being, but we can only grasp the things that appear to us. For example the atom, which always had a Being, but only became reality for us once we made it appear with the help of technology. Likewise humans can have a being while being outside our reality until they become reality.

²⁴ This is the fundamental flaw in the exchange market. If we try to appear in the political sphere through what we've created (*action*) then we will never become anything more than makers of a product. To understand what motivates someone to make that product one must speak to one another.

²⁵ This will become easier to understand once Arendt discuss her concept of power contra violence.

Thus we have Arendt's core aspects of politics: human plurality, which follow humanity's double quality of both Being's equality and distinction, and miraculous ability to take initiative. What makes this initiative a *human* quality is its ability, through the praxis of action and speech, to reveal the uniqueness of the individual to his/her peers.

However, this joyful existence has never been (except for ancient Greece) aligned with political structures, for the revelation of one's uniqueness depends upon the community surrounding one²⁶. This makes the shape and structure of the public realm *the* crucial political question²⁷:

This revelatory quality of speech and action comes to the fore where people are with others and neither for nor against them— that is, in sheer human togetherness. Although nobody knows whom he reveals when he discloses himself in deed or word, he must be willing to risk the disclosure, and this neither the doer of good works, who must be without self and preserve complete anonymity [...] Because of its inherent tendency to disclose the agent together with the act, action needs for its full appearance the shining brightness we once called glory, and which is possible only in the public realm [...] whenever human togetherness is lost, that is, when people are only for or against other people, as for instance in modern warfare, where men go into action and use means of violence in order to achieve certain objectives for their own side and against the enemy. In these instances, which of course have always existed, speech becomes indeed "mere talk," simply one more means toward the end, whether it serves to deceive the enemy or to dazzle everybody with propaganda; here words reveal nothing, disclosure comes only from the deed itself, and this achievement, like all other achievements, cannot disclose the "who," the unique and distinct identity of the agent. (P.180)

Chapter 25 – The web of Relationships and the Enacted Stories

Arendt returns to the claim in the previous chapter, her argument that human initiative is a definition of *who* is a human. She argues that by focusing on *who* a human is, through their subjective uniqueness, it becomes possible to create a unified definition of humanity based on our "*who-ness*" over the *what-ness* that occupied the ancient philosophers ("behold a man!").

This then makes the public sphere, where our "*who-ness*" can be fully expressed, crucial for our individuality, which is why Arendt spent such time discussing how labor satisfies the necessities required to appear in the public sphere, and how work creates the very physicality demanded for us to have a place to meet.

In a line that summarizes one of the main concerns Arendt has:

What is at stake is the revelatory character without which action and speech would lose all human relevance. (P.182)

²⁶ This is why Arendt begins the book by discussing the dynamic between the Public and Private realm in ancient Greece. Being in private was to be invisible, and revelation was only possible in the public realm.

²⁷ Indeed, the great European historian Tony Judt made this argument on the importance of the public realm into *the* central argument of the entire book, over all other arguments related we've already discussed, and the ones we're also about to discuss. It must also be noted how the public sphere is absolutely central to her analysis of totalitarianism – which is a political system that simultaneously destroyed the private sphere (imagine 1984's Winston dissidence in scribbling in his book) while also reducing the public sphere's plurality into oneness in the loyal Nazi or dedicated Bolshevik communist.

The central importance of the public sphere is that it is a meeting place, a sphere where different human persons can disclose themselves to one another, where we can discuss our own subjective approaches to the issues of our times. It's through these intersubjective meetings where "everybody sees and hears from a different position" that "things can be seen by many in a variety of aspects without changing their identity, so that those who are gathered around them know they see sameness in utter diversity" (page 57). In this way the public sphere is the foundation for our very reality.

On the opposite side, in its most abstracted form, the public sphere is the very web of relationships we're all enmeshed within. Arendt wants to define the public sphere with this abstraction to move the western political tradition from its materiality. As argued above, Arendt wants to create a political ontology based on our (inter-)subjectivity to move away from the modern Hobbesian materialistic management of politics. This is important because the materialistic bureaucratic state can never tell a story about itself, and through these stories achieve immortality²⁸. She notes how all the Great People in history (Alexander, Cyrus, Caesar, Boudica etc.) have been distinct actors who revealed themselves in both deed and speech, while the people who remained within the state-management have rarely been recorded, even less remembered.

However, just doing great deed and speaking great words is not enough:

Although everybody started his life by inserting himself into the human world through action and speech, nobody is the author or producer of his own life story. In other words, the stories, the results of action and speech, reveal an agent, but this agent is not an author or producer. Somebody began it and is its subject in the twofold sense of the word, namely, its actor and sufferer, but nobody is its author (P.184)

The issue is that we're all in the great story of humanity, which can be told from our evolution into Homo Sapiens to today, which, it's commonly believed, must possess some deeper and more fundamental logic or structure, be it an invisible hand, political cycle, racial biology, material dialectics. This is a *very* important argument in Arendt's general thinking. It's not only the origin of the 'laws of history' that would become the ideological foundations for the totalitarian movements²⁹ but also the basis for the determinist skepticism of free will³⁰. Instead of focusing on the "maker" or the abstract force of history in humanity, Arendt wants us to focus on the people in the story itself:

The real story in which we are engaged as long as we live has no visible or invisible maker because it is not made. The only "somebody" it reveals is its hero, and it is the only medium in which the originally intangible manifestation of a uniquely distinct "who" can become tangible ex post facto through action and speech. Who somebody is or was we can know only by knowing the story of which he is himself the hero—

²⁸ Once again, we see how Arendt refers back to the discussion in the very first chapters in the book, where she argues that immortality was the end/meaning of politics in ancient Greece.

²⁹ If all human history is determined by race or material dialectic, then we must make society follow that law, which only becomes possible by intervening into the public sphere and force it to adhere to the law of history.

³⁰ Arendt argues in *The Life of the Mind* that we're phenomenologically bound to the present, and that the past is only available by looking at the objects we understand as having historical qualities and then interpolate those into a logic that made the present into what it is – determinism is a confusion of causality.

his biography, in other words; everything else we know of him, including the work he may have produced and left behind, tells us only what he is or was. Thus, although we know much less of Socrates, who did not write a single line and left no work behind, than of Plato or Aristotle, we know much better and more intimately who he was, because we know his story, than we know who Aristotle was, about whose opinions we are so much better informed. (P.186)

This is important because if we focus on the story as an object then we're treating the people in it as *what* instead of *who*: we know *what* Aristotle wrote but we know *who* Socrates was. This also becomes the difference between the story itself and the object produced by Homo Faber, for while Homo Faber may create an object ("*what*") it will not say much about the person who produced it ("*who*"), which is another reason the exchange market cannot replace the intersubjectivity of the public sphere, and why we know much of Mayan society from their ruins and remains (*what*), but little of them as individual historical actors and persons (*who*).

Thus theatre becomes the greatest political artform, since it bridges the *what* (actors) of the story also becomes *who* (people) in their craft.

Chapter 26 – The Frailty of Human Affairs

So, while the *work* of art and action may have much in common it is a catastrophic mistake to mistake them for one another. Action is impossible without the surrounding people to acknowledge a deed with no durability at all ("If a tree falls in a forest..."); work is only possible when a single man acts alone upon the material surrounding him.

Arendt is very clear about the consequences of applying Homo Faber on the political sphere:

The popular belief in a "strong man" who, isolated against others, owes his strength to his being alone is either sheer superstition, based on the delusion that we can "make" something in the realm of human affairs—"make" institutions or laws, for instance, as we make tables and chairs, or make men "better" or "worse"—or it is conscious despair of all action, political and non-political, coupled with the Utopian hope that it may be possible to treat men as one treats other "material." (P.188)

Just like the artistic genius stands above the rest in a form of splendid isolation, so we also want to understand the great political geniuses who created laws or vast empires or kingdoms as splendid geniuses. This categorical mistake makes the messiness of politics look like the romantic Great Man hindered by the envious inferiors that plot their downfall.

This has created the historical illusions (see above about the flawed way we read human history) that there are great individual leaders (rulers) who direct and manage the subjects in the same way that an artist or craftsman would direct and rule his disciples in a building project, on which he places his own name.

Reading history in this way results in a tyrannical mindset. Just like the Greek tyrant was a person who ruled the public sphere as his own personal private sphere, so does the confusion of Homo Faber with action result in the mindset that politics is about a great leader/ruler constructing a form of machine that will, like the best artworks, have the durability to last forever. This was the central flaw of Rome, who saw their foundation as the great event to only be expanded upon, but never changed.

The consequences of this form of politics can be seen everywhere, where the political norms set by the leaders of the previous generations are in full decline over the western world, and that the political “artwork” of the last century is seemingly losing its durability. The reason for this is because:

[A]ction, though it may proceed from nowhere, so to speak, acts into a medium where every reaction becomes a chain reaction and where every process is the cause of new processes. Since action acts upon beings who are capable of their own actions, reaction, apart from being a response, is always a new action that strikes out on its own and affects others. Thus action and reaction among men never move in a closed circle and can never be reliably confined to two partners. This boundlessness is characteristic not of political action alone, in the narrower sense of the word, as though the boundlessness of human interrelatedness were only the result of the boundless multitude of people involved, which could be escaped by resigning oneself to action within a limited, graspable framework of circumstances; the smallest act in the most limited circumstances bears the seed of the same boundlessness, because one deed, and sometimes one word, suffices to change every constellation. (P.190)

It is therefore impossible to imagine a political machine that will be able to contain and manage all the inexplicable consequences of our actions. There is no such thing as a law that can foresee and give legal constraints on all possible situations that may arise, giving the theoretical justification of a Sovereign who would resolve the issue like a foreman at a building site³¹.

But it's not just the unexpected consequences of our actions that challenge the Homo Faber-model of politics. As all humans are defined by our ability to take initiatives and reimagine the world, the political building must also be flexible enough to provide alternative political ideals that change from each generation. In a sentence that's very much relevant for contemporary Europe, in panic over migration and how to approach it:

Limitations and boundaries exist within the realm of human affairs, but they never offer a framework that can reliably withstand the onslaught with which each new generation must insert itself. The frailty of human institutions and laws and, generally, of all matters pertaining to men's living together, arises from the human condition of natality and is quite independent of the frailty of human nature. The fences inclosing private property and insuring the limitations of each household, the territorial boundaries which protect and make possible the physical identity of a people, and the laws which protect and make possible its political existence, are of such great importance to the stability of human affairs precisely because no such limiting and protecting principles rise out of the activities going on in the realm of human affairs itself. (P.190f)

The fundamental issue of reducing politics and action into Homo Faber is that there will never be any entity³² that can foresee the consequences of our actions, nor be able to tell *human* stories that reveal our *who-ness* that can give us the immortality that will give meaning to our short time here on earth – except us humans.

Chapter 27 – The Greek Solution

So how do we manage the unpredictability of politics? Arendt believes the Greeks can teach us.

³¹ An argument raised by Carl Schmitt, who Arendt was aware of and trying to provide a solution for

³² Except a sufficiently advanced AI that we decide to rule us all? That's a “great” solution, right?

If the issue is that we're trying to form a stable structure on the unpredictability of both action and individual humans, then we must base our politics on the individuals themselves – this is the Greek solution. As Arendt mentioned in the first chapters of the book, the Greeks sought the meaning of politics in the achievement of great deeds and therethrough immortality:

No doubt this concept of action is highly individualistic, as we would say today. It stresses the urge toward self-disclosure at the expense of all other factors and therefore remains relatively untouched by the predicament of unpredictability. As such it became the prototype of action for Greek antiquity and influenced, in the form of the so-called agonai spirit, the passionate drive to show one's self in measuring up against others that underlies the concept of politics prevalent in the city-states. An outstanding symptom of this prevailing influence is that the Greeks, in distinction from all later developments, did not count legislating among the political activities. In their opinion, the lawmaker was like the builder of the city wall, someone who had to do and finish his work before political activity could begin. He therefore was treated like any other craftsman or architect and could be called from abroad and commissioned without having to be a citizen, whereas the right to *politeuesthai*, to engage in the numerous activities which eventually went on in the polls, was entirely restricted to citizens. To them, the laws, like the wall around the city, were not results of action but products of making. (P.194)

By introducing the Greek approach to politics Arendt wants to turn the relationship between the political person and the political structure. If the structure cannot withstand the unpredictability of human action, then we ought to make human action the basis of politics instead. **This is Arendt's great innovation in political theory³³.**

This leads into her famous argument that the western tradition of politics had just begun when Plato destroyed it. When Socrates showed how no philosophical structure hold up to examination he destroyed all justification and basis for all political structures, and placed the thinking man in the center of it, forced to apply his own subjectivity and thinking to reality and Being. Horrified how this led to Socrates execution, Plato misunderstood his old teacher by trying to find a compromise that would both give philosophers the highest position in society *while also* creating an absolute from which politics could be justified.

Plato's historical mistake was to introduce the creation of political structures into philosophy (thinking), which can only destroy these structures – resulting with Plato admitting to the necessity of noble lies, which is nothing else than the limitation of thinking, the separation of human beings from reality, and the destruction of the possibility for action. His betrayal of his teacher's insight was handed down to Aristotle who made the same mistake:

How this remedy can destroy the very substance of human relationships is perhaps best illustrated in one of the rare instances where Aristotle draws an example of acting from the sphere of private life [...] he thinks of acting in terms of making, and of its result, the relationship between men, in terms of an accomplished "work" (his emphatic attempts to distinguish between action and fabrication, *praxis* and *poiesis*,

³³ to which she ultimately connects the occurrence of banal evil (identification with sociocultural structures), the lost promise of revolutions (the attempt to build structures instead of public sphere for action), the lost art of thinking for the cognition on the structure's basis, the occurrence of totalitarianism (the attempt to make a structure that can triumph over action) and so much more.

notwithstanding). In this instance, it [...] actually spoils the action itself and its true result, the relationship it should have established. (P.196).

Arendt's claim is that the philosophers, faced with the horrifying possibility that nothing could be justified, tried to create new reasons for politics – doing so assuming the role of Homo Faber and the creation of a political structure. But in doing this they “threw out the baby with the bathwater” and destroyed the intuitive political genius of the City-State, which was the only political unit (according to Arendt) that could create meaning in immortality:

The polls was supposed to multiply the occasions to win "immortal fame," that is, to multiply the chances for everybody to distinguish himself, to show in deed and word who he was in his unique distinctness. One, if not the chief, reason for the incredible development of gift and genius in Athens, as well as for the hardly less surprising swift decline of the city-state, was precisely that from beginning to end its foremost aim was to make the extraordinary an ordinary occurrence of everyday life. The second function of the polls, again closely connected with the hazards of action as experienced before its coming into being, was to offer a remedy for the futility of action and speech; for the chances that a deed deserving fame would not be forgotten, that it actually would become "immortal," were not very good. Homer was not only a shining example of the poet's political function, and therefore the "educator of all Hellas"; the very fact that so great an enterprise as the Trojan War could have been forgotten without a poet to immortalize it several hundred years later offered only too good an example of what could happen to human greatness if it had nothing but poets to rely on for its permanence. We are not concerned here with the historical causes for the rise of the Greek city-state; what the Greeks themselves thought of it and its *raison d'etre*, they have made unmistakably clear. The polls—if we trust the famous words of Pericles in the Funeral Oration—gives a guaranty that those who forced every sea and land to become the scene of their daring will not remain without witness and will need neither Homer nor anyone else who knows how to turn words to praise them; without assistance from others, those who acted will be able to establish together the everlasting remembrance of their good and bad deeds, to inspire admiration in the present and in future ages. (P.197)

Politics, this form of acting together, is only possible in the public sphere, where we as unique people with our own unique stories appear to one another and tell the stories of who we are and do deeds together. The polis, the public sphere, is not a material entity like we've come to believe, but it's a form of intersubjective praxis that we all have the right to participate in, to appear and be recognized for who we are – and be remembered.

The issue we have today is best summarized by Arendt at the end of the chapter:

This space does not always exist, and although all men are capable of deed and word, most of them—like the slave, the foreigner, and the barbarian in antiquity, like the laborer or craftsman prior to the modern age, the jobholder or businessman in our world—do not live in it. No man, moreover, can live in it all the time. To be deprived of it means to be deprived of reality, which, humanly and politically speaking, is the same as appearance. To men the reality of the world is guaranteed by the presence of others, by its appearing to all; "for what appears to all, this we call Being," and whatever lacks this appearance comes and passes away like a dream, intimately and exclusively our own but without reality.

Without the public sphere we're not humans – we're bare life to be treated like animals, and then forgotten.

Discussion questions:

1. Are we, in the book club, engaged in Action as we are having our seminars?
2. Is the Homo Faber approach to politics still *politics*, or does Arendt deny it that privilege?
3. Can Arendt's political philosophy survive the discovery of the principles of our consciousness and being?
4. Is human plurality possible under the limits of the nation-state?
5. How can we relate this political philosophy to Arendt distinction between thinking and cognition?
6. Is Arendt's critique against Plato reasonable?
7. Are there others than the Greeks who solved the issue of unpredictability and meaning?
8. Is totalitarianism always a threat when we make politics about leaders and structures, instead of individuals and intersubjectivity?
9. If politics must be based on our subjectivity, then how do we meet the arguments of thinkers like Foucault or Wittgenstein who argue that our subjectivity is formed by the political/linguistic structures of modernity? Is Arendt's veneration of speech philosophically naïve?

Seminar 10.5: chapters 26-28

This write-up was made for the 26th of September seminar in which we decided to have a closer discussion of the chapters for the previous seminar on the 19th of September. Therefore, the write-ups for chapters 26-27 are the same, while a new write-up for chapter 28 was added.

Chapter 26 – The Frailty of Human Affairs

While the *work* of art and action may have much in common it is a catastrophic mistake to mistake them for one another. Action is impossible without the surrounding people to acknowledge a deed with no durability at all (“If a tree falls in a forest...”); work is only possible when a single man acts alone upon the material surrounding him.

Arendt is clear about the consequences of applying Homo Faber on the political sphere:

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Reading history in this way results in a tyrannical mindset. Just like the Greek tyrant was a person who ruled the public sphere as his own personal private sphere, so does the confusion of Homo Faber with action result in the mindset that politics is about a great leader/ruler constructing a form of machine that will, like the best artworks, have the durability to last forever. This was the central flaw of Rome, who saw their foundation as the great event to only be expanded upon, but never changed.

The consequences of this form of politics can be seen everywhere, where the political norms set by the leaders of the previous generations are in full decline over the western world, and that the political “artwork” of the last century is seemingly losing its durability. The reason for this is because:

[A]ction, though it may proceed from nowhere, so to speak, acts into a medium where every reaction becomes a chain reaction and where every process is the cause of new processes. Since action acts upon beings who are capable of their own actions, reaction, apart from being a response, is always a new action that strikes out on its own and affects others. Thus action and reaction among men never move in a closed circle and can never be reliably confined to two partners. This boundlessness is characteristic not of political action alone, in the narrower sense of the word, as though the boundlessness of human interrelatedness were only the result of the

boundless multitude of people involved, which could be escaped by resigning oneself to action within a limited, graspable framework of circumstances; the smallest act in the most limited circumstances bears the seed of the same boundlessness, because one deed, and sometimes one word, suffices to change every constellation. (P.190)

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But it is not just the unexpected consequences of our actions that challenge the Homo Faber-model of politics. As all humans are defined by our ability to take initiatives and reimagine the world, the political building must also be flexible enough to provide alternative political ideals that change from each generation. In a sentence that is very much relevant for contemporary Europe, in panic over migration and how to approach it:

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Politics, this form of acting together, is only possible in the public sphere, where we as unique people with our own unique stories appear to one another and tell the stories of who we are and do deeds together. The polis, the public sphere, is not a material entity like we have come to believe, but it's a form of intersubjective praxis that we all have the right to participate in, to appear and be recognized for who we are – and be remembered.

The issue we have today is best summarized by Arendt at the end of the chapter:

This space does not always exist, and although all men are capable of deed and word, most of them—like the slave, the foreigner, and the barbarian in antiquity, like the laborer or craftsman prior to the modern age, the jobholder or businessman in our world—do not live in it. No man, moreover, can live in it all the time. To be deprived of it means to be deprived of reality, which, humanly and politically speaking, is the same as appearance. To men the reality of the world is guaranteed by the presence of others, by its appearing to all; "for what appears to all, this we call Being," and whatever lacks this appearance comes and passes away like a dream, intimately and exclusively our own but without reality.

Without the public sphere we are not humans – we're bare life to be treated like animals, and then forgotten.

Chapter 28 – Power and the Space of Appearance

Thus, the Space of Appearance is constituted when people meet one another and disclose who they are. This requires the Public Sphere that Arendt has been discussing and characterized through the book so far, tracing through its discovery in Ancient Greece, its abandonment by the rise of *Vita Contemplativa*, and substitution by modern capitalism and social bureaucracy. It is now that Arendt tries to rehabilitate it and provide reasons why we must rediscover it in our modern political society. The final section of the book is about the danger we face when modern technology and science is disconnected from the *power* people possess when organizing in the

public sphere, but here she will portray politics in a unique understanding of what constitutes 'power,' it is potential and hopefulness, danger, and what destroys it.

For Arendt, the Public Sphere is about potentiality, nothing is ever certain in the human realm as we're all different and impossible to account for, both greatness and great evil is possible when humans meet. This potentiality is due to us having the option to either unite with one another or seek other ways of engagement, and Arendt provides a hierarchical schema for the different approaches we can use towards one another.

Power	Power is the potential brought forth by humanity when acting together in the pursuit of some goal. It's always voluntary, joyful, and unlimited in its possibilities from the great (Athens) to the murderous (Genghis Khan). <i>Is created in the Public Sphere, and in turn supports and sustains it.</i>
Strength	Strength is the qualities possessed by one isolated individual to affect their surroundings and apply themselves to it.
Violence	Violence is the mute coercion that imitates power. Tyrannies are the exemplary political structure of violence, which coerces an imitation of <i>power</i> from society fully lacking its voluntary and joyful characteristics. However, it is <i>always</i> powerless since it isolates people from one another in fear of the violent coercion from the tyrant.

In one way one may equate *power* with civic society, the voluntary organizations characterized by the meeting of people who acts to resolve specific issues or achieve certain goals that the strength of one individual would never achieve on their own. This organizing also means that there is no such thing as 'passive' power which always requires a form of active engagement – indeed, Gandhi's passive resistance was everything but passive, it was only limited in methods.

In contrast to Gandhi's powerful movement there are the societies that has used violence to isolate people from one another to rule them, and while it may seem that these tyrannies are powerful and able to achieve anything, they are Potemkin polities. See for example the potential revolution in Iran, where the violence of the theocratic polity tried to destroy the power of the society by only allowing certain people to appear in the Public Sphere and become political. Invisible to all was the anger that united the Iranian women in opposition to this violence and have now become so powerful that the regime is trying to oppose their power by using violence to isolate the protesters from one another.

This also show how Arendt seems to be correct in her analysis of Montesquieu that *only* power can limit *power* and not violence since some of the police forces and military in Iran has *joined* the protesters, against the potential violence they face for disobedience to a military hierarchy they don't believe or identify with – lacking *power* over them.

While not expanded upon in The Human Condition, Arendt is concerned about what form a revolution takes once it's in power. In On Revolution she is argues that the power that's created will not be used to form a public sphere in a social revolution, and create the structure that separates people from one another in voluntary agreement, but will only create the nationalistic (Yugoslavia/Germany) or communist (Russia/China) mobs, or fail to create any political community at all in a civil war (Arab Spring).

In contrast to these societies that has *too* much power there is the sterile societies that has no power at all, which I think can be characterized by Russia, who in their recent partial mobilization has found themselves unable to gain any mass-support since only the few seems to believe in

the politics that surrounds them. This seems to have forced Putin to rely on even more violence (draconic penal laws) to try to motivate people into fighting the war on Ukraine. As Timothy Snyder recognized, the difference between Ukrainian power is their ability to fight for something they all believe in, while the Russians only fight for political nihilism. Power is neigh unstoppable once it appears in human politics. The futility of the different Afghan and Vietnam wars showed how any escalation of violence against a sufficiently determined and united political unit will never be able to triumph, unless one uses totalitarian ideology and terror, or kill them all.

This then returns us to Arendt's claim in *The Human Condition*, that the public sphere is disappearing in the political philosophy and the modern state. If we no longer meet one another to create power what then is moving our societies forward? She gave the answer in the previous chapters: the autonomous processes of a rhythmic machinelike society of continual consumption and growth, not our actual engagement with politics and power – which brings us to the claim made in the first chapters, that modern nihilism is the decline of the public sphere and politics:

Without being talked about by men and without housing them, the world would not be a human artifice but a heap of unrelated things to which each isolated individual was at liberty to add one more object; without the human artifice to house them, human affairs would be as floating, as futile and vain, as the wanderings of nomad tribes. The melancholy wisdom of Ecclesiastes—"Vanity of vanities; all is vanity . . . There is no new thing under the sun, . . . there is no remembrance of former things; neither shall there be any remembrance of things that are to come with those that shall come after"—does not necessarily arise from specifically religious experience; but it is certainly unavoidable wherever and whenever trust in the world as a place fit for human appearance, for action and speech, is gone. (p.204)

The rise of the Hobbesian bureaucratic and rationalistic state has replaced all our power and politics into the exercise of bureaucracy. The idea that power corrupts, and the experiences of mob rule during the French revolution, has made the professional politician and objective bureaucrat the replacement of actual human power who is now in deep suspicion. Instead of *power* we have *social forces* that are about as suitable a replacement for power as violence is. They are both isolating and turn each person away from one another and makes us all powerless and unable to change society to become more human, as Kafka's "K" experience in his trial. What changes society in modernity is autonomous processes, like the market *forces* with its sterile and predictable version of humanity in Homo Economicus.

Discussion questions:

1. Are we, in the book club, engaged in Action as we are having our seminars?
2. Is the Homo Faber approach to politics still *politics*, or does Arendt deny it that privilege?
3. Can Arendt's political philosophy survive the discovery of the principles of our consciousness and being?
4. Is human plurality possible under the limits of the nation-state?
5. How can we relate this political philosophy to Arendt distinction between thinking and cognition?
6. Is Arendt's critique against Plato reasonable?
7. Are there others than the Greeks who solved the issue of unpredictability and meaning?
8. Is totalitarianism always a threat when we make politics about leaders and structures, instead of individuals and intersubjectivity?

9. If politics must be based on our subjectivity, then how do we meet the arguments of thinkers like Foucault or Wittgenstein who argue that our subjectivity is formed by the political/linguistic structures of modernity? Is Arendt's veneration of speech philosophically naïve?
10. Can the rebellions in Iran be understood from Arendt's description of power and violence?
11. Is Russia, both now and in its previous Soviet iteration, characterized by a seemingly complete lack of *power*?

Seminar 11: chapters 29-30

Despite being two chapters, at a total of 13 pages, the content of this week's reading are some of the most central discussions in Arendt's oeuvre. We are introduced to her analysis of Common Sense as a sixth sense that structures our senses – which will become crucially important in later chapters – and her analysis of the tragedy of the labor movement, the potential it had, and its end in modernity's political disaster.

Major themes

- The relationship between reality, common sense, the public sphere, and alienation
- The anti-politics of the massified labor-society
- Arendt's critique of Heidegger's *being-towards-death*
- The potential of the labor movement, but it is reduction to massification.

Chapter 29 – Homo Faber and the Space of Appearance

Arendt begins the chapter by reiterating the inherent conflict between Labor, Work and Action. They are all equally necessary for the functioning of society, and Action must present its relevance against the self-evident usefulness of Work's durability and Labor's social Lifehood. Seen from their perspectives, Action is mere pointless and idle talk, and the public realm, held as inherently important for action, should instead be instrumental in the production use-objects and labor "biopolitics" (as Foucault would refer to it).

However, even if society is oriented around exchange or labor, action can never be fully abolished (and visa-versa in an Action society, as seen with Greece's slavery). The matter of fact is that all aspects of Vita Activa require the existence of reality to even make sense, and for Being to be actualized. Neither of these are possible without the togetherness that gives the actualization of subjectivities that gives the world the "sameness in utter plurality" that connects our worlds to one another.

For *reality* must be common to all for the simple reason that an atomized person's reality cannot make sense on its own but require some socialization to be validated. I believe this is a phenomenological critique against Descartes *Cogito* as the idea that one's mind applies itself to an objective world, while the phenomenological critique claim that 'the world' shapes the subject in return, with Arendt arguing that we need intersubjectivity to structure the world around us and thereby stabilize our subjectivity.

The only character of the world by which to gauge its reality is its being common to us all, and common sense occupies such a high rank in the hierarchy of political qualities because it is the one sense that fits into reality as a whole our five strictly individual senses and the strictly particular data they perceive. (P.208)

This 'stabilization' can be called Common Sense, and is a central term in Arendt's thinking on politics. Her argument is that common sense is connected to public intersubjectivity that establishes the shared experience of reality, which is only possible in the public sphere³⁷:

³⁷ Later she will argue that the disappearance of this public sphere is the cause of the complete disappearance of common sense in the 20th century, and was what enabled all the horrors of that century

A noticeable decrease in common sense in any given community and a noticeable increase in superstition and gullibility are therefore almost infallible signs of alienation from the world. (p.209)

This is the first mention of a central concept in the final section of the book (The Vita Active and the Modern Age), where Arendt refers to *World Alienation* as the central character of a modern world that has abolished the public sphere. She will be explicit that Marx's concept of Self-Alienation is as true as it was in the 19th century, but that it now has been intensified by our alienation from the world around us, so that we're thrown back on our isolated selves, which we're still alienated from, resulting in a form of universal alienation that has us viewing ourselves and the world from a third person perspective without any common sense – the "Archimedean Point".

Chapter 30 – The Labor Movement

The central issue of the labor-society is that its politics is a mere façade. While labor will always require some togetherness to be efficient, and to establish reality and common sense as argued in chapter 29, it does not create the plurality crucial for action. As she argued in its section, labor corresponds to the biological necessities of human existence, and we all share the same biological needs. Any society founded on it will never be able to create distinctions between the laborers – it is inherently massifying, and thereby anti-political. If there is no difference between people there is no diversity or different lifeworlds to share and talk about.

This is why Arendt claims that the public realm is *instrumentally good* and not inherently good. A public realm will appear whenever people meet, and the political vitality of the public realm depends on how we use it, and Arendt's argument is that we must use it to disclose ourselves and our lives. If we use it for the establishment and prolongation of biological life then we're in a laboring society and treat it as a naturally existing phenomenon following and enabling our biological existence, and not to achieve something 'great' that can give meaning and authenticity to our individual lives – as Arendt recommends.

Here is where Arendt gives her critique against Heidegger. He claimed that we can achieve individual authenticity and meaning in the *being-towards-death*. Arendt fundamentally disagrees with this as *death* is a natural phenomenon shared by everyone, and if we construct society around *being-towards-death* then we're still basing society on the biological massification that we see in labor-society. Her claim is that Heidegger's solution is massifying and thereby anti-political – and can only create the worldlessness and loneliness.

From the viewpoint of the world and the public realm, life and death and everything attesting to sameness are non-worldly, antipolitical, truly transcendent experiences. (p.215)

This massification, Arendt speculates, can also explain why there were never any successful revolts against slavery (with the exception of Haiti, which later descended into bloody civil war) or totalitarianism. When our politics is reduced into the care for our biological nature then we have no plurality, or ability to transcend the masses to become leaders, except for the truly unique 'geniuses' who can transcend the massification.

Despite this strong indictment Arendt makes an abrupt turn to argue that this outcome wasn't inevitable, and that the labor movement had the potential to create the civic republicanism she seeks. Her argument is that the 19th century European laboring movements where

extraordinarily successful organizations that were close to bringing down the capitalist order at several points in the century, with 1848 as the culmination.

Following those events the movements moved from being challengers to the social order into being internalized as political parties. This was *the* big mistake according to Arendt. When they allowed themselves to become parliamentary parties they had to change their organization from the revolutionary councils working in each factory, into becoming an hierarchically ordered and massified party. The emancipation of laborers was the *class* emancipation and not individual emancipation, making the central distinction in society *which class you belonged to* and not *who you are as a person*. The central question in politics became "*which party do you belong to*" and not "*what do you believe in politics*".

The effect of this reduction of *labor movements* into *labor parties* was the creation of the mass society. The public sphere became occupied by classes and groups instead of individuals, which connects the argument to Arendt's analysis in *Origins of Totalitarianism* where the massified society understood Jews as a homogenous social group all in themselves, antagonized by the antisemitic parties who could point to individual Jews to make claims about the entire group.

The massification the party-political societies also meant that common sense became unique for each party, making it impossible for members of 'regular society' to communicate with members of the totalitarian movements, whose reality and common sense were incommensurable with a common sense, as argued in chapter 29, unique for that political party. That's how it became *common sense* that Jews or Kulaks had to be exterminated. It began with the laboring movement transforming politics into mass-politics.

Discussion questions:

1. Is there a connection between reality, common sense, and the public realm?
2. Should we understand Common Sense to be a singularly defined concept shared by many, or a plural and individually unique entity with some shared common traits?
3. Is the contemporary death of common sense (flat earthers, conspiracy theories, Trumpism, etcetera) an "infallible" sign that we have widespread alienation in today's world? Or is it rather the common sense of massified groups in internet echo-chambers?
4. Is Arendt's critique of Heidegger's *being-towards-death* reasonable? Is Heidegger politically naïve?
5. Is Arendt correct in her claim that the internalization of the labor movements into political parties was the revolutionary event that birthed modern mass society?

Seminar 12: chapters 31-32

Not much to say about this week's readings. Chapter 31, where Arendt makes the distinctions between politics based on work and politics based on action, was a positive surprise for me. I knew about her critique of Plato's political philosophy, but I was not aware that Arendt discussed it in *The Human Condition*!

Major themes

- The reason political philosophy is dangerous and detrimental to politics

- The unpredictability of Action, and its consequences
- Why the “taming” of action’s unpredictability to undesired by Arendt
- Plato and political philosophy
- Plato and our tradition of legitimacy
- Plato and the failure of revolutions
- Freedom in politics, or freedom in our mind
- Determinism and humane politics
- The dangerous unshackling of our minds

Chapter 31 – The Traditional Substitution of Making for Acting

There are three central issues in Action:

1. Its unpredictability
2. Its irreversibility
3. The anonymity of their agents.

These are the inevitable consequences of human plurality, in our individual uniqueness and need to act in a shared public sphere. There has, however, been many attempts to solve these issues through political theory, but Arendt thinks it is a genuine mistake to do so.

According to her all attempts to make action predictable comes with the implication that politics can be made into a form of science/art where one knowledgeable and executive person can foresee and plan all consequences of political decisions. It’s related to her critique of Great Person history that implies that politics was the designed craftsmanship of one great founder.

Generally speaking, they always amount to seeking shelter from action's calamities in an activity where one man, isolated from all others, remains master of his doings from beginning to end. This attempt to replace acting with making is manifest in the whole body of argument against "democracy," which, the more consistently and better reasoned it is, will turn into an argument against the essentials of politics. (p.220)

The essentials of politics refer to the plurality and the public sphere. When we have one ‘master’ (as in monarchy or tyranny) we are in essence removing the existence of plurality since, as she explained in an earlier chapter, the public realm becomes the private realm of the ‘master’ within which everyone is the same.

The first person to try to find a solution to the issue of action’s unpredictability was Plato:

Plato's solution of the philosopher-king, whose "wisdom" solves the perplexities of action as though they were solvable problems of cognition, is only one—and by no means the least tyrannical—variety of one-man rule. (p.221)

It was Plato that tried to make politics into *cognition* instead of thinking, where the givenness of our being, and its inexplicability, is replaced by unquestionable premises (*ideas*) that we must follow in our politics. When we have achieved this shared premise in politics, a shared *truth* as discovered by the Philosopher Kings, politics takes the form of machine:

Escape from the frailty of human affairs into the solidity of quiet and order has in fact so much to recommend it that the greater part of political philosophy since Plato could easily be interpreted as various attempts to find theoretical foundations and practical ways for an escape from politics altogether. The hallmark of all such escapes is the concept of rule, that is, the notion that men can lawfully and politically live

together only when some are entitled to command and the others forced to obey. The commonplace notion already to be found in Plato and Aristotle that every political community consists of those who rule and those who are ruled (on which assumption in turn are based the current definitions of forms of government—rule by one or monarchy, rule by few or oligarchy, rule by many or democracy) rests on a suspicion of action rather than on a contempt for men, and arose from the earnest desire to find a substitute for action rather than from any irresponsible or tyrannical will to power. (p.222)

When our politics is defined by the enlightenment and wisdom of the few who have seen the 'light' outside the cave, who then return to rule, we have destroyed plurality and the public realm – we have masters and followers. Equality and freedom are gone in the name of stability and predictability.

Under these circumstances, the essence of politics is "to know how to begin and to rule in the gravest matters with regard to timeliness and untimeliness"; action as such is entirely eliminated and has become the mere "execution of orders." (p.223)

This is one of the reasons why Arendt doesn't want to refer to herself as a political philosopher since all knowledge or systematization of politics is per definition incompatible with politics as free and originating from one's being and perplexity. When we make politics into philosophy and systematic knowledge then we create rulers and the ruled – systematic philosophy becomes the art of the ruler, or the tyrant.

It has also spoiled any hope for a revolution for Arendt claims that today's legitimacy comes from our inheritance of laws (*work*) that we adhere to, instead our ability to create something new (*action*). And all activities of *work* are distinct from action: *action* requires a union between thinking and doing, while *work* is organized through plans and the execution of those plans, which is a source of Arendt's worry that modern politics – defined by work over action – has made us act to achieve some greater plan, instead of actual realization of what we're doing. In revolutions we create new beginnings, which in the western tradition is not a source of legitimacy, which can only come from the laws established in the revolution, which is incompatible with the action required to create and sustain a revolution (as argued in *On Revolution*).

Plato, with his analogy of the cave, wants the philosophers to exit the cave to see the truth and then return to the peoples with it. In doing so he will also arrive with the *truth*, which is nothing else than presuppositions to legitimize governing. Following this, thinking becomes a form of subversion for everyone but the philosophers, for thinking would be to challenge the truths of the ideas. His political blueprint would try to resolve the issues of action by making into a form of machine:

Plato, who was the first to design a blueprint for the making of political bodies, has remained the inspiration of all later Utopias. And although none of these Utopias ever came to play any noticeable role in history—for in the few instances where Utopian schemes were realized, they broke down quickly under the weight of reality, not so much the reality of exterior circumstances as of the real human relationships they could not control (p.227)

Another consequence of the reduction of action into work is that work always implies violence and means/end logic in the shaping of society. So, when we have a revolution and need to

recreate a new order, and we try to base our legitimacy from the laws we create, we need to use violence to achieve it, causing a contradiction as violence is inherently a-political and destructive instead of politically creative. Further, the use of means/ends in politics will always bring the risk that some considers any means as justified by the ends in the establishment of a new political body:

As long as we believe that we deal with ends and means in the political realm, we shall not be able to prevent anybody's using all means to pursue recognized ends. The substitution of making for acting and the concomitant degradation of politics into a means to obtain an allegedly "higher" end [...] is as old as the tradition of political philosophy. (p.229)

As a certain peasant in a Monty Python sketch would say: "Come see the violence inherent in the system!"... Our philosophical system.

Chapter 32 – The Process Character of Action

Arendt begins this chapters by teasing a later discussion of natural science. She claims that work and philosophy has not only reduced Action into a structure, but that we've done the same with nature through the application of science. Here Heidegger's influence on Arendt becomes highly visible for she relies heavily on his concept of "challenging forth" nature to reveal itself to us and make itself available to our use. Arendt seems to claim the same thing.

She quickly emphasizes that this is a political act, for the science shares the same structure as action in its unpredictability, irreversibility, and anonymity of its actors. Arendt is very clear about this because the illusion that nature, through science, can be understood by the application of systematic knowledge has been applied on human history, so that history became a science, with the attempt to find the natural laws of behind all events.

Arendt is worried about this because it's just this historical pseudo-science that became the "blueprint" for the totalitarian states, who believed that action and free-will was pointless and even unattractive, for whatever we did the structures around us has already predetermined the result of our actions in the same way that attempting to make a pen float in the air is futile.

What Arendt wants to discuss is how we've tried to find excuses for ourselves to not engage in action. Just like the previous chapter was about building political systems to make action superfluous, here she wants to abolish the excuses we use to dismiss action as futile.

She does understand the impulse behind it as she acknowledges how action is unpredictable and scary. If one's actions have unforeseen and possibly horrible consequences, then action should not be taken by the sovereign (as Machiavelli noticed). The only way to make this palatable for everyone is to claim that the outcome of our action was predetermined by the structures around us, by denying free will, and therefore assuming that blame cannot be assigned to the person responsible for the action that resulted in the undesired outcome.

Since action was made impotent non-action (*vita contemplativa*) became a higher form of activity than action (*vita activa*). For it was only in the freedom of the mind, where the effects of one's thoughts are reversible and have predictable outcomes, that one can be truly sovereign. Hence the idea that true freedom lies in the mind, as argued by the Stoics.

For Arendt this is unacceptable. The belief that that freedom can only be achieved in the mind is to define freedom as the ability to be free from consequences, and the reality of action's

unpredictability. But freedom is only possible in politics, which require the public sphere and its plurality. If one uses the singularity of one's mind to achieve freedom, then we are essentially defining away the concept of freedom or servitude.

This is what Arendt believe the modern age has done with us. The idea that our freedom is only available to us in our mind is to distance ourselves from politics and seek freedom from politics' intervention in our lives (as she argues in the essay "what is freedom"). This form of freedom is also scary, for it knows no bounds or limitations, the freedom of my singularity is the conceptualization of my full sovereignty over everyone else, who, like in Plato's politics, become depoliticized and to be ruled.

In the last section of the book Arendt will try to return us from this unleashed imagination and tyrannous mindset, and to anchor ourselves in the reality that everything is *not* possible, to oppose the 20th-century mindset that seems to think that it was.

But, for the coming chapters, Arendt will first try to find a solution to the unpredictability of action in forgiveness – that's for next week.

Discussion questions:

1. Is political philosophy a form of cognition, or does it only create the foundation for a politic of cognition based on it?
2. Is political philosophy by necessity a form of work?
3. Should we be scared of the unpredictability of action? Is our fear of it justified, or something that must be overcome?
4. Is Arendt correct that legitimacy comes from the inheritance of laws over our ability to create new beginnings?
 - a. Is this why revolutions tend to fail?
5. Is Arendt correct that the systematization of politics always results in violence?
6. Do we believe we are only free when we are liberated from politics?
7. Is the belief in determinism incompatible with humane politics?

Part 6: The Vita Activa and The Modern Age

Seminar 13: chapters 33-34

I write this on the McDonalds at Düsseldorf's train station after the buss I was to take from München to Linköping got cancelled, and I was rerouted with three layovers and will arrive home 12 hours after schedule. I certainly need some inspiration to forgive – isn't that a coincidence?

Regardless, we've now reached the end of Action, and Arendt flexes her poetic muscles to end this famous section with as strong an impression as possible. I always get excited and feel profoundly inspired reading these chapters – I hope you did too.

Major themes

- Irreversibility: Forgiveness, Revenge, and Punishment
- Promises: Power, Authority, and Stability
- *Nativity* as the ontology of politics and authority
- Love and Politics

Chapter 33 – Irreversibility and The Power to Forgive

In the previous chapters Arendt began her discussion about the unpredictability of action, and how Plato and other political scientists have tried to find a remedy to it in political theory, *work*. Arendt rejects this.

In this chapter she begins, as usual, by reiterating the relationship between Labor, Work and Action, and how only action can create meaning in the stories we surround ourselves with. Not even thinking can create meaning, bound by its own activity of perplexed introspection.

With action being the “highest faculty” that can control and limit the other aspects of the *vita activa*, there is nothing that can control and manage action, except forgiving:

The possible redemption from the predicament of irreversibility—of being unable to undo what one has done though one did not, and could not, have known what he was doing—is the faculty of forgiving. The remedy for unpredictability, for the chaotic uncertainty of the future, is contained in the faculty to make and keep promises. The two faculties belong together in so far as one of them, forgiving, serves to undo the deeds of the past, whose "sins" hang like Damocles' sword over every new generation; and the other, binding oneself through promises, serves to set up in the ocean of uncertainty, which the future is by definition, islands of security without which not even continuity, let alone durability of any kind, would be possible in the relationships between men. (p.237)

The reason forgiveness is so important is that the sins we commit, and inherit, are the negative form of the stories that Arendt value, it is the stories that *destroy* the common world instead of *creating* it. Equally, the reason promises are so important is that they offer the “islands of stability” that not only enables action to be trusted, but also the stability *within* us so the radical freedom of action becomes manageable.

Both are only possible in interchange with others and are therefore only possible in the public realm – they both rely on it, but also create and sustain it. Without forgiveness and promises action would become impossible as its unpredictability.

This is another of the core mistakes done by Plato in his political theory. His wish to establish the political order on self-rulership and personal morality ignores the fact that morality is created and sustained in intersubjectivity:

For Platonic rulership, whose legitimacy rested upon the domination of the self, draws its guiding principles—those which at the same time justify and limit power over others—from a relationship established between me and myself, so that the right and wrong of relationships with others are determined by attitudes toward one's self, until the whole of the public realm is seen in the image of "man writ large," of the right order between man's individual capacities of mind, soul, and body. The moral code, on the other hand, inferred from the faculties of forgiving and of making promises, rests on experiences which nobody could ever have with himself, which, on the contrary, are entirely based on the presence of others. And just as the extent and modes of self-rule justify and determine rule over others—how one rules himself, he will rule others—thus the extent and modes of being forgiven and being promised determine the extent and modes in which one may be able to forgive himself or keep promises concerned only with himself.

She contrasts this Platonic self-rule and self-forgiveness with Jesus of Nazareth, whose "experiences in the small and closely knit community of his followers" made him discover the importance of forgiveness in the sustaining of a public sphere. While God may be the ultimate source of forgiveness His will must be enacted by us humans here in the mortal realm. The reason we may do this, according to Arendt, is that radical (willed and intended) evil is rare, and that most evil is done by people who don't know what they are doing³⁸.

This is the true hallmark of those offenses which, since Kant, we call "radical evil" and about whose nature so little is known, even to us who have been exposed to one of their rare outbursts on the public scene. All we know is that we can neither punish nor forgive such offenses and that they therefore transcend the realm of human affairs and the potentialities of human power, both of which they radically destroy wherever they make their appearance. Here, where the deed itself dispossesses us of all power, we can indeed only repeat with Jesus: "It were better for him that a millstone were hung about his neck, and he cast into the sea." (P.241)

In fact, in Eichmann in Jerusalem she seeks revenge at Eichmann due to his "unwillingness to share earth with others" and therefore broke the golden rule of plurality – hence nobody should have to share the earth with him. Here in *The Human Condition* Arendt is clear that this is revenge, and that any other response (forgiveness) would be impossible as his crimes require that he suffer what for he did to so many others:

In contrast to revenge, which is the natural, automatic reaction to transgression and which because of the irreversibility of the action process can be expected and even

³⁸ This is where things become interesting in a meta-perspective – she claims that trespasses and sins are inevitable aspects of taking action, and that we therefore must be able to forgive to sustain the 'web of relationships' and allow humanity to be free from the burden of history... But how does this relate to her discussion of Eichmann's Banal Evil? She did not think that his deeds were possible of being forgiven, and that he should hang for his crimes. So, are we only able to forgive if a trespass was done under the activity of action, but not work?

calculated, the act of forgiving can never be predicted; it is the only reaction that acts in an unexpected way and thus retains, though being a reaction, something of the original character of action. Forgiving, in other words, is the only reaction which does not merely re-act but acts anew and unexpectedly, unconditioned by the act which provoked it and therefore freeing from its consequences both the one who forgives and the one who is forgiven. The freedom contained in Jesus' teachings of forgiveness is the freedom from vengeance, which encloses both doer and sufferer in the relentless automatism of the action process, which by itself need never come to an end. (P.241)

This makes Arendt claim that forgiveness is a form of love in its ability to oversee the action of a *what* for *who* it was that did it. Hence it is only love that truly has the power to forgive. I consider this to be one of Arendt most beautiful passages, and I don't think I could summarize her thoughts while doing justice to her:

For love, although it is one of the rarest occurrences in human lives, indeed possesses an unequalled power of self-revelation and an unequalled clarity of vision for the disclosure of who, precisely because it is unconcerned to the point of total unworldliness with what the loved person may be, with his qualities and shortcomings no less than with his achievements, failings, and transgressions. Love, by reason of its passion, destroys the in-between which relates us to and separates us from others. As long as its spell lasts, the only in-between which can insert itself between two lovers is the child, love's own product. The child, this in-between to which the lovers now are related and which they hold in common, is representative of the world in that it also separates them; it is an indication that they will insert a new world into the existing world. Through the child, it is as though the lovers return to the world from which their love had expelled them. But this new worldliness, the possible result and the only possibly happy ending of a love affair, is, in a sense, the end of love, which must either overcome the partners anew or be transformed into another mode of belonging together. Love, by its very nature, is unworldly, and it is for this reason rather than its rarity that it is not only apolitical but antipolitical, perhaps the most powerful of all antipolitical human forces. (P.242)

Ending the chapters Arendt makes a short claim that she returns to later in her career: that we need someone external to us to forgive us. In *Life of The Mind* Arendt argues that thinking is a form of "two-in-one" in that we are one person who still have an internal dialogue when we are thinking. This means that all deeds we do will be brought up on ourselves by ourselves – it is the typical sleepless night where we torment ourselves over things we regret. We have this internal dialogue because we are unable to forgive ourselves. This is where an external person is needed to intervene and give us "the world's" opinion on what we did, and then either forgive us, take revenge on us, or punish us.

It's also related to Eichmann in Arendt's theory that he had no such "two-in-one" and that he had no bad conscience about what he did during the holocaust. He didn't lose much sleep over it and didn't seek any forgiveness.

Chapter 34 – Unpredictability and the Power to Forgive

While forgiveness (love) has a complicated relationship to the public realm, promises is possibly the essence of it. As politics demands plurality and a multitude of perspectives and actors, we cannot be sure of the stability of either individual persons (who may change overnight) or of entire political communities, who may betray the individual. Promises are the social contract we

engage with each other on a daily basis and is what sustains the public sphere and the web of relationship – destroy the trust in promises and there are no certainties anymore, neither in the character of men nor the virtues or sins of communities. Indeed, this connects us back to Arendt's discussion of power originating the ability to act in unison, which require the structure created by promises.

Here I also think Arendt gives a critique of Carl Schmitt's Sovereignty theory. According to him politics demand sovereigns, who are the singular entity that can make exceptions to rules – to break promises. Their claim to rule is to act without the trust of the people around them, only acting through the authority of their position, and it's a form of politics that I believe Arendt tries to give a fundamental critique of in her works; following the complete collapse of European political traditions we need to recreate authority, and while Schmitt finds it in the tyrant, Arendt seeks it in the Being of the individual in a political community, citing Nietzsche's argument that *will* distinguishes animal from human. Promises are intrinsic goods for any political body, and not as the instrumental tool to broken by the sovereign as Schmitt thinks:

These moral precepts are the only ones that are not applied to action from the outside, from some supposedly higher faculty or from experiences outside action's own reach. They arise, on the contrary, directly out of the will to live together with others in the mode of acting and speaking, and thus they are like control mechanisms built into the very faculty to start new and unending processes. If without action and speech, without the articulation of natality, we would be doomed to swing forever in the ever-recurring cycle of becoming, then without the faculty to undo what we have done and to control at least partially the processes we have let loose, we would be the victims of an automatic necessity bearing all the marks of the inexorable laws which, according to the natural sciences before our time, were supposed to constitute the outstanding characteristic of natural processes (p.246)

This '*natality*' – the ability to create something new – is where Arendt wants to cite the foundation of all politics. Humanity, in our property of *being*, possess the plurality and ability to start something new, to make a new start and create a new Rome. This, of course, was of crucial importance in the time where the book was written, with a seeming inevitability of a third world war, repeat of totalitarianism, and political nihilism. The central message in Arendt's conception of Action is our ability to create the *new*:

The new always happens against the overwhelming odds of statistical laws and their probability, which for all practical, everyday purposes amounts to certainty; the new therefore always appears in the guise of a miracle. (178)

The reason Arendt took aim at psychology and behavioral sciences in the beginning of the book is that they will abolish this *natality* for a polity of scientific framework. A political entity based on the management of an "*what-ified*" humanity will result in the tyrannic delusions of viewing political history like the Great Lawgiver establishing politics on everyone else. Politics demands plurality and is only possible in the public sphere where we are all participants and makers of our own destinies.

If her quote on love is one of her most beautiful quotes, her ending paragraphs in Action is the most beautiful. Instead of dissecting it I will just copy it in and then add footnotes where I'll contextualize what she's saying:

The life span of man running toward death³⁹ would inevitably carry everything human to ruin and destruction⁴⁰ if it were not for the faculty of interrupting it and beginning something new, a faculty which is inherent in action like an ever-present reminder that men, though they must die, are not born in order to die but in order to begin⁴¹. Yet just as, from the standpoint of nature, the rectilinear movement of man's life-span between birth and death looks like a peculiar deviation from the common natural rule of cyclical movement⁴², thus action, seen from the viewpoint of the automatic processes which seem to determine the course of the world, looks like a miracle. In the language of natural science, it is the "infinite improbability which occurs regularly." Action is, in fact, the one miracle-working faculty of man, as Jesus of Nazareth, whose insights into this faculty can be compared in their originality and unprecedentedness with Socrates' insights into the possibilities of thought⁴³, must have known very well when he likened the power to forgive to the more general power of performing miracles, putting both on the same level and within the reach of man⁴⁴. The miracle that saves the world, the realm of human affairs, from its normal, "natural"⁴⁵ ruin is ultimately the tact of natality, in which the faculty of action is ontologically rooted. It is, in other words, the birth of new men and the new beginning⁴⁶, the action they are capable of by virtue of being born. Only the full experience of this capacity can bestow upon human affairs faith and hope, those two essential characteristics of human existence which Greek antiquity ignored altogether⁴⁷, discounting the keeping of faith as a very uncommon and not too important virtue and counting hope among the evils of illusion in Pandora's box. It is this faith in and hope for the world that found perhaps its most glorious and most succinct expression in the few words with which the Gospels announced their "glad tidings": "A child has been born unto us."⁴⁸

Discussion questions:

1. On page 238 Arendt claims that we've performed acted in nature and that we've done things that cannot be undone. While arguably referring to atmospheric testing of nuclear bombs, can we make the same argument with climate change? And if so, how do the coming generations forgive and recreate the public realm, and should they?

³⁹ Critique of Heidegger's Being-towards-Death

⁴⁰ The massification caused by Being-towards-death will ruin all politics and cause a potentiality of totalitarianism.

⁴¹ Action is natality – the ability to interrupt processes (*work & labor*) and begin anew and recreate authority

⁴² Reducing man into his biology is to destroy him by turning a *who* into a *what* – *murder to dissect*.

⁴³ She is referring to Socrates discovery that *thought (thinking)* can destroy anything and everything given to us, and thereby throw us back on ourselves and our perplexity over the world.

⁴⁴ This is what I referred to when describing the section on Action being Arendt's attempt to make a philosophy of miracles.

⁴⁵ I believe this refers to the claims to truth by Racial Biology and Bolsheviks – they claimed they represented the natural order of the world, but Arendt denies there's any such thing except what we've created in our intersubjectivity in the public sphere – "truths" that are as easily dispelled as someone shouting the 'King has no cloths!'.

⁴⁶ While both the Nazis and Bolsheviks tried to create new men, Arendt claims that the only way to do that is by rediscovering and redefining yourself – not by applying ideological claims to universal truths.

⁴⁷ The Greeks got much right, but they never came face-to-face with anything like our 20th century. Hope and faith are crucial political virtues for Arendt, for the alternative is intolerable.

⁴⁸ The 'natality' is not just our ability to take action but it's also each of our births! Whenever a person is born a completely new world is also created, full of potentiality, unpredictability, love and forgiveness. As long as a new generation is created there will always be hope for change. See also how love creates a new world through love resulting in a new person, implying a connection between natality, love, and worldliness: *Amor Mundi*.

2. Is it only possible to forgive people who took action over people who were only engaged in work?⁴⁹
3. Is Arendt's concept of Natality realistic or more poetic? Is it about inspiring faith in politics and political engagement?
4. Having now finished the section on Action, do you agree that Arendt's conception of politics is *joy*?
5. Do you agree with Arendt that love is arguably the most prominent antipolitical force?
6. Arendt considered naming *The Human Condition* as *Amor Mundi* (Love for the world) – how do you think her concept of love refers to worldliness, and the main topics in the book?
7. Is Arendt's existentialist reimagining of politics and authority as originating from *being* over *laws* attractive, or even realistic?

⁴⁹ This is a question she confronts directly in *Eichmann in Jerusalem*. How can you put a person on trial who never did anything criminal under his legal jurisdiction? How can you attribute responsibility to a person who lacked any real personal initiative or will? Among many other questions.

Seminar 14: chapters 35-36

Having finished her discussion of labor, work and action, Arendt now turns to science and technology. In general Arendt is most famous for her critique of modern politics, but her unique and insightful critique of scientism and logical positivism deserve equal amount of respect, and lately more attention has been brought to it.

In some way I believe she was before her time, and that the ideas she sketched here was later picked up by thinkers such as Haraway, whose concept of the 'god-trick' shares many similarities to Arendt's Archimedean Point. This is a discussion that Arendt has been implying throughout the entire book, as seen by the following two quotes from the section on Work:

It is quite obvious that the Greeks dreaded this devaluation of world and nature with its inherent anthropocentrism—the "absurd" opinion that man is the highest being and that everything else is subject to the exigencies of human life (Aristotle)—no less than they despised the sheer vulgarity of all consistent utilitarianism. [...] The point of the matter is that Plato saw immediately that if one makes man the measure of all things for use, it is man the user and instrumentalizer, and not man the speaker and doer or man the thinker, to whom the world is being related. (p.157)

It is this loss of standards and universal rules, without which no world could ever be erected by man, that Plato already perceived in the Protagorean proposal to establish man, the fabricator of things, and the use he makes of them, as their supreme measure. This shows how closely the relativity of the exchange market is connected with the instrumentality arising out of the world of the craftsman and the experience of fabrication. (p.166)

Major themes

- Science as a force of objectification and nihilism
- The concept of World Alienation as our loss of the public sphere
- Objectification and totalitarianism
- The telescope and our discovery of a de-subjectified subject-position
- The Archimedean Point, science, mathematics, and totalitarianism

Chapter 35 – World Alienation

Having already argued that modernity is characterized by the reduction of the public sphere into exchange-logics and management, Arendt will now begin to contextualize this analysis in science and technology.

She begins by noting that three persons, and their deeds, created the threshold which brought us to modernity – Luther, Galileo, and Columbus. She will give them each their due attention, but she begins by sketching the outlines of her theory by noting the curiosity that the pursuit of expanding knowledge reduced the world's complexity. The reason for this pursuit of knowledge will be introduced in the next chapter⁵⁰.

⁵⁰ The reason is that the European medieval worldview was profoundly chocked if not destroyed by the threefold discoveries of new continents not mentioned in the bible, the insight that the moon was full of craters, and that the religious practices of the time had no support in the bible. This shock forced European societies to try and find a new basis for all knowledge in science.

When humanity mapped the entire world, brought it together through increases in transportation and information speed, and once things became mapped and known, they lost their potentiality and were reduced into parts⁵¹, for “nothing can remain immense if it can be measured” (p.250). To measure the immensity of things however require that they can be conceptualized and observed, which requires the measurer to take a step backwards from the direct phenomenological and empirical sphere:

It is in the nature of the human surveying capacity that it can function only if man disentangles himself from all involvement in and concern with the close at hand and withdraws himself to a distance from everything near him. The greater the distance between himself and his surroundings, world or earth, the more he will be able to survey and to measure and the less will worldly, earth-bound space be left to him (p.251)

This measuring perspective thus require us to remove ourselves from direct impressions and try to find some ‘larger picture’ that tells more about the reality of things than the actual worldly experiences we have in our embodiment. Arendt calls it *world alienation*.

This world alienation is however different from another form of alienation that coincidentally⁵² appeared independently yet simultaneous with world alienation: inner alienation. Here she relies on Max Weber’s famous Protestant Work Ethic to argue that the birth of capitalism required an internal split between desire and will, and that Calvinists had to view their inner world with the same suspicion that modern man must have toward his embodied experiences in his world alienation.

The combination of both forms of alienation (world alienation & inner alienation) has made everything ‘given’ become reduced into Heidegger’s Standing Reserve: secularized and objectified resources without any subjective attachment to humanity – which echoes Arendt’s discussion in Work on how our standard of value has become exchange-market valuation.

The historical evidence, on the contrary, shows that modern men were not thrown back upon this world but upon themselves. One of the most persistent trends in modern philosophy since Descartes and perhaps its most original contribution to philosophy has been an exclusive concern with the self, as distinguished from the soul or person or man in general, an attempt to reduce all experiences, with the world as well as with other human beings, to experiences between man and himself. The greatness of Max Weber's discovery about the origins of capitalism lay precisely in his demonstration that an enormous, strictly mundane activity is possible without any care for or enjoyment of the world whatever, an activity whose deepest motivation, on the contrary, is worry and care about the self (p.254)

If everything has become objectified, as Arendt argue is the consequence of capitalism in the section on work, then all concerns between a person and themselves becomes equally

⁵¹ In origins of Totalitarianism Arendt argues that this happened to the very concept of humanity as race ‘science’ dissected human differences to understand the world better. She explicitly referred to it as the ‘end of humanity’.

⁵² Just like science became a solution to the cosmological crisis in footnote #1, the birth of world alienation and inner alienation was both created from the turn towards science to find a solution to the cosmological crisis.

objectified, so that desires, wishes, will and all other mental experiences must find objective and materialistic reasons and logics⁵³ for our unique traits.

This is then connected to an argument that Giorgio Agamben clarified, namely the distinction between Bios (bare life: biological existence) and Zoe (qualified life: soul, dignity, value-in-itself). If our relationship to ourselves have become the relationship to a scientific and objective mass of biological and chemical reactions, then we are essentially sack of meat (bios) that can be treated in horrific ways. As Arendt argued in *Origins of Totalitarianism*, the force behind those politics was the reduction of all humans into superfluous persons in a mass, just mere sacks of meat to be reformed or exterminated, and that all human dignity was gone.

But it was not just science that created this de-valuation of the world into consumer objects. Arendt makes sure to repeat the argument that capitalism and the consumer's machine-society reduced every person into classes and destroyed the public sphere that separates us into individual persons. This destruction of the public sphere, and its world alienation, is given a strong implication of being a source of the totalitarian mass-movements:

Just as the family and its property were replaced by class membership and national territory, so mankind now begins to replace nationally bound societies, and the earth replaces the limited state territory. But whatever the future may bring, the process of world alienation, started by expropriation and characterized by an ever-increasing progress in wealth, can only assume even more radical proportions if it is permitted to follow its own inherent law. For men cannot become citizens of the world as they are citizens of their countries, and social men cannot own collectively as family and household men own their private property. The rise of society brought about the simultaneous decline of the public as well as the private realm. But the eclipse of a common public world, so crucial to the formation of the lonely mass man and so dangerous in the formation of the worldless mentality of modern ideological mass movements, began with the much more tangible loss of a privately owned share in the world. (p.257)

Chapter 36 – The Discovery of the Archimedean Point

While the previous chapter was about the effect of worldlessness, Arendt now sets focus on the first of the three main persons responsible for modernity's distrust of the world, and the dangerous unforeseen consequences of their achievements. First is Galileo and the telescope.

Not Galileo but the philosophers were the first to abolish the dichotomy between one earth and one sky above it, promoting, as they thought, the earth "to the rank of the noble stars" and finding her a home in an eternal and infinite universe. And it seems the astronomers needed no telescope to assert that, contrary to all sense experience, it is not the sun that moves around the earth but the earth that circles the sun. If the historian looks back upon these beginnings with all the wisdom and prejudices of hindsight, he is tempted to conclude that no empirical confirmation was needed to abolish the Ptolemaic system. What was wanted was, rather, the speculative courage to follow the ancient and medieval principle of simplicity in nature—even if it led to the denial of all sense experience—and the great boldness of Copernicus' imagination,

⁵³ I think Arendt will argue later in this section that this objectification of humanity is the founding issue for behavioral sciences and psychology.

which lifted him from the earth and enabled him to look down upon her as though he actually were an inhabitant of the sun (p.285f)

Here, in summary, is Arendt argument regarding the seminal importance of the telescope. While there was no instruments that could enhance hearing, touch, smell, or any other of our senses, Galileo was able to enhance our vision to such a degree that the world of appearances could be shown to be incorrect – for the moon had craters, and earth rotated around the sun.

The radical implications of this becomes obvious when Descartes decided to take seriously the issue raised by the telescope when he asked if we were all being deceived by our senses by some demon, and that we needed a new source to base all our knowledge on. His radical skepticism threw us back on our internal faculties and accepted that the external world could be a mirage, forcing us to find some methodology to stabilize our surroundings and perception – a methodology that would eventually become science.

The modern astrophysical world view, which began with Galileo, and its challenge to the adequacy of the senses to reveal reality, have left us a universe of whose qualities we know no more than the way they affect our measuring instruments, and—in the words of Eddington—"the former have as much resemblance to the latter as a telephone number has to a subscriber." Instead of objective qualities, in other words, we find instruments, and instead of nature or the universe—in the words of Heisenberg—man encounters only himself. (p.261)

Here we see that Arendt is reiterating the same argument as in chapter 35, that modernity has exchanged all values for mere factuality. This factuality is enforced both by our economic system where work has been reduced into labor, but also in our thinking where our distrust of our senses has forced us into scientific objectivity in which we must view everything, including ourselves and our bodies, in a third person perspective – this is the Archimedean point, the delusion that we can separate ourselves from *the human condition* and view reality from an imagined position outside our bodies and subjectivity.

[W]e always handle nature from a point in the universe outside the earth. Without actually standing where Archimedes wished to stand (*dos moi pou sto*), still bound to the earth through the human condition, we have found a way to act on the earth and within terrestrial nature as though we dispose of it from outside, from the Archimedean point. (p.262)

Arendt finds the concept to be concerning. If we need to think what we're doing⁵⁴ we must embody ourselves and think from body and 'soul'. If we displace ourselves into a third-person perspective our thinking will always be cognition, and not bound to the perplexity of our existence.

This is to some point the very goal of discovering and using the Archimedean point. If we're unable to trust our senses, and must use science to understand the world, then we must find some fixed position from which to approach our concepts. Arendt argues that Einstein's

⁵⁴ This makes her initial statement in the beginning of the book, "What I propose, therefore, is very simple: it is nothing more than to think what we are doing," into a claim that she is passing judgement on the factuality goes-on of her contemporary world, and that a world which has stopped thinking can be destroyed and shown its contingency through the power of thinking.

relativity has forced us to find some fixed position which we can view as normative, and she believes that the answer was found in mathematics:

[I]nstead of observing natural phenomena as they were given to him, he placed nature under the conditions of his own mind, that is, under conditions won from a universal, astrophysical viewpoint, a cosmic standpoint outside nature itself. It is for this reason that mathematics became the leading science of the modern age (p.265)

If our only way of describing reality has become mathematical calculations then we have both made reality into cognition, unable to approach it from our natural language given to us in our existential being, but also unable to have any subjectivity for everything must be expressed in numbers:

Now the phenomena could be saved only in so far as they could be reduced to a mathematical order, and this mathematical operation does not serve to prepare man's mind for the revelation of true being by directing it to the ideal measures that appear in the sensually given data, but serves, on the contrary, to reduce these data to the measure of the human mind, which, given enough distance, being sufficiently remote and uninvolved, can look upon and handle the multitude and variety of the concrete in accordance with its own patterns and symbols. These are no longer ideal forms disclosed to the eye of the mind, but are the results of removing the eyes of the mind, no less than the eyes of the body, from the phenomena, of reducing all appearances (p.267)

But all of this is an illusion. Arendt is firm in her belief that there is nothing that can remain when exposed to our "winds of thought" which blows everything away. What modernity has done is however to try and replace the need for thought by building knowledge-systems that gives the appearance of objectivity, so that we can accept the premises provided without analyzing them too closely and discover their inherent flaws.

The reason this is of crucial importance for Arendt is revealed in the ending quote of the chapter:

[T]he feeling of suspicion, outrage, and despair, which was the first, and spiritually is still the most lasting consequence of the discovery that the 'Archimedean point was no vain dream of idle speculation, is not unlike the helpless outrage of a man who, having watched with his own eyes how these dots were thrown arbitrarily and without foresight onto the paper, is shown and forced to admit that all his senses and all his powers of judgment have betrayed him and that what he saw was the evolution of a "geometrical line whose direction is constantly and uniformly defined by one rule. (p.267f)

That is, if we believe that we can find a science of everything, then we have found a truth that both dismisses free will and political freedoms due to the necessity to follow that truth. Two societies tried that in the previous century, and they were both totalitarian.

Arendt wants to dispel the cognitive structures supported by science to bring forth new thinking, for that's obligatory if we want to achieve Natality.

Discussion questions:

1. What is the difference between world alienation and the Archimedean Point?

2. Is it true that science is per definition reductive of the things it studies?
3. Do you think World Alienation is real? And if so, what has changed from Arendt's time to today?
4. Is the connection between the objectification of reality, and the reduction of everything into resources realistic? If so, could it be a cause for the horrors of totalitarianism?
5. Does capitalism tend to reduce the value of things, or just express it in valuation?
6. Is Arendt's argument about the connection between the telescope and Descartes reasonable?
7. Can we *think* (as distinct from cognition) in the Archimedean Point?
8. Is there any truth the argument that the Archimedean Point is crucial for totalitarian societies?
9. On page 252 Arendt writes
"Yet, such [contrafactual historical] speculations are meaningful to the extent that they remind us that history is a story of events and not of forces or ideas with predictable courses. They are idle and even dangerous when used as arguments against reality and when meant to point to positive potentialities and alternatives, because their number is not only indefinite by definition but they also lack the tangible unexpectedness of the event, and compensate for it by mere plausibility."

It strikes me as being a claim that history is indeed a procession of events, but that using the same logic in our reality is to deny the impossibility to expect or predict action. Why would that be "dangerous"?

Seminar 15: chapters 37-39

Not much to say about these chapters, more investigations into the relationship between Descartes, World Alienation, and Science. If anything these may be some of her more dystopic chapters – if they weren't preceded by her suggested solution in Action.

Major themes

- The necessity to find a new foundation for modern cosmology, and why science can't be a solution to it.
- Descartes inversion of Doubt
- Descartes attempt to bridge Vita Contemplativa with worldliness.
- Descartes contribution to world alienation
- The decline of Common Sense in world alienated modernity.
- Mathematics and logic as massifying

Chapter 37 – Universal versus Natural Science

Arendt makes a distinction between three vaguely defined forms of science:

1. Terrestrial and natural laws
2. Cosmic natural science
3. Universal science

For brevity they can be summarized in the following table

	Terrestrial natural laws	and	Cosmic science	natural	Universal Science
Founding event	Aristotle(?)		The telescope's discovery of sense-unreliability		Einstein's relativity and nuclear physics
Premised perspective	Embodied experience	sense-	Archimedean Point		Universally distributed and disembodied
Phenomenology	Being in the world		Introspection		Self-denial

Arendt will discuss cosmic natural science at length in chapters 38 & 39, but spends some time on 'universal science' in this chapter, in which she claims that the discovery of relativity, and the ability to channel cosmic forces (nuclear physics) into human society, has reduced everything into hard objectivity:

From the viewpoint of the universe, the earth is but a special case and can be understood as such, just as in this view there cannot be a decisive distinction between matter and energy, both being "only different forms of the selfsame basic substance [...] Everything happening on earth has become relative since the earth's relatedness to the universe became the point of reference for all measurements." (p.269f)

This new science is fundamentally liberating for humanity. Through it we have found new incredible technology and powers in nuclear physics, but also dangers, not just in the possibility of the destruction of life on Earth, but in our necessity to find new sociopolitical and cultural structures that correspond to our new technology and objectified cosmology.

Indeed, the very eclipse of 'terrestrial and natural laws' and 'cosmic natural science' for the new 'universal science' has thrown us into the same situation Europeans found themselves in with Luther's, Galileo's and Columbus's implosion of the medieval worldview. According to Arendt we need to establish a new cosmology to organize the world around us according to some principles. We can't rely on more science according to her as the relativity of universal science does not provide any of the foundations from which moral laws can be enabled:

[I]t took no more than a few decades, hardly one generation, for the human mind to draw certain conclusions from Galileo's discoveries and the methods and assumption by which they had been accomplished. The human mind changed in a matter of years or decades as radically as the human world in a matter of centuries; and while this change naturally remained restricted to the few who belonged to that strangest of all modern societies, the society of scientists and the republic of letters (the only society which has survived all changes of conviction and conflict without a revolution and without ever forgetting to "honor the man whose beliefs it no longer shares"), this society anticipated in many respects, by sheer force of trained and controlled imagination, the radical change of mind of all modern men which became a politically demonstrable reality only in our own time. (p.271)

Here Arendt is referring to her analysis of Totalitarianism, as a political system that believed that anything can be possible: "the radical change of mind of all modern men which became politically demonstrable reality".

Further issues arise from our need to have something given to have cognition. Descartes found this in Doubt – as we shall see in chapter 38 – but in a fully relativist and objectified universe then our thinking and philosophy can make nothing else than subjectivist approaches to the world – which is always going to place us in the danger of the totalitarian manipulation of "objective reality" and the colonization of our subjectivities.

Luckily, Arendt has given a solution to these issues in intersubjectivity and Amor Mundi, as argued in the section on Action.

Chapter 38 – The Rise of Cartesian Doubt

In contrast to the title of the chapter Arendt makes sure to mention that Philosophy has always been relying on doubt for its activity. She explicitly mentions the Greek *Thaumazein* as a form of perplexity that gave rise to Socrates. In contrast to this she argues that Descartes founded a different form of philosophical doubt which concerns her.

Horrified over Galileo's discovery, and subsequent treatment by the authorities, Descartes set out to resolve the empirical and ontological issues created by him:

The philosophers understood at once that Galileo's discoveries implied no mere challenge to the testimony of the senses and that it was no longer reason, as in Aristarchus and Copernicus, that had "committed such a rape on their senses," in which case men indeed would have needed only to choose between their faculties and to let innate reason become "the mistress of their credulity." It was not reason but a manmade instrument, the telescope, which actually changed the physical world view; it was not contemplation, observation, and speculation which led to the new knowledge, but the active stepping in of homo faber, of making and fabricating. In other words, man had been deceived so long as he trusted that reality and truth would

reveal themselves to his senses and to his reason if only he remained true to what he saw with the eyes of body and mind. (p.274)

All common sense said that the sun revolved around earth, but all that had been disproven by Galileo, which motivated Descartes to question everything that his senses told him:

If Being and Appearance part company forever, and this—as Marx once remarked—is indeed the basic assumption of all modern science, then there is nothing left to be taken upon faith; everything must be doubted. (p.275)

To do this Descartes took the radical step to challenge and question everything given except God. All authority had to be abolished and recreated anew by introspection in the Cogito. The trade-off, which Descartes seems to have been unaware of, was that the phenomenological world lost its reality and truth, and that these could only be found within our internal Being – setting us on the path towards world alienation:

This Being, on the contrary, is tremendously active and energetic: it creates its own appearances, except that these appearances are delusions. Whatever human senses perceive is brought about by invisible, secret forces, and if through certain devices, ingenious instruments, these forces are caught in the act rather than discovered—as an animal is trapped or a thief is caught much against their own will and intentions—it turns out that this tremendously effective Being is of such a nature that its disclosures must be illusions and that conclusions drawn from its appearances must be delusions. (p.276)

As the world thus had become unreliable an opening was created for philosophical ideas that would explain the hidden forces that moved the world, acting on the Cartesian premise that the 'outside'/objective world could be explained by introspection. This then led to creation of grand meta-narrative theories that claimed to explain reality with thinkers like Hegel, Marx, and Darwin.

Another unintended effect of these theories was that they came with claims to authority and emphasis on political "work," and following this came whole new moralities and cosmologies. In this way ideologies became a way to reorient humanity to the world through a form of collective introspection and world alienation over Action.

What Descartes achieved was to turn doubt from a reflexive premise for thinking and philosophy (perplexity/*Thaumazein*) into an instrument for cognition. The Cartesian Doubt Arendt refers to in the title is the doubt that does not disclose our being-in-the-world and existence, but the premise for cognition in the same way that the Socratic revolution in the Athenian cosmology resulted in Plato finding a premise for politics in the Ideas.

Chapter 39 – Introspection and the loss of Common Sense

Introspection is a form of perplexity where one encounters only oneself, in this way we never have to prove our existence as Descartes believed – as we have introspection, we also have Being per the motto that there is instead of there being not.

In this way our mental life is real and has being, but in its introspective focus it cannot prove the being of the world that surrounds us since appearance (to our being and perception) is distinct from Being, which Descartes realized after reading Galileo's discovery.

However, when Descartes encouraged introspection, he did so in the belief that he only needed to prove his own existence and God to ensure that he was not deceived by some malicious demon. The consequence was that the bridge between being and the world had to rely on God, which makes his version of the *Vita Contemplativa* worldly, and could formulate the core premise of the scientific methodology.

But this solution was the subjectification of the world, preparing us for the universal science:

Nothing perhaps could prepare our minds better for the eventual dissolution of matter into energy, of objects into a whirl of atomic occurrences, than this dissolution of objective reality into subjective states of mind or, rather, into subjective mental processes. (p.282)

But the subjectification of the world could be overcome by the triumph of humanity over nature. If we could tame and “enframe” it (as Heidegger would say) then we could be sure about the reality of it as what we produce always originate from a model understood in our mental faculties – as argued in the section on Work.

This Cartesian move from *introspection into world* made common sense impossible. If *common sense* is a form of judgement, which itself is a form of taste⁵⁵, then the world alienation of Cartesian introspection and instrumental doubt means that everything has become possible, for common sense and taste can be manipulated by totalitarian political regimes.

This sense now was called common merely because it happened to be common to all. What men now have in common is not the world but the structure of their minds, and this they cannot have in common, strictly speaking; their faculty of reasoning can only happen to be the same in everybody. The fact that, given the problem of two plus two we all will come out with the same answer, four, is henceforth the very model of common-sense reasoning. (p.283)

And since we have lost the world (public sphere) we've also lost that entity which both binds us all together and separates us. So, with the Cartesian doubt we've built a world upon logic, which assumes that every brain functions according to the same principles, and that a shared reality can be built upon this massification, and that those who do not understand or believe in said logic must be excluded from our public sphere as people who don't live in reality. This is of course precarious, for what if there's a regime, as Orwell feared, that makes everyone believe that two plus two is five? If our reality stems from our introspection applied on the world then we're always going to be in danger of the politics of inner “colonialization” – and I believe this is exactly what we're seeing in today's social media madness.

Discussion questions:

1. Is the distinction between cosmic natural science and universal science reasonable?
2. Is Arendt believing too much in the “two cultures” (C.P Snow) discourse about the incompatibility between STEM and the Humanities? Can't science resolve the crises of the 1950's?
3. Is science incompatible with action?

⁵⁵ As Arendt argues in *Life of the Mind*

4. Is Arendt's analysis of Descartes reasonable?
5. Does it follow that the Cogito resulted in world alienation, and gave rise to ideologies and the decline of common sense?
6. If our need to subjectify the world through measuring it originated from our introspection, then can a parallel to imperialism be drawn here? Arendt argues in *Origins of Totalitarianism* that imperialism had a two-fold character of objectifying every atrocity while subjectifying the endless need for its expansion
7. Does logic and math really originate from the structures of our brain?
8. Are cognitive premises inherently massifying?
9. Has the world lost its "common sense" as Arendt would describe it?

Seminar 16: chapters 40-42

We're approaching the end of *The Human Condition*, and that's quite noticeable in these chapters. Arendt makes several references to previous discussions and it's quite hard to understand what she's trying to say, and how she is arguing, if one can't recall her analysis of work or the relationship between science and democracy.

Major themes

- Mathematics, cosmology, and society
- Science, technology, and introspection
- *Being's* change into *Becoming*.
- History and process as the foundation of modern society
- Ontology and Epistemology, and modern political change

Chapter 40 – Thought and the Modern World View

Arendt begins where she left off in chapter 39, by claiming that the Descartes had moved the Archimedean Point into ourselves, in the sense that our doubt has distanced the world of appearances from our Being. Combined with the perspective of universal science it is not only the world that we've alienated ourselves from but earth itself, connecting Descartes to science's Earth Alienation.

As science has become our method of understanding the world, and if science relies on mathematics as a form of systematizing universal language, then the relationship between mind & matter and world & man (after Descartes's separation of them), can be healed if we assume that science will eventually be able to give a theory of everything.

However, the 'being-in-the-world' we desire can't be constructed upon mathematics since, depending on where we apply it, we create different cognitive sense-positions. For example, the mathematics of outer space produces world- and earth alienation, while its implementation at the close-at-hand produces something like the geocentric perspective.

But all of this is theoretic speculation (that's quite hard to understand or agree with) for however much we may try to mathematize the world it will never be able to uncover the Being behind the appearances, and it is just this Being that Arendt wants us to rediscover. The mathematical approach to discovering the truth of "why there is instead of there being not" (Heidegger) is a dead-end:

Here again, we may for a moment rejoice in a refound unity of the universe, only to fall prey to the suspicion that what we have found may have nothing to do with either the macrocosmos or the microcosmos, that we deal only with the patterns of our own mind, the mind which designed the instruments and put nature under its conditions in the experiment—prescribed its laws to nature, in Kant's phrase—in which case it is really as though we were in the hands of an evil spirit who mocks us and frustrates our thirst for knowledge, so that wherever we search for that which we are not, we encounter only the patterns of our own minds (p.287f)

The issue is that all mathematic relations must be placed in a model, and that model can only be constructed by relying on our common sense. This creates a vicious circle:

[S]cientists formulate their hypotheses to arrange their experiments and then use these experiments to verify their hypotheses; during this whole enterprise, they obviously deal with a hypothetical nature. In other words, the world of the experiment seems always capable of becoming a man-made reality, and this, while it may increase man's power of making and acting, even of creating a world, far beyond what any previous age dared to imagine in dream and phantasy, unfortunately puts man back once more—and now even more forcefully—into the prison of his own mind, into the limitations of patterns he himself created. (p.287f)

This scares her. If our mind now has become capable of creating 'objective realities' by assuming realistic hypotheses (mathematical truths) that we then access in our 'subjectivities' (mathematical models) in order to establish the objectivity of the first hypothesis (re-hypothesis) then we have lost the capacity to think and ensured the total and absolute victory of a closed system of cognition. Our senses are abolished for the triumph of cognition:

With the disappearance of the sensually given world, the transcendent world disappears as well, and with it the possibility of transcending the material world in concept and thought. It is therefore not surprising that the new universe is not only "practically inaccessible but not even thinkable," for "however we think it, it is wrong; not perhaps quite as meaningless as a 'triangular circle,' but much more so than a 'winged lion.'"(p.288)

Chapter 41 – The Reversal of Contemplation and Action

Arendt begins this chapter by making an interesting claim in that everything she's described could've been avoided, that world and earth alienation didn't have to follow from the cosmological havoc brought by Galileo, Luther and Columbus. Yet, however, the victory of the Vita Activa over Vita Contemplativa was unavoidable.

She argues this by claiming that no scientific research is done to create tools or technology, but to find "useless knowledge." This seems to be a claim that scientific research was a practical form of the Vita Contemplativa, an attempt to understand the world, rather than a full activity of Homo Faber. She claims that:

[T]he watch, one of the first modern instruments, was not invented for purposes of practical life, but exclusively for the highly "theoretical" purpose of conducting certain experiments with nature. This invention, to be sure, once its practical usefulness became apparent, changed the whole rhythm and the very physiognomy of human life; but from the standpoint of the inventors, this was a mere incident. (p.289)

If we had remained purely practical beings, then we would never had begun to investigate the forces of electricity or radiation and the awesome powers and tools they've given us. And Arendt thinks this is good, for if we were we would never have been able to manage our technology, for responsibility demands more than just mere practicality.

Her point is that technology is a consequence of our thirst for knowledge, which, after Descartes and Galileo, could only be found in the activities of Homo Faber and work. Truth no longer discloses itself to our senses but must be teased out ("challenged forth" by Heidegger):

It was an instrument, the telescope, a work of man's hands, which finally forced nature, or rather the universe, to yield its secrets. The reasons for trusting doing and for

distrusting contemplation or observation became even more cogent after the results of the first active inquiries. After being and appearance had parted company and truth was no longer supposed to appear, to reveal and disclose itself to the mental eye of a beholder, there arose a veritable necessity to hunt for truth behind deceptive appearances. Nothing indeed could be less trustworthy for acquiring knowledge and approaching truth than passive observation or mere contemplation. In order to be certain one had to make sure, and in order to know one had to do. Certainty of knowledge could be reached only under a twofold condition: first, that knowledge concerned only what one had done himself—so that its ideal became mathematical knowledge, where we deal only with self-made entities of the mind—and second, that knowledge was of such a nature that it could be tested only through more doing. Since then, scientific and philosophic truth have parted company (p.290)

We can no longer contemplate the truth for it exists outside us. Thinking, the invisible and physically inactive but cognitively active dialogue between a person's "2-in-1", has become utterly pointless in trying to find truth by introspection into our bodies. Introspection is meaningless in relation to that which gives something tangible value in modernity, i.e., truth. This is, of course, a profoundly scary mentality which produces people like Eichmann and others who become incapable of using their cognition and 2-in-1 to realize the hollow core of grand ideologies.

Even worse, since the world around us has become unanchored by Galileo, and Arendt's contemporary Einstein, we have tried to look inside us to find some sort of stability on which to construct a stable reality – but this is equally pointless. Our insides are as moving and as mysterious as the modern world that surrounds us. As Arendt argued in the section on Action, we are inherently unpredictable even to ourselves, which is why promises are so important to create the stability social relations require. But however much we may try to create a science of ourselves through psychology, behavioral sciences, game theory, or economy we will always be trying to find an objective perspective on the human condition from inside the human condition itself: it's like trying to see your back without a mirror.

This argument is a nice reformulation of her claim that science and democracy is incompatible with one another. Earlier she claimed that science's attempt to explain human behavior was incompatible with Action, here she claims that science's need for a stable observer require the same 'taming' of our subjectivities.

Chapter 42 – The Reversal within the Vita Activa and the Victory of Homo Faber

Having established Vita Activas triumph over Vita Contemplativa, Arendt now claims that it was Homo Faber that led this revolution. In the section on work Arendt claims that tools are always known to us as their creators, which means that knowledge about reality, and truth, can be produced by tools instead of thoughts. This has led to modernity being a form of procession of tools made to create more tools to make our world understandable to us.

But that mainly relates to physics and other sciences related to the abstract forces of our world, when it comes to biology and natural sciences, we must instead *treat everything as tools* to be reverse-engineered to be understandable and cognitive to us. This is because the Homo Faber worldview is distinct in its approach to the world, for while philosophy approaches it to know "what" the world is, and theology and Action "who" it is, Homo Faber must know *How* it is.

We reached this situation as Homo Faber, who became our main activity to know the world, can only work through *processes* from A to B, as claimed in the section on Work:

The shift from the "why" and "what" to the "how" implies that the actual objects of knowledge can no longer be things or eternal motions but must be processes, and that the object of science therefore is no longer nature or the universe but the history, the story of the coming into being, of nature or life or the universe. (p.299)

Being (*dasein*), which we previously accessed through the combined activities of Action and contemplation, became a *Process* so that we must explain everything by accessing its history in Homo Faber's A-to-B logic. Being became *Becoming*.

This has made History paramount for our understanding of meaning and Being, for it is through History that the processes of objects makes sense, increasing our need to reverse-engineer everything around us to disclose its natural history and the dynamic or force that *made* it into what it is.

This was inevitably also applied on humans, ending in Hobbes attempt to make a new Human in his Leviathan:

The establishment of the Commonwealth, the human creation of "an artificial man," amounts to the building of an "automaton [an engine] that moves [itself] by springs and wheels as doth a watch." In other words, the process which, as we saw, invaded the natural sciences through the experiment, through the attempt to imitate under artificial conditions the process of "making" by which a natural thing came into existence, serves as well or even better as the principle for doing in the realm of human affairs. (p.299)

It is this attempt to *make* a political society through the application of philosophy that made politics lose its possibilities. When our politics is defined by an attempt at fabrication, *making*, then that political system will always have rationalistic approaches to human interchange, which is incompatible with the unpredictability of our Action and subjectivity.

The political philosophy of the modern age, whose greatest representative is still Hobbes, founders on the perplexity that modern rationalism is unreal and modern realism is irrational—which is only another way of saying that reality and human reason have parted company. (p.300)

The impossibility of changing the foundation of our political system, which would require a complete change in epistemology and ontology from the Homo Faber investigative Vita Activa, made it the philosophers' role to find the rationality behind the unpredictability of human action and succession of human events. This was first achieved by Hegel's historicism, in his attempt to solve the mystery of human Action.

Here Arendt makes a very peculiar and awkward shift back to ancient Greece, who also had the same attempt to solve the issue of political action. As mentioned in the section on Action, Plato's despair over the execution of Socrates made him try to philosophize politics, and thereby try to become a political craftsman, turning action into work.

There are however some crucial differences between Plato's project and Hobbes's, and the most important one is that Plato's end goal was to create a political system that enabled the highest

good in the possibility to contemplate over Being and its eternity⁵⁶ – not to create more fabrication, which is exactly what Homo Faber tries to do in his equalization of the fabrication-*process* and Being.

For this implied both that contemplation was no longer believed to yield truth and that it had lost its position in the *vita activa* itself and hence within the range of ordinary human experience. (p.304)

Modernity can now only explain Being by its history and fabrication, not in its own givenness, or very fact of existence.

Discussion questions:

1. What is the relationship between math and common sense?
 - a. “Facts not feelings” is a term you often hear in contemporary political discourse; does it somehow relate to Arendt’s point?
2. Would a complete ‘theory of everything’ be as scary as implies?
3. Is it really true that scientific research was done to find “useless knowledge”? Has it changed today?
4. Arendt claims that responsibility demands more than just mere practicality, what does she mean with this?
5. Arendt claims that the truth’s location in our surroundings has made introspection meaningless, yet she claims in all her works that contemplation and thinking is crucial for ethics and responsibility. How do we relate these two claims? Is ethics more important than truth, or is it a question of balancing these two separate and incompatible goods?
6. If Being is now a Becoming, what effect does that have? Why care?
7. Is History as important as Arendt implies it has become? In other works (*Life of the Mind*) she claims that history is inaccessible to our phenomenology and should be understood as a separate faculty following memory.
 - a. What then is the relation between *Becoming* and memory?
8. Is Arendt’s claim that we must first change our ontology and epistemology if we wish to change our politics reasonable?

Seminar 17: chapters 43-45

This is it! The grand finale – the last three chapters. I have said it many times before, but *this* must be Arendt at her most dystopian with the possibility of hope in *Natality* and *Thinking*, as we shall see in the very last quote of the book, a brilliant one that discloses so much about Arendt’s understanding of things and the world.

⁵⁶ It seems that Arendt would even appreciate Medieval politics of the contemplation of God over modernity.

Major themes

- The end of all values other than life
- Christianity's qualified form of life-politics, and modernity's devalued form of life-politics
- Life Politics as labor's victory over Homo Faber
- Homo Faber's internal contradiction and its inevitable defeat
- The massified society of life-politics, the triumph of *Becoming* and process.
- Process humanity as the death of politics and human dignity
- Thinking as a greater activity than Action

Chapter 43 – The Defeat of Homo Faber and the Principle of Happiness

As Arendt argued in the previous chapters, Homo Faber is now the premier human activity to know the world and ourselves – but in this chapter she sets out to prove that this isn't true anymore, Homo Faber's inner contradictions makes it unsustainable.

But, before making the situation even worse, Arendt makes sure to point out that a society based on Work isn't something we should be too enthusiastic about either.

And, indeed, among the outstanding characteristics of the modern age from its beginning to our own time we find the typical attitudes of homo faber: his instrumentalization of the world, his confidence in tools and in the productivity of the maker of artificial objects; his trust in the all-comprehensive range of the means-end category, his conviction that every issue can be solved and every human motivation reduced to the principle of utility; his sovereignty, which regards everything given as material and thinks of the whole of nature as of "an immense fabric from which we can cut out whatever we want to resew it however we like"; his equation of intelligence with ingenuity, that is, his contempt for all thought which cannot be considered to be "the first step . . . for the fabrication of artificial objects, particularly of tools to make tools, and to vary their fabrication indefinitely"; finally, his matter-of-course identification of fabrication with action (p.205)

Homo Faber's ordering of things may have begun with science, where the object under observation become systematized and reduced into a process – but it has also begun to bleed into all other social spheres. Our economists do the same, where the change of some leverages of rent sets into motion processes that change entire global monetary systems. Arendt even claims that the same systematization and process-reduction happened in modern philosophy that has made Man the standard of all things in the post-cartesian subjectivism.

... But all of this is a past that Arendt believe we will leave behind for something even more dystopic – the life-politics of the *animal laborans*. She claims that Homo Faber can't sustain itself and has already begun to collapse in her age. The argument is quite complicated, but I believe it is as follows.

As Arendt claimed earlier in the book, work require an absolute in our cognitive process of creating an item through a model. This is why work became foundational for truth in our post-cartesian skeptical cosmology. However, this absolute cannot survive the capitalist exchange society that turn all values first into interchangeability (into market goods), then into relativity (only market valuation) and ultimately devaluation (no value outside market). This means that work has two contradictory forces:

1. It makes everything into a process, as argued in previous chapters
2. It requires an exchange market for valuation, which inevitably leads into devaluation of all values

Homo faber, in other words, as he arose from the great revolution of modernity, though he was to acquire an undreamed-of ingenuity in devising instruments to measure the infinitely large and the infinitely small, was deprived of those permanent measures that precede and outlast the fabrication process and form an authentic and reliable absolute with respect to the fabricating activity. (p.307)

While not said in the book this is a central connection to Arendt's analysis of totalitarianism. In *Origins of Totalitarianism* she argues that the totalitarian movements were a way of recreating value in reaction to the nihilist devaluation of everything. If we are to use a dialectic critique of totalitarianism we may argue that the contradiction of a process of a devalued future led into an antithesis in the totalitarian movement that tries to reestablish value through another process, trying to counter the thesis without breaking its paradigm.

Getting back to the chapter, we now have a conflict in cosmology. If our way of knowing the world through Homo Faber is defeated by its own process, then modernity's world alienation and Archimedean Point has become more foundational for our worldview than the Homo Faber cosmology. This can be seen as economy, science, and philosophy, who rely on World Alienation and Archimedean Points, began to systematize the world given to our senses by Homo Faber:

It is as though in the latent seventeenth-century conflict between the two possible methods to be derived from the Galilean discovery, the method of the experiment and of making on one hand and the method of introspection on the other, the latter was to achieve a somewhat belated victory. (p.312)

This is however no solution to Homo Faber's problem of processual understanding of value, for the reduction of the world into a systematized science provides even *less* value than Homo Faber's inevitable devaluation. The scientification of the world and society is non-normative and can only leave us with Bentham's utilitarian "happiness" as the ultimate value.

This horrifies Arendt. Pain and Pleasure are based on the body, and any person who only pursues pain or pleasure can never develop any higher achievements than internal experiences, which makes a society of pleasure/pain massified. Here one can see Arendt's Nietzschean influence, she agrees with him that a society that bases their values on the body over their achievements is "the last man." In fact, in her essay *On Violence*, Arendt claims that pain is de-politicizing since it forces our Being's intentionality toward our body and inner suffering.

Pain is the only inner sense found by introspection which can rival in independence from experienced objects the self-evident certainty of logical and arithmetical reasoning. While this ultimate foundation of hedonism in the experience of pain is true for both its ancient and modern varieties, in the modern age it acquires an altogether different and much stronger emphasis. For here it is by no means the world, as in antiquity, that drives man into himself to escape the pains it may inflict, under which circumstance both pain and pleasure still retain a good deal of their worldly significance. Ancient world alienation in all its varieties— from stoicism to epicureanism down to hedonism and cynicism— had been inspired by a deep mistrust of the world and moved by a vehement impulse to withdraw from worldly involvement, from the trouble and pain it inflicts, into the security of an inward realm

in which the self is exposed to nothing but itself. Their modern counterparts—puritanism, sensualism, and Bentham's hedonism—on the contrary, were inspired by an equally deep mistrust of man as such; they were moved by doubt of the adequacy of the human senses to receive reality, the adequacy of human reason to receive truth, and hence by the conviction of the deficiency or even depravity of human nature. (p.310)

Just like pleasure/pain is bodily, so is mathematics and logic. Arendt claim that their premises are connected to the biological structure of our brain, and thereby is as massifying, in fact, they have the same world alienating effects as the ancient world's stoics' abuse of will to reduce all sensually given impression into a learned system.

All of this is to support the claim that "happiness" is the highest form of value in modernity, as the result of a bodily society, but Arendt claims that it is even worse, for happiness is just an expression of the imperative of our biological ego. That which makes us happy has been decided by the evolutionary forces to preserve our species, and happiness is therefore nothing but the interests of *animal laborans*.

For what matters today is not the immortality of life, but that life is the highest good. (p.319)

And when politics is about life then there is no value at all. Life is factual, and not normative.

Chapter 44 – Life as the Highest Good

The entirety of The Human Condition has thus far been about the historical and political background that enabled a society of life-politics, but that does not matter much for Arendt, for the problems and threats brought by it are too grave to just be of interest for an analyst or historian.

The defeat homo faber may be explainable in terms of the initial transformation of physics into astrophysics, of natural sciences into a "universal" science. What still remains to be explained is why this defeat ended with a victory of the animal laborans; why, with the rise of the vita activa, it was precisely the laboring activity that was to be elevated to the highest rank of man's capacities or, to put it another way, why within the diversity of the human condition with its various human capacities it was precisely life that overruled all other considerations (p.313)

Regardless the background of this situation, life was chosen due to the western world's structural legacy of Christian theology in the sacrosanctity of Life. Here Arendt seems to try and re-connect the argument to the very first chapters of the book where she claims that the ancients' worldliness was changed to vita contemplativa by Christianity, and that the ancient's pursue of immortality became the Christians pursue of eternity in heaven.

Aspiration toward immortality could now only be equated with vainglory; such fame as the world could bestow upon man was an illusion, since the world was even more perishable than man, and a striving for worldly immortality was meaningless, since life itself was immortal (p.316).

But Arendt makes a further distinction that she didn't include in the beginning. The Christians valuation of individual life made the person higher than the survival of the political unit, which is foretold to eventually perish anyhow. On the other side of the extreme were the ancients'

valuation of the collective life over the individual life as it is only the political community that can ensure the immortality of the individual.

This results in a weird situation where the confirmation of each man's eventual death become the premise for worldliness and political engagement, while the Christians have it the opposite way:

The point is that Christianity—except for heretical and gnostic speculations—always insisted that life, though it had no longer a final end, still has a definite beginning. Life on earth may be only the first and the most miserable stage of eternal life; it still is life, and without this life that will be terminated in death, there cannot be eternal life. This may be the reason for the undisputable fact that only when the immortality of individual life became the central creed of Western mankind, that is, only with the rise of Christianity, did life on earth also become the highest good of man (p.316)

In this way they both practiced a politics that had a fundamental concern for biological life. The ancients in that life was short and must be made immortal to have had any value, and the Christians in that life was, per definition of being Divine in origin, an authority in itself and thereby qualified instead of the mere biological existence that the ancients tried to raise themselves from.

In this way life was never seen as merely instrumental in the growth-process of society. For the ancients' life was instrumentally valuable because it could become immortal, for us moderns' life is good because each person contributes to the higher prosperity (the de-politicized "happiness") of society.

Chapter 45 – The Victory of the Animal Laborans

In this final chapter of the book Arendt begins by summarizing the argument that the Animal Laborans won over Action and Homo Faber due to secularization, cartesian doubt, and the loss of immortality, but she also makes an interesting observation that, at a first glance, we seem to have returned to the same worldview as the ancients had, but that we just lack the same worldliness that defined their system of values (immortality). So, while we live in the world and have passed beyond the Vita Contemplativa, we have not found the world as the ancients found it.

Modern man, when he lost the certainty of a world to come, was thrown back upon himself and not upon this world; far from believing that the world might be potentially immortal, he was not even sure that it was real. And in so far as he was to assume that it was real in the uncritical and apparently unbothered optimism of a steadily progressing science, he had removed himself from the earth to a much more distant point than any Christian otherworldliness had ever removed him (p.320)

It seems that our world has been given to us against our will, in that the secularization, and violence done by modernity on our cosmology, has thrown us back on a world we're still trying to escape with our instrumentalized cartesian doubt – indeed, if the recreation of the public sphere can be achieved through Action and our subjectivity then the salvation of the ancient value-system shouldn't be further away than changing the way we understand being. However, the issues are too structural to be solved by us just changing our way of being. The newly established life-politics has made us lose contact with the very idea of having a Being, so to

reconnect our Being to the world we need to first find a new worldliness beyond science's systematizing and "dissecting" cosmology. This art of life must be achieved despite modernity's body-oriented life-politics.

One such attempt could've been Marxism, but Arendt doesn't think that finding worldliness and Being in sociality is a solution.

Socialized mankind is that state of society where only one interest rules, and the subject of this interest is either classes or man-kind, but neither man nor men. (p.321)

As she argued in the section on Action, Being must be found in the unique and plural individuals. Seeking it through socialization is a contradiction for it achieves the same de-individualizing as the massified life-politics, which is based on the biological force (*biological process/becoming*) that reduces our qualified life (Zoe, as the ancients would call it) into mere biological existence (Bios).

In fact, in a society of life-politics human life has taken on the characteristics of labor: something circular and pointless, which exists for a brief and unnoteworthy period to then disappear without a trace. Whatever we do or try to achieve can only be understood as a biological motive stemming from our reduction into biological entities:

What was not needed, not necessitated by life's metabolism with nature, was either superfluous or could be justified only in terms of a peculiarity of human as distinguished from other animal life—so that Milton was considered to have written his *Paradise Lost* for the same reasons and out of similar urges that compel the silkworm to produce silk. [...] Thought itself, when it became "reckoning with consequences," became a function of the brain, with the result that electronic instruments are found to fulfil these functions much better than we ever could. (p.321f)

But even if our lives have become *like* labor, not even labor as an activity can withstand life-politics for today (1958) labor has become mechanicalized, routinized, and rationalized into a functionality of the society-wide life-process of ever continuing growth – the laboring individuals without a public sphere has become a laboring and anonymous mass.

And if it is only Action that can be considered unexpected and miraculous, the reduction of humanity into laboring masses of unnoteworthy lives means human history has essentially ended and become a process:

The trouble with modern theories of behaviorism is not that they are wrong but that they could become true, that they actually are the best possible conceptualization of certain obvious trends in modern society. It is quite conceivable that the modern age—which began with such an unprecedented and promising outburst of human activity—may end in the deadliest, most sterile passivity history has ever known (p.322)

This quote is the central threat that Arendt presents in *The Human Condition* – and I think there is real truth to the statement. For when society and politics has become a mass of biological entities then everything must become a process of evolution or cyclical existences like a larva eventually becoming a butterfly. It's the absolute triumph of *Becoming* over *Being*. Science, our way of understanding reality, is one of the main issues that has caused this, we can't simply replace it, its knowledge-generation and the power it provide nation-states is connected to

global political dynamics, and it is at the same time the force that contributes to the "biologization" of human life and politics:

The reason why scientists can tell us about the "life" in the atom—where apparently every particle is "free" to behave as it wants and the laws ruling these movements are the same statistical laws which, according to the social scientists, rule human behavior and make the multitude behave as it must, no matter how "free" the individual particle may appear to be in its choices—the reason, in other words, why the behavior of the infinitely small particle is not only similar in pattern to the planetary system as it appears to us but resembles the life and behavior patterns in human society is, of course, that we look and live in this society as though we were as far removed from our own human existence as we are from the infinitely small and the immensely large which, even if they could be perceived by the finest instruments, are too far away from us to be experienced (p.323)

So, despite Arendt providing us hope in Natality, the outlook is dire for the future of humanity. For while the only unexpected thing we can expect from humanity is the unexpected discoveries from scientists who may stumble upon something that changes the cosmology and values of politics and science, they can never replace the Action they have made ontologically impossible:

But the action of the scientists, since it acts into nature from the standpoint of the universe and not into the web of human relationships, lacks the revelatory character of action as well as the ability to produce stories and become historical, which together form the very source from which meaningfulness springs into and illuminates human existence. In this existentially most important aspect, action, too, has become an experience for the privileged few, and these few who still know what it means to act may well be even fewer than the artists, their experience even rarer than the genuine experience of and love for the world (p.324)

Here, at the very end of the book, Arendt uses one of the key terms in The Human Condition's central message: "love for the world". For while action is a form of activity where you act into the world, it's an entirely different thing to *love* it, for as she claimed in the section of Action, love is to bind yourself to it in amazement, to make yourself indistinguishable from it. To do that in today's world one must not only overcome the "biologization" of oneself, but also the systematization of the world. It takes a double act of Nietzschean self-ennobling, revaluation of values, and the willing ignorance of scientific facts and systematization, but this is exactly what politics need but can't afford to do in the concert of nation-states.

With this work being a masterpiece of political thinking Arendt makes an acknowledgement of her own achievement as the closing statement in the book, for she claims that while the Vita Activa is an important essence of human existence, she has proven that *thinking* is an even greater achievement than all activities in the Vita Activa, for she has *thought what we are doing* and proven that the activities in society can be described if one goes into contemplation and separates oneself from the world and gaze upon it with the "wind of thoughts" that removes all ideologies and reduces us to our naked being – from which we can view the world and create Natality. And I am pretty sure that Arendt writing this book is one of the greatest achievements of Natality.

Never was Arendt more active than when she did nothing, never was she less alone than when she was by herself.

Discussion questions:

1. Where do we start if we want to move beyond life-politics?
2. Arendt is normative in her fear for life-politics, why can't we just be happy with a short, temporary life of pleasant experiences?
3. Is her equation of life-politics and Marxist socialized humanity reasonable?
4. If the ancients' acknowledgement of their inevitable bodily death made them seek authenticity in great deeds and action... is Arendt making a synthesis of her own Nality and Heidegger's being-towards-death?
5. Arendt's claim that our selection of Life as the highest value is partly because our Christian inheritance seems historically naïve – the Christian church has been quite happy to end lives and send people to their judgement.
6. It seems to me that the hyper-individualized society of today should provide quite good opportunities to recreate the ancients' strive for immortality, but it still seems that we seek greatness in careers, salaries, wealth so we can enjoy "the good life" – how can we understand modern pursuits without the pain/pleasure principle? What other goals are there?
7. The book we have read makes the claim that Action creates values, but that thinking and writing can be made to set a new foundation for Action, as seen in this book – how do we understand this? Is thinking a form of work, or is this work only the reification and durability of Arendt's thinking? If that is the case, could a wholly new foundation for the public sphere be made if we were to destroy all artifacts of work? Seems there should be more to it than this.